

Analyses of the informational needs of the
Web User Interfaces of Repertoires of European poetry

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Abstract

This document is framed in the work of defining a domain model (or data model) for the European poetry. This work includes the study of the data structures of several databases of repertoires elected as representatives of the European Poetry. Some of these repertoires did not make available its data structure so in order to overcome this absence of information the work-team used other approaches with various techniques.

The map <https://goo.gl/00mqhI> presents the repertoires and the phases of the analysis.

This document presents the analysis of the graphical user interface (GUI) of 1) the repertoires that are in the Web of Documents that did not provide its database structure, and 2) the repertoires whose database structure analysis was not enough to understand its data model.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

POSTDATA is an European Research Council Starting Grant research project that aims to provide means for the European Poetry to be able to publish data as linked open data. One of the milestones of the project is the development of a domain model, a data model that expresses the informational needs of this community of practice.

The work to define the data model started with the selection of a sample of repertoires that represent the European poetry in what concerns traditions, language and period. The repertoires were contacted by means of its representatives and they were asked to send the database structures of their repertoires. Most of them sent these information but some did not. The work team built a first draft version of the domain model out of the analyses of these database structures. This step was followed by an informational needs analysis of the Graphical User Interfaces (GUI) of the repertoires that did not send the database structures.

This document presents this informational needs analyses. Each analyses comprises a functionality analysis focused only on the data needs of the GUI. For each repertoire, the data needs of the GUI are confronted with the draft data model already built. If the model responds to the need, nothing more is done. If the model does not respond to the specific need, the data model is modified to integrate the specific requirement.

1.1 How to read the tables

The first row of each table with the informational needs analysis looks like the one presented in Table 1.1. The meaning of each column is as follows:

- Label: a label given to the data need (string),
- Cardinality: number of times the data need can be repeated. “1” when it can not be repeat, or “M”, when it can be repetead. Also called “Card.” to save space,
- Link: when in the interface the data need presents a link to another window (boolean)
- Comments: any comment that might be important, such as e.g. if link=true, indicates the Window that will be open, or any other comment
- DM: the property of the domain model that responds to the data need

Table 1.1: The first line of each table

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
-------	-------------	------	----------	----

When the draft data model is changed to integrate a data need that was identified on one GUI, the text or the cell is in green.

As a final remark it is important to say that the screen shots of the windows of the GUI presented on this document represent a sample. This windows do not represent all the possibilities of the window, they depend on the resources that are being requested on the queries. Some of the windows are very large, it would not be possible to present them in such a document.

1.2 Conventions

Each table is “positioned” in a certain entity of the DM. That entity is the starting point for the analyses - the name of the information is provided in the paragraph before the table. The column “DM” of Table 1.1 presents the correspondent DM property for the data need. We have used the following conventions:

- If the data need corresponds to a property of a entity, the name of the property is written followed by a point and the name of the entity (e.g. name.Place: the property “name” of the entity “Place”)
- If the data need expresses a connection between two entities, the name of the first entity is followed by a property that is preceded and followed by the symbol “-”, and it continues with the name of the second entity (e.g. Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction: “Opus” and “Redaction” are connected through the property “isRealisedThrough”)
- When the property to be used to describe the data need belongs to an entity different from the one in which the table is positioned, the DM cell presents first the path to arrive to the entity (with the same convention explained in the previous entry), followed by the symbol “+” and the name of the property (with the same convention detailed in the first entry) (e.g. The starting point of the Table is “Redaction” the property is the siglum of the Witness: Redaction-interprets-Witness + siglum.Witness)
- On occasion, one single data need needs more than one property of the DM to be completely described, or there are several options depending on data fields or interpretations of the data that can not be expressed with a simple analyses of the GUI. In such cases, the DM cell is divided in as many rows as necessary to decribe the data need.

Chapter 2

MedDB - Base de datos da Lírca Profana Galego-Portuguesa

URL: <http://www.cirp.es/bdo/med/meddb.html>

2.1 Informational Needs

The MedDB entry page provides two types of search: the simple and the advanced. Window 2.1 (Figure 2.1) presents the entry page for a simple search (*Buscas simples*). This Window allows the users to search by author (*Trobador*) and by poem (*Cantiga*).

Figure 2.1: Window2.1: MedDB Frontpage for simple searches

Window 2.2 (Figure 2.2) presents the default view of the advanced search¹. This advanced search window provides four search possibilities: Poem (*Cantigas*), Stanzas (*Estrofas*), Lines (*Versos*) and Authors (*Trobadores*). The default view presents a search by *Cantiga* (Poem) with the following options:

- by author (*Trobador*)
- by type of authorship² (*Tipo de Autoría*)
- by number of the *Cantiga*³ (*Nº de Cantiga*). Number of six digits, three of them correspond to the identifier the author has in Tavani's repertoire and the remaining three reference the number of the *cantiga*. This last number enumerates the *cantigas* by the same author, listing them in alphabetically order by incipit
- by incipit
- by poem in the manuscript⁴ (*Cantiga no manuscrito*)

¹To access this Webpage the user needs to register and login. The registration is free.

²https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=394338540744288609&p_session=801355036897716461

³https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=408989671063046304&p_session=801355036897716461

⁴https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=408982875503046274&p_session=801355036897716461

- by folio in the manuscript (*Folio no manuscrito*). The number of the folio in a certain manuscript: siglum of the manuscript, number of folio, and “r” or “v” meaning front or back. E.g. “A20r”
- by number of stanzas (*Número de estrofas*). The total number of stanzas of the cantiga
- by interstrophic relations (*FRI – Forma de relación interestrofica*). This field has a controlled entry of terms
- by theme of the *cantiga* (*Tema*). This field has a controlled entry of terms
- by category⁵ (*categoría*). This field has a controlled entry of terms
- by contents of the *cantiga* (*Texto cantiga*). For searching textual patterns in the contents of the *cantiga*

The screenshot shows the MedDB Frontpage for an advanced search in the 'Cantigas' section. The interface is divided into two main panels: 'Buscas' (Search) and 'Filtros' (Filters).

Buscas (Search):

- Buttons: Reiniciar, Buscar
- Trobador: igual (dropdown), text input
- Tipo autoría: igual (dropdown), Calquera (dropdown)
- Nº Cantiga: igual (dropdown), Calquera (dropdown)
- Incipit: como (dropdown), text input
- Cantiga no manuscrito: como (dropdown), text input
- Folio no manuscrito: como (dropdown), text input
- Número de estrofas: como (dropdown), text input
- FRI: igual (dropdown), Calquera (dropdown)
- Tema: igual (dropdown), Calquera (dropdown)
- Categoría: contén (dropdown), text input
- Texto cantiga: contén (dropdown), text input
- Conector: Calquera condición, Todas as condicións

Filtros (Filters):

- Tipo cantiga:
 - Mestria
 - Non aplicable
 - Refrán
 - Intercalar
- de seguir:
 - SI
 - NON
- Outras linguas:
 - SI
 - NON
- Música:
 - SI
 - NON
- Espazo música:
 - SI
 - NON

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Figure 2.2: Window2.2: MedDB Frontpage for an advanced search – default view “Cantigas”

Together with all these possibilities, there is also the option to turn on the following filters:

- Type of *cantiga* (*Tipo cantiga*). Controlled list: “Mestria”, “Refrán” or “Intercalar”. There is also the possibility to choose “Non aplicable”
- *de seguir*. Boolean
- Other languages (*outras linguas*). Boolean. If “yes” the system only searches for the *cantigas* that are in other languages than “Galician”
- Music (*Música*). Boolean. If “yes” the system only searches for the *cantigas* that have musical notation
- Space for music (*Espazo música*). Boolean. If “yes” the system only searches for *cantigas* whose witness or witnesses contain space for musical notation

As mentioned above, Window 2.2 also provides three additional buttons that enable an advanced search on Stanzas (*Estrofas*), Lines (*Versos*) and Authors (*Trobadores*).

If the user clicks on the button “Estrofas”, the system opens Window 2.3 (Figure 2.3). The searchable fields are:

- Author (*Trobador*). It presents a list of the names of all authors
- Number of *cantiga* (*Nº de Cantiga*). A list of the numbers is provided
- Reference to Tavani’s repertoire (*Número de Esquema*). A list of the references is provided
- Rhyme scheme (*esquema rimático*)
- Metrical scheme (*esquema métrico*)
- Total number of lines of the stanza (*Total versos*)

⁵https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=408982875503046274&p_session=801355036897716461

- Category (*Categoría*)⁶
- Number of stanzas (*Número estrofas*). This field allows the user to choose between a set of options such as “bigger than”, “smaller than”, “between” etc.
- *Cantiga* in the manuscript (*Cantiga no manuscrito*)
- Contents of the stanza (*Texto Estrofa*)

The user can select between “or” and “and” in all available options.

Together with all these possibilities, there is also the option to turn on the following filters:

- Type of *cantiga* (*Tipo cantiga*). Controlled list: “Mestria”, “Refrán” or “Intercalar”. The option “Non aplicable” is also available.
- Type of stanza (*Tipo estrofa*). Controlled list: “Estrofa”, “Finda”, “Refrán Inicial”, “Dístico inicial”, “Tetrástico Inicial” and “Hexástico Inicial”

Figure 2.3: Window2.3: after selecting the top button “Estrofas” from Window 2.2

Still on Window 2.2, if the user clicks on “Versos”, the system opens Window 2.4 (Figure 2.4). The searchable fields are:

- Author (*Trobador*). A list of the names of the authors available is provided
- Number of *cantiga* (*Nº de Cantiga*). A list of the numbers is provided
- Number of syllables (*Nº de Sílabas*)
- Rhyme ending (*Rima*)
- Rhyme word (*Palabra rimante*)
- Category (*Categoría*). The same as previously mentioned
- *Cantiga* in the manuscript (*Cantiga no manuscrito*)
- Contents of the line (*Texto Verso*)

The user can select between “or” and “and” on all the options.

Together with all these possibilities, there is also the option to turn on the following filters:

- Type of *cantiga* (*Tipo cantiga*). Controlled list: “Mestria”, “Refrán” or “Intercalar”. There is also the possibility to choose “Non aplicable”
- Type of stanza (*Tipo estrofa*). Controlled list: “Estrofa”, “Finda”, “Refrán Inicial”, “Dístico inicial”, “Tetrástico inicial” and “Hexástico inicial”
- Refrain (*Refrán*). Boolean. If “yes”, the system looks only for refrains, if “no”, the system looks for lines that are not part of a refrain

Still on Window 2.2, if the user clicks on “Trobadores”, the system opens Window 2.5 (Figure 2.5). This Window allows the user to search information concerning the authors of the *Cantigas*. The searchable fields that available:

⁶https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=408967377600996757&p_session=801355036897716461

Figure 2.4: Window2.4: after selecting the top button “Versos” from Window 2.2

- Name of the author (*Nome*). A drop-down list with all the names
- Number of the author (*Número Trobador*). A drop-down list with all the identifiers and names of authors
- Origin (*Orixe*) of the author. A drop-down list with all places of origin
- Social status (*Condición social*) of the author. A drop-down list with every social status
- Period (*Período*). A list of ranges is provided: “1170-1220”; “1220-1240”; “1240-1300”; “1300-1350”; “1400-1480”

The user can select between “or” and “and” on all the options.

Figure 2.5: Window2.5: after selecting the top button “Trobadores” from Window 2.2

2.1.1 Simple Search

Search *Cantiga* (by incipit)

Window 2.1 (Figure 2.1) allows the selection of a specific *Cantiga* from the drop-down list of every incipit. After selecting a *Cantiga*, the system updates the window with the result as shown on Window 2.6 (Figure 2.6). This

window presents the following information about the selected *cantiga*:

- Authorship (*Autoría*)
 - Type (*Tipo*). The type of authorship: “Autor” (one known author), “Tenzón” (dialogue between two trobadours), “Doble atribución” (two possible authors)
 - Number (*Nº*). Number of three digits which correspond to the identifier the author has in Tavani’s repertoire
 - Name (*Nome*). The name of the author
 - Short name of the author
 - Origin (*Orixe*). Nationality of the author
 - Reliability (*Fiabilidade*). Reliability of the information about the origin
 - Social status (*Condición Social*)
 - Activity (*Actividade*). Period when the author was working
 - Period (*Período*). In which period the author is catalogued (the period is defined by the project –four periods of production are identified)
 - Biography (*Biografía*). A biography of the author
- Text (*Texto Cantiga*)
 - The complete text of the *cantiga*

The screenshot shows a web application interface with a search bar at the top. Below the search bar, there is a section titled "Selección" with two dropdown menus: "Trobador" (set to "Todos") and "Cantiga" (set to "Vou-m' eu, fremeosa, pera 'l-rey"). Below this, there are two columns: "Autoría" and "Texto Cantiga".

Autoría

Tipo **Autor**
 Nº **117**
 Nome **Pedr' Eanes Solaz [PEaSol]**
 Orixe **GALEGA (Fiabilidade: probable)**
 Condición social **nobre**
 Actividade **1245-1275**
 Período **1240-1300**

Probablemente, trobador galego, xa que Solaz é un topónimo galego e o trobador está integrado no que constitúe un vestixio de Cancioneiro Aristocrático. Este rango social motiva que non se poida identificar o noso autor co "Pedro Anes, jogral" mencionado logo da morte da súa muller Umaca en 1268, a pesar de que se adecúa á cronoloxía (mediados do século) derivada da súa colocación. As súas cantigas de escamio non conteñen datos históricos que nos permitan unha mellor definición da súa persoa e dos ambientes en que desenvolveu as súa actividade poética (cf. Menéndez Pidal, que lle deu unha orixe galega ao relacionar a referencia a unha "freira de Nogueira", contida nunha das súas cantigas de amor, co mosteiro de Nogueira, Pontevedra; Michaélis 1904, II: 448-450; Menéndez Pidal 1991: 224; Nunes 1973, I: 212-215; Tavani 1991: 312-313, que, baseándose no seu apelido, visto como un alcume, lle deron unha condición de xogar ou de segrel).

Tipo **Doble atribución**
 Nº **157**
 Nome **Anónimo [anonim]**
 Período
 Biografía

Texto Cantiga

Vou-m' eu, fremeosa, pera 'l-rey:
 por vós, u fôr, penad' irey
 d' amor; d' amor; d' amor; d' amor;
 por vós, senhor; d' amor; d' amor;

Vou-m' eu a la corte morar:
 por vós, u fôr, ey a penar
 d' amor; d' amor; d' amor; d' amor;
 por vós, senhor; d' amor; d' amor;

E se vos non vir, que farey?
 Cuydand' en vós, marrer-vos-ey
 d' amor; d' amor; d' amor; d' amor;
 por vós, senhor; d' amor; d' amor;

Figure 2.6: Window2.6: The result after selecting a *Cantiga* from the drop-down list of Window 2.1

Search Author

When selecting a specific *Trobador* (author name) from the drop-down list of Window1 (Figure 2.1), the system updates the window with the result as shown on Window 2.7 – Figure 2.7). This Window presents information about the selected *Trobador* which is exactly the same as Window 2.6 (Figure 2.6) with the complete text of

the *Cantiga*.

Selección

Trobador [025] Don Denis ▾ **Cantiga** ▾

Autoría

Tipo Autor
Nº 025
Nome Don Denis [Den]
Orixe PORTUGUESA (Fiabilidade: coflecida)
Condición social nobre
Actividade 1279-1325
Periodo 1240-1300

Biografía

Fillo de Afonso III de Portugal e de Dona Beatriz de Castela e, polo tanto, neto de Afonso X, naceu en 1261. Reinou desde 1279 ata 1325, data da súa morte. Continuou a liña iniciada polo seu pai, convertendo a súa corte en fogar para moitos trobadores (cf. números 9, 29, 30, 35, 48, 61, 66, 75, 82, 96, 100, 118, 133, 141) e no núcleo de supervivencia da tradición lírica galego-portuguesa (Tavari 1991: 282). O feito de ter un mestre francés (Aimeric d' Erbrard) púxoo en contacto coas líricas de oc e de oïl, contacto favorecido polo seu casamento con Isabel de Aragón, educada nunha corte onde foran adoptadas a lingua e a poesía occitanas (Gonçalves, DLMGP, 206). Froito destas ensinanzas son as súas 137 cantigas, que o converten no trobador con máis produción da nosa lírica. Emprendeu unha política cultural que desembocou na aparición de novos xéneros na literatura portuguesa (as *Livros de Linhagens* e a historiografía), na tradución ao portugués de non poucos textos históricos e xurídicos (as *Partidas de Afonso X*) e na creación da Universidade en 1290. Tivo que facer fronte, no tempo que durou o seu reinado, ás continuas pretensións de enriquecemento da nobreza, causa pola que prosegue o proceso centralizador, iniciado polo seu pai, coas *Inquirições* que ordenou entre 1284 e 1317 (Oliveira, 1994: 328). Os derradeiros anos do seu goberno están marcados polo enfrontamento entre o seu primoxénito (futuro Afonso IV) e o seu fillo bastardo, Afonso Sanchez (cf. nº 9).

Figure 2.7: Window2.7: after selecting “Don Denis” from the drop-down list “Trobadores” of Window 2.1

After selecting the *Trobador*, a filter is applied to the drop-down list of *Cantigas*. The user can then select a incipit to see the text of the chosen *cantiga*, and, on the same page, the system updates the window (see Window 2.8 on Figure 2.8) with the new information which is exactly the same as Window 2.6 (Figure 2.6).

Selección

Trobador [025] Don Denis Cantiga Que soidade de mha senhor ei

Autoría

Tipo **Autor**
Nº **025**
Nome **Don Denis [Den]**
Orixe **PORTUGUESA (Fiabilidade: cofiecida)**
Condición social **nobre**
Actividade **1279-1325**
Período **1240-1300**

Biografía

Fillo de Afonso III de Portugal e de Dona Beatriz de Castela e, polo tanto, neto de Afonso X, naceu en 1261. Reinou desde 1279 ata 1325, data da súa morte. Continuou a liña iniciada polo seu pai, convertendo a súa corte en fogar para moitos trobadores (cf. números 9, 29, 30, 35, 48, 61, 66, 75, 82, 96, 100, 118, 133, 141) e no núcleo de supervivencia da tradición lírica galego-portuguesa (Tavani 1991: 282). O feito de ter un mestre francés (Aimeric d' Erbrard) puxoo en contacto coas líricas de oc e de oit, contacto favorecido polo seu casamento con Isabel de Aragón, educada nunha corte onde foran adoptadas a lingua e a poesía occitanas (Gonçalves, DLMGP, 206). Froito destas ensinanzas son as súas 137 cantigas, que o converten no trobador con máis produción da nosa lírica. Empezou unha política cultural que desembocou na aparición de novos xéneros na literatura portuguesa (os *Livros de Lnhagens* e a historiografía), na tradución ao portugués de non poucos textos históricos e xurídicos (as *Partidas* de Afonso X) e na creación da Universidade en 1290. Tivo que facer fronte, no tempo que durou o seu reinado, ás continuas pretensións de enriquecemento da nobreza, causa pola que prossegue o proceso centralizador, iniciado polo seu pai, coas *Inquiriçoes* que ordenou entre 1284 e 1317 (Oliveira 1994: 328). Os derradeiros anos do seu goberno están marcados polo enfrontamento entre o seu primoxénito (futuro Afonso IV) e o seu fillo bastardo, Afonso Sanchez (cf. nº 9).

Texto Cantiga

Que soidade de mha senhor ei
quando me nembra d' ela qual a vi,
e que me nembra que bem a oi
falar; e por quanto bem d' ela sei,
rog' eu a Deus que end' a o poder,
que mh a leixe, se lhi prouguer, veer

Cedo; ca pero mi nunca faz bem,
se a nom vir, nom me posso guardar
d' ensandecer ou morrer com pesar;
e porque ela tod' em poder tem,
rogu' eu a Deus que end' a o poder,
que mh a leixe, se lhi prouguer, veer

Cedo; ca tal a fez nostro senhor,
de quantas outras no mundo som
nom lhi fez par, a la minha fe, nom;
e poi-la fez das melhores melhor,
rogu' eu a Deus que end' a o poder,
que mh a leixe, se lhi prouguer, veer

Cedo; ca tal a quizo Deus fazer,
que se a nom vir, nom posso viver.

Figure 2.8: Window 2.8: after selecting “Que soidade de mnha senhor ei” from the dropdown “Cantigas” of Window 2.7

2.1.2 Advanced Search

In *Cantiga*

Window 2.2 provides, by default, search fields by *Cantigas*. Selecting a set of criteria (e.g. Trobador “Afonso Sanchez” and “autor” as the type of authorship) the system opens Window 2.9 (Figure 2.9) with the result of the search organised in a table.

Window 2.9 presents a table with as many rows as the number of *Cantigas* that match the criteria of the search; each row presents information about the *Cantiga* at hand. The information for each *cantiga* is:

- Number of the *cantiga* (*Cantiga*)
- Incipit
- Short name of the author (*Trobador*)
- Number of stanzas of the *cantiga* (*Nº Estrofas*)
- Type of *cantiga* (*Tipo*)
- Category of the *cantiga* (*Categoría*)
- For each row, there is a link (“VER”) that opens Window 2.10 (Figure 2.10)

Window 2.10 (Figure 2.10) presents the following information:

- The complete text of the *cantiga*, the internal number of the *cantiga*, its incipit, the number of stanzas, the language (“yes”, if it is not Galician-Portuguese, otherwise “no”), if it is a *cantiga* “de seguir” or not, the type of *cantiga* and the category of the *cantiga*. The category of the *cantiga* is a code⁷
- Authorship (*Autoría*). Shortname and complete name. The internal number of the author. The name of the author is a link that opens Window 2.11 (Figure 2.11).
- Information about the witnesses (manuscripts)

⁷https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/wwv_flow_item_help.show_help?p_item_id=408967377600996757&p_session=801355036897716461

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Inicio > Cantiga

Buscas

Reiniciar Buscar

Trobador igual Afonso Sanchez [009]

Tipo autoria igual Autor

Nº Cantiga igual Calquera

Incipt como

Cantiga no manuscrito como

Folio no manuscrito como

Número de estrofas como

FRI igual Calquera

Tema igual Calquera

Categoría contén

Texto cantiga contén

Conector Calquera condición Todas as condicións

Resultados

1 - 15 (15 cantigas)

ID	Cantiga	Incipt	Trobador	Nº Estrofas	Tipo	Categoría
[VER]	009001	Afons' Afoneses, batiçar queredes	AfSchz	3	Non aplicable	E EP
[VER]	009002	Conhocedes a donzela	AfSchz	4	Mestria	E EP
[VER]	009003	De vos servir, mia senhor, non me val	AfSchz	3	Mestria	A
[VER]	009004	Dizia la fremosinha	AfSchz	4	Intercalar	M
[VER]	009005	Estes que m' ora tolhen mia senhor	AfSchz	2	Mestria	A
[VER]	009006	Mia senhor, quen me vos guarda	AfSchz	3	Mestria	A
[VER]	009007	Muitos me dizen que servi doado	AfSchz	3+F	Mestria	A
[VER]	009008	Pero eu dixee, mia senhor	AfSchz	3	Mestria	A
[VER]	009009	Pois vós per i máis de valer cuidades	AfSchz	3+F	Mestria	E EL
[VER]	009010	Quand', amiga, meu amigo veer	AfSchz	1	Non aplicable	M
[VER]	009011	Sempre vos eu doutra ren máis amei	AfSchz	3+F	Refrán	A
[VER]	009012	Tan grave dia que vos conhoci	AfSchz	3+F	Mestria	A
[VER]	009013	Ôu ric' ome a que ôu trobador	AfSchz	3	Mestria	E ES
[VER]	009014	Vaasco Martiz, pois vós trabalhadese	AfSchz	4+2F	Mestria	T EP
[VER]	009015	Vedes, amigos, que de perdas ei	AfSchz	1	Non aplicable	A

1 - 15 (15 cantigas)

Figure 2.9: Window2.9: result of search implemented on Window 2.2

- The “siglum” of the manuscript (first letter of the “Folio” field) where the Witness is, the page in the Manuscript (the numbers after the siglum in the “Folio” field), the number of the *cantiga* in the manuscript (“Num.”) and whether the *cantiga* has music or if there is a space in the witness for the music notation
- A link to the image of the witness of the *Cantiga* that opens Window 2.12 (Figure 2.12).
- A link to notes by Colocci (*nota colocciana*) that opens Window 2.13 (Figure 2.13).
- A link to the explanatory rubric (*Rúbrica explicativa*) present in some witnesses that opens Window 2.14 (Figure 2.14) with its contents.
- Information about interstrophic relations (*formas de relación interestróficas*). Sometimes this information provides a link that opens Window 2.15 (Figure 2.15) for an example of other *Cantiga*.
- The theme (*Tema*) of the *cantiga*.
- Information about the editions. The edition followed and additional critical, paleographic and divulgative (educational) editions.

Window 2.2.10 integrates a navigation bar (see detail in Figure 2.16) on the top left of the window.

This navigation bar allows the user to click on:

- Stanza number (e.g. “E1”, “E2”, “E3”): the Window keeps the information of the left and right, highlights the stanza at hand, and updates the information on the middle of the Window (see Figure 2.17;
- Stanza line. After each stanza number, there are numbers that correspond to the number of the line inside that stanza): if the user clicks on a Stanza number (e.g. “E1-1”), Window updates (see Window 2.18 –

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Inicio Buscas simples Cantigas Estrofas Versos Trobadores

Inicio > Cantiga > Visualiza cantiga

NAVCAN: [009014] • E1: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E2: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E3: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E4: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E1: 1 2 3 • E2: 1 2 3

Regresar

Texto Cantiga	Cantiga	Autoria																																								
<p>- Vaasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades e trabalhastes de trobar d' amor, do que agora, par Nostro Senhor, quero saber de vós que mi o digades; dizedemio, ca ben vos estara: pois vos esta por que talhastes ja morreo, por Deus, ¿por quen trobades?</p> <p>- Afonso Sanchez, vós me preguntades e querovos eu fazer sabedor: eu trobo e trobei pola melhor das que Deus fez, esto ben o creades; esta de curaçon non me salra e atenderei seu ben, se mi o fara, e vós al de min saber non queirades.</p> <p>- Vaasco Martiiz, vós non respondedes nen er entendo, asi veja prazer, por que trobades, que ouvi dizer que aquela por que trobad' avedes e que amastes vós máis doutra ren que vos morreo á gran temp', e por én vós pola morta trobar non deveades.</p> <p>- Afonso Sanchez, pois non entendedes en qual guisa vos eu fui responder, a min én culpa non deven poer, mais a vós, se o saber non podeades: eu trobo pola que m' en poder ten e vence todas de parecer ben pois viva é, ca non como dizedes.</p> <p>- Vaasco Martiiz, pois vos morreo por quen sempre trobastes, maravilhom' én, pois vos morreo, como non morredes.</p> <p>- Afonso Sanchez, vós sabede ben que viva é e comprida de sén a por que eu trob', e sabelo edes.</p>	<p>Número cantiga <input type="text" value="p09014"/></p> <p>Incipit <input type="text" value="Vasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades"/></p> <p>Número estrofas <input type="text" value="4+2F"/></p> <p>Outras linguas NON</p> <p>De seguir NON</p> <p>Tipo cantiga Mestria</p> <p>Categoría <input type="text" value="T EP"/></p>	<p>▶ Autor: (AfSchz) [Afonso Sanchez] 9 14</p> <p>▶ Tensó: (VAMrZRes) [Vasco Martiiz de Resende] 153 1</p> <p>Manuscritos</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Folio</th> <th>Num.</th> <th>Música</th> <th>Espazo</th> <th>Imaxe</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>B92r</td> <td>B416</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B92v</td> <td>B416</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>M25r</td> <td>M1</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P9</td> <td>P1</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P10</td> <td>P1</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P11</td> <td>P1</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>V-07v</td> <td>V27</td> <td>NON</td> <td>NON</td> <td>[imaxe]</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>▶ Nota colocciana</p> <p>▶ Rubrica explicativa</p> <p>▶ Rubrica explicativa</p> <p>Formas de relación interestrófica</p> <p>▶ Cobras dobias</p> <p>Temas</p> <p>▶ ben trobar</p> <p>Edicións</p> <p>Seguida:</p> <p>▶ Arbor 11</p> <p>Críticas:</p> <p>▶ CA 453</p> <p>▶ Longo 11</p> <p>▶ Lapa 66</p> <p>▶ Crestomatia, pp. 189-190</p> <p>▶ Machado 359</p> <p>▶ Vasconcelos, Tenção, pp. 145-147 (ed. sobre M)</p> <p>▶ Randgl. XV, pp. 700-701</p> <p>Paleográficas:</p> <p>▶ Lopes 409</p> <p>▶ Braga 27</p> <p>Divulgativas:</p> <p>▶ Gonçalves/Ramos, A lírica, 105</p>	Folio	Num.	Música	Espazo	Imaxe	B92r	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]	B92v	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]	M25r	M1	NON	NON	[imaxe]	P9	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]	P10	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]	P11	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]	V-07v	V27	NON	NON	[imaxe]
Folio	Num.	Música	Espazo	Imaxe																																						
B92r	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
B92v	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
M25r	M1	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
P9	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
P10	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
P11	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						
V-07v	V27	NON	NON	[imaxe]																																						

Figure 2.10: Window 2.10: result when clicking on the “VER” link of one entry of the Table of Window 2.9

Figure 2.18). The highlighted text on the left corresponds to the line selected in the navigation panel;

- Number of the *Cantiga* at hand on the database: it allows the user to return to the initial information about the *Cantiga* (see Figure 2.10).

Window 2.11 (Figure 2.11) presents:

- The information concerning the author of the *Cantiga* selected in the drop-down list. This information is the same as Window 2.7 (Figure 2.7), with an exception on field “Activity” (*Actividade*). This field is in fact a range of two years, Window 2.11 provides the range in the field activity as follows: “Actividade: (1260-1270)”. For its part, Window 2.7 (Figure 2.7) displays two different fields:
 - “activity from” (*actividade desde*): “1260”
 - “to” (*ata*): “1270”
- In the section concerning *Cantigas*, the window presents all the *Cantigas* composed by the author. Each row has the following information:
 - internal number of the *cantiga*. The internal number of the *Cantiga* has a link that opens a new window. This window is the same as Window 2.10 (Figure 2.10).
 - type of authorship
 - incipit

Window 2.12 (Figure 2.12) presents the information concerning the witness of the *cantiga*:

- the image of the witness (*Imaxe Manuscrito*)
- the siglum and folio of the manuscript (*Manuscrito*) where the *cantiga* is
- the size of the image file (*Tamaño*) in bytes
- the size of the image in pixels (*Lonxitude*), width and height in pixels

Trobador

IDT

Nome abreviado

Nome

Orixe Fiabilidade

Condición social

Actividade desde ata

Período 1300-1350

Cantigas

IDE	TIPO	INCIPIIT
[009001]	Autor	Afons' Afonses, batiçar queredes
[009002]	Autor	Conhocedes a donzela
[009003]	Autor	De vos servir, mia senhor, non me val
[009004]	Autor	Dizia la fremosinha
[009005]	Autor	Estes que m' ora tolhen mia senhor
[009006]	Autor	Mia senhor, quen me vos guarda
[009007]	Autor	Muitos me dizen que servi doado
[009008]	Autor	Pero eu dixei, mia senhor
[009009]	Autor	Pois vós per i máis de valer cuidades
[009010]	Autor	Quand', amiga, meu amigo veer
[009011]	Autor	Sempre vus eu doutra ren máis amei
[009012]	Autor	Tan grave dia que vos conhocei
[009013]	Autor	Ôu ric' ome a que ñu trobador
[009014]	Autor	Vaasco Martiñ, pois vós trabalhadés
[009015]	Autor	Vedes, amigos, que de perdas ei

1 - 15

Biografía

Fillo bastardo de Don Denis de Portugal e de Dona Aldonça Rodrigues de Telha, Afonso Sanchez debeu nacer pouco antes de 1289, momento en que aparece mencionado por primeira vez nunha doazón de seu pai. Lexitimado por carta do 8 de maio de 1304 e entregado ao coidado da raíña Dona Isabel, recibiu cuantiosos bens por parte de Don Denis, que foron administrados polo seu titor, o privado do monarca Pero Afonso Ribeiro. Vinculado á curia rexia desde 1303, detivo o cargo de mordomo-mor entre 1312 e posiblemente 1323. O importante patrimonio e o seu peso e influencia políticos na corte incrementáronse mediante o seu casamento (antes de 1306) con Dona Teresa Martins Telo, filla maior de Don Johan Afonso Telo II (ou de Albuquerque), primeiro Conde de Barcelos, e de Dona Teresa Sanchez, bastarda de Sancho IV de Castela. Por medio deste matrimonio, Don Afonso Sanchez entrou en posesión da metade do señorío de Albuquerque, de grande importancia estratéxica, e obtivo en 1308 a totalidade do señorío por medio dun cambio co infante Don Afonso de Molina. Obtivo tamén de seu sogro outros bens, feito que provocou un duro enfrontamento co seu cuñado, Don Martín Gil de Riba de Vizela, desposado con Dona Violante, irmá de Dona Teresa. O conflito, resolto mediante unha sentenza emitida por Don Denis en 1312, provocou o abandono da corte por parte do de Riba de Vizela e a súa partida para Castela. Na guerra civil de 1319-1324 culminaría a tensión acumulada ao longo de varios anos entre Don Denis e o príncipe herdeiro Don Afonso, pero tamén, e sobre todo, o descontento da nobreza ante a política de centralización exercida por Don Denis. O conflito pechouse en 1324 cun acordo de paz que, ademais de diversos beneficios para o infante Don Afonso, contemplaba o exilio de Don Afonso Sanchez, quen se retirou a Castela, á corte do seu sobriño Alfonso XI, cara a 1324. En 1325, xa como rei, Afonso IV confiscou todas as posesións que Don Afonso Sanchez tiña en Portugal. En resposta, este realizou varias incursións armadas en territorio portugués co apoio das tropas castelás. Tras as hostilidades, debeuse establecer un acordo entre as partes, posiblemente a partir de 1326, aínda que os bens do bastardo rexio só volverían a mans da súa dona despois do seu pasamento. O infante morreu no cerco de Escalona en 1328. O seu corpo, xunto co da súa esposa, repousa no mosteiro de Santa Clara de Vila do Conde, fundado polo matrimonio en 1317.

Figure 2.11: Window 2.11: result when clicking on the name of the author on Window 2.10

Window 2.13 (Figure 2.13) presents the information concerning a note by Angelo Colocci:

- the note itself
- an explanation with the exact location of the note in the witness

Window 2.14 (Figure 2.14) presents the information:

- the rubric itself
- an explanation with the exact location of the rubric

Window 2.15 (Figure 2.15) presents the type of interstrophic relation.

Window 2.17 (Figure 2.17) presents the information concerning the specific stanza selected. The additional information (comparing it to Window 2.10 – Figure 2.10) is:

- Type of stanza (*Tipo de Estrofa*)
- Number of stanza (*Número de estrofa*)
- Total number of lines (*Total de versos*)
- Reference to Tavani's repertoire (*Número esquema*)
- Rhyme scheme (*esquema rimático*)
- Metrical scheme (*esquema métrico*)

Window 2.18 (Figure 2.18) presents the information concerning the specific line selected. The extra information (in comparison to the Window 2.10 – Figure 2.10) is:

- Line content (*Verso*)
- Number of the line (*Número de verso*) of the stanza
- Number of syllables (*Número de sílabas*) of the line
- Boolean expressing whether the line is a refrain (*Refrán*)
- Rhyme ending (*Rima*)
- Rhyme word (*Palabra rimante*)

Propiedades

Centro Ramón Piñeiro para a Investigación en Humanidades
Cortesia da Biblioteca Nacional de Lisboa (Lisboa)

- ▶ Manuscrito: B92r
- ▶ Tamaño: 299318 bytes
- ▶ Lonxitude: 1156 x 1700 pixeles

Imaxe Manuscrito

Pechar

Figure 2.12: Window2.12: the image of the Witness of the *Cantiga* of Window 2.10

Nota

Nota colocciana

tenzon: per le rime supra 403

Nota colocciana á cantiga B 416. Está situada na marxe inferior dereita do fol. 92r.

Pechar

Figure 2.13: Window2.13: “nota colocciana” of the *Cantiga* of Window 2.10

Nota

Rúbrica explicativa

No mesmo libro estaban as trovas seguintes: Trovas de don Afonso Sanches filho del-Rei don Dinis a Vasco Martinz de Resende, e resposta do mesmo Vasco Martinz.

Rúbrica explicativa que precede a cantiga en M. Está situada na marxe superior da col. a do fol. 25r.

Pechar

Figure 2.14: Window2.14: *Rubrica explicativa* of Window 2.11

Figure 2.15: Window2.15: an example of a Window with notes on interstrophic relations

NAVCAN: [009014] • E1: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E2: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E3: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E4: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • F1: 1 2 3 • F2: 1 2 3

Figure 2.16: Window2.16: the navigation bar as a detail of Window10

The image shows a detailed web page for a stanza. At the top, there is a navigation bar with buttons for 'Inicio', 'Búsquas simples', 'Cantigas', 'Estrofas', 'Versos', and 'Trobadores'. Below the navigation bar, the page title is 'MARIANA.MALTA@LINHD.UNED.ES'. The main content area is divided into three columns: 'Texto Cantiga', 'Cantiga', and 'Autoria'. The 'Texto Cantiga' column contains the text of the stanza, with a blue highlight on the first line. The 'Cantiga' column contains the title '009014 Vaasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades' and a table of analysis tools for the stanza, including 'Número estrofa', 'Total versos', 'Número esquema', 'Esquema rímático', and 'Esquema métrico'. The 'Autoria' column contains the author's name 'Afonso Sanchez' and a list of manuscripts. The page also features sections for 'Manuscritos', 'Formas de relación interestrófica', 'Temas', and 'Edicións'.

Figure 2.17: Window 2.17: a stanza highlighted when the user clicks on the number of the stanza on the navigation bar of Window 2.16

NAVCAN: [009014] • E1: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E2: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E3: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • E4: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 • F1: 1 2 3 • F2: 1 2 3

Texto Cantiga

- Vaasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades e trabalhastes de trobar d' amor, do que agora, par Nostro Senhor, quero saber de vós que mi o digades; dizedemio, ca ben vos estara: pois vos esta por que talhastes ja morreo, por Deus, ¿por quen trobades?

- Afonso Sanchez, vós me preguntades e querovos eu fazer sabedor: eu trobo e trobei pola melhor das que Deus fez, esto ben o creades; esta de curaçon non me salra e atenderei seu ben, se mi o fara, e vós al de min saber non queirades.

- Vaasco Martiiz, vós non respondedes nen er entendo, asi veja prazer, por que trobades, que ouví dizer que aquela por que trobad' avedes e que amastes vós máis doutra ren que vos morreo á gran temp', e por én vós pola morta trobar non deveades.

- Afonso Sanchez, pois non entendedes en qual guisa vos eu fui responder, a min én culpa non deven poer, mais a vós, se o saber non podeades: eu trobo pola que m' en poder ten e vence todas de parecer ben pois viva é, ca non como dizedes.

- Vaasco Martiiz, pois vos morreo por quen sempre trobastes, maravilhom' én, pois vos morreo, como non morredes.

- Afonso Sanchez, vós sabede ben que viva é e comprida de sên a por que eu trob', e sabelo edes.

Cantiga

009014 Vaasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades
Número estrofas: 4+2F, Xénero: T EP, Tipo: Mestria

Estrofa

1, Autor: AfSchz, Tipo: ESTROFA, Número de versos: 7
161:122 abbacca 10' 10 10 10' 10 10 10'

Verso

Verso | Vaasco Martiiz, pois vós trabalhades

Número de verso

Número de sílabas

Refrán

Rima

Palabra rimante

Autoría

- ▶ Autor: (AfSchz) [Afonso Sanchez] **9 14**
- ▶ Tensó: (VaMrzRes) [Vasco Martiiz de Resende] **153 1**

Manuscritos

Folio	Num.	Música	Espazo	Imaxe
B92r	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]
B92v	B416	NON	NON	[imaxe]
M25r	M1	NON	NON	[imaxe]
P9	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]
P10	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]
P11	P1	NON	NON	[imaxe]
V-07v	V27	NON	NON	[imaxe]

- ▶ [Nota colocciana](#)
- ▶ [Rúbrica explicativa](#)
- ▶ [Rúbrica explicativa](#)

Formas de relación interestrófica

- ▶ Cobras doblas

Temas

- ▶ ben trobar

Edicións

Seguida:

- ▶ Arbor 11

Críticas:

- ▶ CA 453
- ▶ Longo 11
- ▶ Lapa 66
- ▶ [Crestomatia, pp. 189-190](#)

Figure 2.18: Window 2.18: a line highlighted when the user clicks on the number of the line on the navigation bar of Window 2.16

In Stanza

When the user selects the “Estrofa” button of Window 2.2.2 (Figure 2.2), Window 2.3 (Figure 2.3) opens and allows the user to conduct a specific search choosing criteria among a group of fields. Figure 2.19 presents Window 2.19 with the results of a search carried out with the input “abade de Valadolide Gomez Garcia” in the field author (*Trobador*) and the metrical scheme (*Esquema Métrico*) input of “8 8 8 8 8 8”. The query has as a result a table with the following columns:

- Number of the poem (*Cantiga#*)
- Number of the stanza (*Estrofa#*) in the poem
- Author (*Trobador*)
- First line of the stanza (*Primer Verso*)
- Type of stanza (*Tipo*)
- Total number of lines of the stanza (*Total Versos*)
- Reference to Tavani’s repertoire (*Número Esquema*)
- Rhyme scheme (*Esquema Rimático*)
- Syllabic metrical scheme (*Esquema Métrico*)

The result has three entries, in fact three stanzas of the same poem. Finally, for each row of the table there is a link (“VER”) that opens Window 2.17 (Figure 2.17).

MARIANA.MALTA@LINHD.UNED.ES ?

Inicio > Estrofa

Inicio Buscas simples Cantigas **Estrofas** Versos Trobadores

Buscas Reiniciar Buscar

Trobador igual Gomez Garcia, abade de Valadolide [059]

Nº Cantiga igual Calquera

Número esquema igual Calquera

Esquema rimático como

Esquema métrico como 8 8 8 8 8 8

Total versos igual Calquera

Categoría contén

Número estrofa igual

Cantiga no manuscrito como

Texto Estrofa contén

Conector Calquera condición Todas as condicións

Filtros

Mestria

Non aplicable

Refrán

Intercalar

Estrofa

Finda

Refrán inicial

Distico inicial

Tetrástico inicial

Hexástico inicial

Resultados

1 - 3 (3 estrofas [en 1 cantigas])

ID	Cantiga#	Estrofa#	Trobador	Primer verso	Tipo	Total versos	Esquema#	Esquema rimático	Esquema métrico
[VER]	059001	1	GmzGar	A vossa mesura, senhor,	Estrofa	7	161:243	abbacca	8 8 8 8 8 8 8
[VER]	059001	2	GmzGar	E, senhor, mal dia naçeo	Estrofa	7	161:243	abbacca	8 8 8 8 8 8 8
[VER]	059001	3	GmzGar	A vossa mesura gardei,	Estrofa	7	161:243	abbacca	8 8 8 8 8 8 8

1 - 3 (3 estrofas [en 1 cantigas])

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Figure 2.19: Window2.19: The results of a search in Window 2.3 (Figure 2.3)

In Line

When a user selects the “Versos” button in Window 2.2 (Figure 2.2), Window 2.4 (Figure 2.4) opens and allows the user to conduct a specific search choosing criteria among a group of fields. Window 2.20 (Figure 2.20) presents the results of a search carried out with the field Rhyme (*Rima*) as “aça”. The result is a table with the following columns:

- Number of the poem (*Cantiga#*)
- Number of the stanza (*Estrofa#*) in the poem
- Number of the line (*Verso#*) in the stanza in the poem
- The contents (*Verso*)
- Number of syllables (*Silabas*)
- Refrain (*Refrán*). Boolean (whether the line is part of a refrain)
- Rhyme (*Rima*)
- Rhyme word (*Palabra rimante*)

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Inicio Buscas simples Cantigas Estrofas **Versos** Trobadores

Inicio > Verso

Buscas

Reiniciar **Buscar**

Trobador igual

Nº cantiga igual Calquera

Nº silabas igual

Rima como aça

Palabra rimante como

Categoria contén

Cantiga no manuscrito como

Texto Verso contén

Conector Calquera condición Todas as condicións

Filtros

Tipo cantiga

Mestria

Non aplicable

Refrán

Intercalar

Tipo estrofa

Estrofa

Refrán inicial

Tetrástico inicial

Refrán

Non

Si

Finda

Distico inicial

Hexástico inicial

Resultados

1 - 19 (19 versos [en 8 estrofas en 5 cantigas])

id	Cantiga#	Estrofa#	Verso#	Verso	Silabas	Refran	Rima	Palabra rimante
[VER]	130002bis	1	2	ã, e de mais m' ameaza,	7	Non	aça	ameaza
[VER]	130002bis	1	4	seja, por feito que faça;	7	Non	aça	faça
[VER]	060011	1	5	que tanto dades que bon tempo faça.	10	Non	aça	faça
[VER]	066007	3	1	En meio da praça,	5	Non	aça	praça
[VER]	066007	3	2	en saia de baraça:	6	Non	aça	baraça
[VER]	070045	2	2	que ja esse preyto faça;	7	Non	aça	faça
[VER]	070045	2	3	mays dou-vos esta baraça,	7	Non	aça	baraça
[VER]	085013	1	3	non ajade-la mia graça	7	Si	aça	graça
[VER]	085013	1	5	filha que vos assi faça,	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	1	6	filha que vos assi faça.	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	2	3	non ajade-la mia graça	7	Si	aça	graça
[VER]	085013	2	5	filha que vos assi faça,	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	2	6	filha que vos assi faça.	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	3	3	non ajade-la mia graça	7	Si	aça	graça
[VER]	085013	3	5	filha que vos assi faça,	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	3	6	filha que vos assi faça.	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	4	3	non ajade-la mia graça	7	Si	aça	graça
[VER]	085013	4	5	filha que vos assi faça,	7	Si	aça	faça
[VER]	085013	4	6	filha que vos assi faça.	7	Si	aça	faça

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Figure 2.20: Window2.20: The results of a search in Window 2.4 (Figure 2.4)

The result has 19 entries (19 lines in 8 stanzas of 5 poems). Finally, for each row of the table there is a link (“VER”) that opens Window 2.18 (Figure 2.18).

In Author

When a user selects the “Trobador” button in Window 2.2 (Figure 2.2), Window 2.5 (Figure 2.5) opens and allows the user to conduct a specific search choosing criteria among a group of fields. Window 2.21 (Figure 21) presents the results of a search carried out with the field Nationality (*Orixe*) as “Portuguesa”. The result of the query is a table with the following columns:

- Short name of the author (*Abreviado*)
- Name of the author (*Nome*)
- Origin of the author (*Orixe*)
- Reliability of information provided about the origin of the author (*Fiabilidade da orixe*)
- Social status of the author (*Condición social*)
- Start of activity of the author (*Actividade desde*)
- End of activity of the author (*Actividade ata*)
- Period of time (*Período*). The period is defined by the project and they discriminate four periods of production

The screenshot shows the 'Trobadores' search interface. At the top, there are navigation buttons: 'Inicio', 'Buscas simples', 'Cantigas', 'Estrofas', 'Versos', and 'Trobadores'. Below these is a search form with the following fields:

- Nome:** igual, Calquera
- Número Trobador:** igual, Calquera
- Orixe:** igual, PORTUGUESA
- Condición social:** igual, nobre
- Período:** igual, Calquera

There are 'Reiniciar' and 'Buscar' buttons. Below the form, there are radio buttons for 'Conector': 'Calquera condición' (unselected) and 'Todas as condicións' (selected).

The results section is titled 'Resultados' and shows a table with 39 entries. The table has the following columns: ID, Abreviado, Nome, Orixe, Fiabilidade da orixe, Condición social, Actividade desde, Actividade ata, and Período. The results are sorted by ID, showing entries from [006] to [053].

ID	Abreviado	Nome	Orixe	Fiabilidade da orixe	Condición social	Actividade desde	Actividade ata	Período
[006]	AflpzBay	Afonso Lopez de Baian	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1246	1280	1240-1300
[009]	AfSchz	Afonso Sanchez	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1289	1328	1300-1350
[025]	Den	Don Denis	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1279	1325	1240-1300
[026]	DieGvz	Diogo Gonçalves de Montemor-o-Novo	PORTUGUESA	probable	nobre	1450	1480	1400-1480
[029]	EstCoe	Estevan Coelho	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1300	1325	1300-1350
[032]	EstFdzBarr	Estevan Fernandez Barreto (Barreiro)	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1290	1295	1240-1300
[034]	EstPrzFroy	Estevan Perez Froian	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1283	1305	1240-1300
[035]	EstReim	Estevan Reimondo	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1260	1285	1240-1300
[040]	FerFdzCog	Fernan Fernandez Cogominho	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1250	1275	1240-1300
[042]	FerFroy	Fernan Froiaz	PORTUGUESA	probable	nobre	1250	1275	1240-1300
[043]	FerGarEsg	Fernan Garcia Esgaravunha	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1220	1250	1220-1240
[044]	FerGvzSeav	Fernan Gonçalves de Seabra	PORTUGUESA	probable	nobre	1258	1275	1240-1300
[048]	FerRdzRed	Fernan Rodriguez Redondo	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1294	1320	1300-1350
[050]	FerVelho	Fernan Velho	PORTUGUESA	dubidosa	nobre	1280	1320	1240-1300
[053]	GarMdzEi	Garcia Mendiz d' Eixo	PORTUGUESA	coñecida	nobre	1190	1239	1170-1220

At the bottom of the page, there is a footer: 'Centro Ramón Piñeiro para a Investigación en Humanidades. Base de datos da Lírica Profana Galego-Portuguesa (MedDB). (ISSN 1989-4546)'.

Figure 2.21: Window2.21: The results of a search in Window 2.5 (Figure 2.5)

The system returns 39 entries (authors). For each line of the table there is a link (“VER”) that opens Window 2.11 (Figure 2.11).

2.2 Data needs analysis

2.2.1 Data elements of Window 2.1

Table 2.1 presents the data needs of Window 2.1. This Window is the default entry page of the Website, where the user can conduct a simple search by *Cantiga* (Poem) or *Trobador* (Author).

Table 2.1: Data elements of Window 2.1

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author (<i>Trobador</i>)	1			Opus-hasCreator-Person + name.Person
ID author	1			<i>URI instance of Person</i>
Incipit	1			Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction + incipit.Redaction

2.2.2 Data elements of Window 2.2

Table 2.2 presents the data needs of Window 2.2. This Window is the entry page of the Website for the advanced search options, where the user can conduct more complex searches by *Cantiga* (Poem), *Estrofa* (Stanza), *Verso* (Line) or *Trobador* (Author).

Table 2.2: Data elements of Window 2.2

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all available authors in the DB	Opus-hasCreator-Person + name.Person
Type of authorship	1			<i>autor</i> = Opus-hasCreator-Person <i>doble atribución</i> = Opus-hasDubiousCreator-Person <i>tenzón</i> = Stanza-hasCreator-Person
ID poem	1		No free search. Presents the list with all the ID of the cantigas	<i>URI instance Opus/Redaction</i>
Incipit	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all available incipits in the DB	incipit.Redaction
Siglum and number in manuscript	1		Search using as codes the siglum of the ms. followed by the number of the poem in it	Redaction-considers-Witness + siglum.Witness Redaction-considers-Witness + workNumber.Witness
Folio	1			Redaction-considers-Witness + location.Witness
Number of Stanzas	1		Free search. Presents a list with all possibilities available	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas. WorkPattern

Continued on next page

Table 2.2 – continued from previous page

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Interstrophic relations	1		No free search. Presents a list with the possibilities	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + interstrophicRelations. Workpattern
Theme	1		No free search. Presents a list with the possibilities	theme.Opus
Category	1		Free search	Opus.genre
String match	1			text.Redaction content.Line
Type of poem	1		Filter with 3 options	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + metricalType. WorkPattern
<i>De seguir</i>	1		Boolean	Opus-isDerivedFrom-Intertextuality + typeOfIntertextuality .Intertextuality
Other languages	1		Boolean, whether is written in other languages than Galician-Portuguese	language.Opus
Music	1		Boolean, whether the music notation for this poem is preserved	Redaction-considers-Witness + hasMusicalNotation. Witness
Space for music	1		Boolean, whether there is space for music in one of its witnesses	Redaction-considers-Witness + hasMusicSpace. Witness

2.2.3 Data elements of Window 2.3

Table 2.3 presents the data needs of Window 2.3. This Window allows the user to search for Stanzas.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.3 is related to the entities “Stanza” and “StanzaPattern” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive” to these entities is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza-(isAnalysedThrough-StanzaPattern)-nextStanza-Stanza-isAnalysedThrough-StanzaPattern

In the table, some of the “higher” entities such as “Redaction” or “Opus” might be referenced.

2.2.4 Data elements of Window 2.4

Table 2.4 presents the data needs of Window 2.4. This Window allows the user to search for Lines.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.4 is related to the entities “Line” and “LinePattern” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive” to these entities is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza-(nextStanza-Stanza) - hasFirstLine-Line (-nextLine-Line) (isAnalysedThrough-LinePattern)

2.2.5 Data elements of Window 2.5

Table 2.5 presents the data needs of Window 2.5. This Window allows the user to search for Authors.

⁸Our model retrieves the stanza content from the “Line” or the “Word” not directly from the “Stanza”

Table 2.3: Data elements of Window 2.3

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all available authors in the DB	Stanza-hasCreator-Person + name.Person
ID poem	1		No free search. Presents a list with the ID of all poems in the DB	<i>URI instance Opus/Redaction</i>
Reference to Tavani's repertoire	1		No free search. Presents a list with all possible references in the DB	StanzaPattern-isReferencedIn-Location identifier.Location
Rhyme scheme	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all possible schemes in the DB	rhymeScheme. StanzaPattern
Syllabic Metrical Scheme	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all possible schemes in the DB	syllabicMetricalScheme. StanzaPattern
Number of lines of the stanza	1		Presents a list with all possibilities available	numberOfLines. StanzaPattern
Category	1			Opus.genre
Number of Stanza	1			stanzaNumber. .Stanza
Poem in a manuscript	1		Number of the poem in one of its primary sources	Redaction-considers-Witness siglum.Witness Redaction-considers-Witness + workNumber.Witness
String match	1			content.Line ⁸ content.Word
Type of poem	1		Filter with 3 options	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough- WorkPattern + metricalType. WorkPattern
Type of stanza	1		Filter with 6 options	metricalType. StanzaPattern

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.5 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

2.2.6 Data elements of Window 2.6

Table 2.6 presents the data needs of Window 2.6. This Window returns the result after selecting a poem from the drop-down list of Window 2.1.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.6 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 2.4: Data elements of Window 2.4

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author	1		Free search. Also presents a list with all available authors	Stanza-hasCreator-Person + name.Person
ID poem	1		No free search. Presents a list with the ID of all available poems	<i>URI instance Opus/Redaction</i>
Number of syllables	1			numberOfSyllables. LinePattern
				syllabicMetricalScheme. LinePattern
Rhyme	1		Free search. Presents every possibility available	Line-presents-Rhyme + ending.Rhyme
Rhyme word	1		Free search. Presents every possibility available	Line-presents-Rhyme + rhymeWord.Rhyme
Category	1			Opus.genre
Poem in a manuscript	1		Number of the poem in one of its primary sources	Redaction-considers-Witness + siglum.Witness
				Redaction-considers-Witness + workNumber.Witness
String match	1			content.Line
				content.Word
Type of poem	1		Filter with 3 options	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + metrical-Type.WorkPattern
Type of stanza	1		Filter with 6 options	Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-StanzaPattern + metricalType.StanzaPattern
Refrain	1		Boolean, whether the line is part of a refrain	isRefrain.Line

Table 2.5: Data elements of Window 2.5

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of Author	1		Presents a list with all available authors	name.Person
ID Author	1		Presents a list with the ID of all authors	<i>URI instance Person</i>
Origin	1		Presents a list with all the available nationalities	nationality.Person
Social Status	1		Presents a list with six possible values	socialStatus.Person
Period	1		Presents a list with five possible ranges	literaryPeriod.Person

2.2.7 Data elements of Window 2.7

Table 2.7 presents the data needs of Window 2.7. This Window returns the result after selecting an author from the drop-down list of Window 2.1.

Table 2.6: Data elements of Window 2.6

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
AUTHOR	M			Opus-hasCreator-Person
Type	1			<i>autor</i> = Opus-hasCreator-Person
				<i>doble atribución</i> = Opus-hasDubiousCreator-Person
				<i>tenzón</i> = Stanza-hasCreator-Person
Name	1			name.Person
Nickname	1			altName.Person
ID	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Origin	1			nationality.Person
Social status	1			socialStatus.Person
Activity	1			floruit.Person
Period	1			literaryPeriod.Person
Biography	1			biography.Person

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.7 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 2.7: Data elements of Window 2.7

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Name of Author	1			name.Person
ID Author	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Origin	1			nationality.Person
Social Status	1			socialStatus.Person
Activity	1			florui.Person
Period	1			literaryPeriod.Person
Biography	1			biography.Person

2.2.8 Data elements of Window 2.8

Table 2.8 presents the data needs of Window 2.8. This Window returns the result after selecting an Incipit from Window 2.1 previously filtered by author.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.8 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 2.8: Data elements of Window 2.8

Label	Cardinality	Link	Comments	DM
Name of Author	1			name.Person
ID Author	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Incipit				incipit.Redaction
Origin	1			nationality.Person
Social Status	1			socialStatus.Person
Activity	1			floruit.Person
Period	1			literaryPeriod.Person
Biography	1			biography.Person

2.2.9 Data elements of Window 2.9

Table 2.9 presents the data needs of Window 2.9. This Window returns the result after search using Window 2.2.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.9 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. Since the core entity of the model is “Opus”, the process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus–hasCreator–Person

Table 2.9: Data elements of Window 2.9

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author	1			name.Person
ID author	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
POEM	M			Person–creates–Opus
“VER”	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	Conection with the URI of the Opus instance of the poem
ID Poem	1			<i>URI instance Opus</i>
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
Author nickname	1			altName.Person
Number of stanzas	1			Redaction – isAnalysedThrough – WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern
Type of poem	1			Redaction – isAnalysedThrough – WorkPattern + metricalType.WorkPattern
Category	1			genre.Opus

2.2.10 Data elements of Window 2.10

Table 2.10 presents the data needs of Window 2.10. This Window returns the result after clicking on the link “VER” of one poem of Window 2.9.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.10 is related to the entities “Line” and “LinePattern” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to these entities is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza–(–nextStanza–Stanza)–hasFirstLine–Line (–nextLine–Line) (–isAnalysedThrough–LinePattern)

Table 2.10: Data elements of Window 2.10

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID <i>cantiga</i>	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	<i>URI instance Opus</i>
ID stanza	1	1	Opens Window 2.17	<i>URI instance Stanza</i>
ID line in stanza	1	1	Opens Window 18	<i>URI instance Line</i>
Content	1		shows the complete text of the poem	text.Redaction
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
Number of stanzas	1			Redaction – isAnalysedThrough – WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern
Other languages	1		Boolean	language.Opus
<i>De seguir</i>	1		Boolean	Redaction– isDerivedFrom – Intertextuality typeOfIntertextuality.Intertextuality

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Table 2.10 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Type of poem	1			Redaction – isAnalysedThrough – WorkPattern+metricalType.WorkPattern
Category	1			genre.Opus
AUTHOR	M			Opus –hasCreator –Person
Nickname	1			altName.Person
Name	1	1	Opens Window 2.11	name.Person
ID	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Number of poem	1		Order of poem in the set of poems the author wrote (ordering defined by MeDB)	<i>Not relevant</i>
MANUSCRIPT	M			Redaction–considers–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Folio	1			location.Witness
Number of Poem	1		Number of the poem in the manuscript (different from number of poem of MeDB)	workNumber.Witness
Music	1		Boolean	hasMusicalNotation.Witness
Space of music	1			hasMusicSpace.Witness
Image (<i>imaxe</i>)	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.12	Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile
NOTE BY COLOCCI	M			
<i>Nota colocciana</i>	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.13	
NOTES	M			
<i>Rúbrica explicativa</i>	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.14	
INTERSTROPHIC RELATION	M			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern
Content	1	1	Opens Window 2.15	
THEME	M			Opus
Content	1			theme.Opus
EDITION	M			Redaction–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource Redaction–retrievesText–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource ⁹
Type of edition	1		Controlled list of terms (<i>paleográfica, divulgativa, crítica...</i>)	typeOfEdition.BibliographicSource

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Table 2.10 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Content	1		The content consists of a reference to a bibliographic item using a codification (short name) given by MedDB. This identifier is followed by the pages that locate the reference and other notes if required.	BibliographicSource-refersThrough-Location+identifier.Location

2.2.11 Data elements of Window 2.11

Table 2.11 presents the data needs of Window 2.11. This Window returns the result after a search on Window 2.5.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.11 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Person” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 2.11: Data elements of Window 2.11

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID Author	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Nickname author	1			altName.Person
Name author	1			name.Person
Origin	1			nationality.Person
Origin reliability	1			birthPlaceCertainty.Person
Social status	1			socialStatus.Person
Activity from	1			floruitFrom.Person
Activity to	1			floruitTo.Person
Period	1			literaryPeriod.Person
Biography	1			biography.Person
CANTIGA	M			Person-creates-Opus
ID	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	<i>URI instance Opus</i>
Type	1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + metricalType.WorkPattern
Incipit	1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + incipit.Redaction

2.2.12 Data elements of Window 2.12

Table 2.12 presents the data needs of Window 2.12. This Window returns the result after clicking on the link “IMAXE” of Window 2.10.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.12 is related to the entity “Witness” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Witness” is: Redaction-considers-Witness

⁹This second alternative is the connection required to define the edition followed in the database (the one detailed as *Seguida*)

Table 2.12: Data elements of Window 2.12

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum of Manuscript	1			siglum.Witness
Folio of Witness	1			location.Witness
Size of file			file of image (in bytes)	<i>not relevant</i>
Height of image	1		in pixels	<i>not relevant</i>
Width of image	1		in pixels	<i>not relevant</i>
Image of Witness	1	1	Link to the image file on server	Witness-isReproducedIn-Facsimile

2.2.13 Data elements of Window 2.13

Table 2.13 presents the data needs of Window 2.13. This Window returns the result after clicking on the link “Nota colocciana” of Window 2.10.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.13 is related to the entity “Paratext” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Paratext” is: Redaction-hasItem-Paratext or Redaction-considers-Witness-hasItem-Paratext (whenever this paratextual information is only present in one of the witnesses).

Table 2.13: Data elements of Window 2.13

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Content of the note	1			content.Paratext
Commentary	1		Commentary with the location of the note by Colocci	notes.Paratext + location.Paratext Paratext-hasCreator-Person (=Colocci)

2.2.14 Data elements of Window 2.14

Table 2.14 presents the data needs of Window 2.14. This Window returns the result after clicking on the link “Rubrica explicativa” of Window 2.10.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.14 is related to the entity “Paratext” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Paratext” is: Redaction-hasItem-Paratext or Redaction-considers-Witness-hasItem-Paratext (whenever this paratextual information is only present in one of the witnesses).

Table 2.14: Data elements of Window 2.14

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Content of the note	1			content.Paratext
Commentary	1		Commentary with the location of the note	notes.Paratext + location.Paratext typeOfParatext.Paratext (=rubric)

2.2.15 Data elements of Window 2.15

Table 2.15 presents the data needs of Window 2.15. This Window returns the result after clicking on the link related to the interstrophic relation” of Window 2.10.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.15 is related to the entity “WorkPattern” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “WorkPattern” is: Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern

Table 2.15: Data elements of Window 2.15

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Content	1			interstrophicRelations.WorkPattern

2.2.16 Data elements of Window 2.17

Table 2.16 presents the data needs of Window 2.17. This Window returns the result after clicking on a stanza number on the navigation panel (see detail of navigation panel on Figure 2.16) of Window 2.10 (Figure 2.10).

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.16 is related to the entity “Stanza” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Stanza” is: Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza (–nextStanza–Stanza)

Table 2.16: Data elements of Window 2.17

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID cantiga	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	<i>URI instance Redaction</i>
ID stanza	1	1	Opens Window 2.17	<i>URI instance Stanza</i>
ID line in stanza	1	1	Opens Window 2.18	Stanza–hasFirstLine–Line (–nextLine–Line) <i>URI instance Line</i>
Content	1		shows the complete text of the poem. The stanza selected is highlighted.	text.Redaction
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
Number of stanzas	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern
Type of poem	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + metricalType.WorkPattern
Category	1			genre.Opus
Nickname of the author of the stanza	1			Stanza–hasCreator–Person + altName.Person
Type of stanza	1			typeOfStanza.Stanza
Number of stanza	1		in the poem	stanzaNumber.Stanza
Total number of lines	1		of the stanza	Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + numberOfLines.StanzaPattern
Reference to Tavani’s repertoire	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern–isReferencedIn–Location + identifier.Location
Rhyme scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Metrical scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + syllabicMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern

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Table 2.16 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
AUTHOR	M			See “TYPE”
Type	1			<i>autor</i> = Opus–hasCreator–Person <i>doble atribución</i> = Opus–hasDubiousCreator–Person <i>tenzón</i> = Stanza–hasCreator–Person
Nickname	1			altName.Person
Name	1	1	Opens Window 2.11	name.Person
ID	1			URI instance Person
Number of poem	1		Order of poem in the set of poems the author wrote (order defined by MeDB)	Not relevant
MANUSCRIPT	M			Redaction–considers–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Folio	1			location.Witness
Number of Poem	1		Number of the poem in the manuscript, different from number of poem of MeDB, naturally	workNumber.Witness
Music	1		Boolean	hasMusicalNotation.Witness
Space of music	1			hasMusicSpace.Witness
Image	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.12	Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile
NOTE BY COLOCCI	M			
<i>Nota colocciana</i>	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.13	
NOTES	M			
<i>Rubrica explicativa</i>	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.14	
INTERSTROPHIC RELATION	M			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern
Content	1	1	Link to Window 2.15	
THEME	M			Opus
Content	1			theme.Opus
EDITION	M			Redaction–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource Redaction–retrievesText–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource ¹⁰
Type of edition	1		Controlled list of terms (<i>paleográfica, divulgativa, crítica...</i>)	typeOfEdition.BibliographicSource
Content	1		The content has references to books with a codification given by MedDB to identify the book, than number of pages and other notes.	BibliographicSource–refersThrough–Location+ identifier.Location

2.2.17 Data elements of Window 2.18

Table 2.17 presents the data needs of Window 2.18. This Window returns the result after clicking on a line number on the navigation panel (see detail of navigation panel on Figure 2.16) of Window 2.10 (Figure 2.10).

¹⁰This second alternative is the connection required to define the edition followed in the database (the one detailed as *Seguida*)

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.17 is related to the entity “Stanza” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Stanza” is: Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza (–nextStanza–Stanza)

Table 2.17: Data elements of Window 2.18

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID cantiga	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	<i>URI instance Redaction</i>
ID stanza	1	1	Opens Window 2.17	<i>URI instance Stanza</i>
ID line in stanza	1	1	Opens Window 2.18	Stanza–hasFirstLine–Line (–nextLine–Line) <i>URI instance Line</i>
Content	1		shows the complete text of the poem. The stanza selected is highlighted.	text.Redaction
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
Number of stanzas	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern
Type of poem	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + metricalType.WorkPattern
Category	1			genre.Opus
Nickname of the author of the stanza	1			Stanza–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Type of stanza	1			typeOfStanza.Stanza
Number of stanza	1		in the poem	stanzaNumber.Stanza
Total number of lines	1		of the stanza	Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + numberOfLines.StanzaPattern
Reference to Tavani’s repertoire	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern–isReferencedIn–Location + identifier.Location
Rhyme scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Metrical scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + syllabicMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern
AUTHOR	M			Opus –hasCreator –Person
Type	1			<i>autor</i> = Opus–hasCreator–Person <i>doble atribución</i> = Opus–hasDubiousCreator–Person <i>tenzón</i> = Stanza–hasCreator–Person
Nickname	1			altName.Person
Name	1	1	Opens Window 2.11	name.Person
ID	1			<i>URI instance Person</i>
Number of poem	1		Order of poem in the set of poems the author wrote (order defined by MeDB)	<i>Not relevant</i>
MANUSCRIPT	M			Redaction–considers–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Folio	1			location.Witness
Number of Poem	1		Number of the poem in the manuscript, different from number of poem of MeDB, naturally	workNumber.Witness
Music	1		Boolean	hasMusicalNotation.Witness
Space of music	1			hasMusicSpace.Witness

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Table 2.17 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Image	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.12	Witness-isReproducedIn-Facsimile
NOTE BY COLOCCI	M			Witness-hasItem-Paratext
<i>Nota colocciana</i>	1	1	Opens Window 2.13	content.Paratext + Paratext-hasCreator-Person + name.Person(=Colocci)
NOTES	M			Witness-hasItem-Paratext
<i>Rúbrica explicativa</i>	1	1	Opens Window 2.14	content.Paratext + typeOfParatext.Paratext(=rubrica)
INTERSTROPHIC RELATION	M			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern
Content	1	1	Link to Window 2.15	
THEME	M			Opus
Content	1			theme.Opus
EDITION	M			Redaction-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource Redaction-retrievesText-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource ¹¹
Type of edition	1		Controlled list of terms (<i>paleográfica, divulgativa, crítica...</i>)	typeOfEdition.BibliographicSource
Content	1		The content has references to books with a codification given by MedDB to identify the book, than number of pages and other notes.	BibliographicSource-refersThrough-Location+ indentifier.Location

2.2.18 Data elements of Window 2.19

Table 2.18 presents the data needs of Window 2.19. This Window returns the result after a search on Window 2.3.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.18 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Redaction” is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

2.2.19 Data elements of Window 2.20

Table 2.19 presents the data needs of Window 2.20. This Window returns the result after a search on Window 2.3.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.19 is related to the entity “Redaction”, “Stanza” and “Line” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to these entities is:

- Redaction: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction
- Stanza: Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza (-nextStanza-Stanza)
- Line: Stanza-hasFirstLine-Line (nextLine-Line)

2.2.20 Data elements of Window 2.21

Table 2.20 presents the data needs of Window 2.21. This Window returns the result after a search on Window 2.5.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 2.20 is related to the entity “Author” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive”to “Author” is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

¹¹This second alternative is the connection required to define the edition followed in the database (the one detailed as *Seguida*)

Table 2.18: Data elements of Window 2.19

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
“VER”	1	1	No data, only link. Opens Window 2.10	<i>Conection with the URI of the Opus instance of the poem</i>
ID poem	1			<i>URI instance Opus</i>
Number of Stanza	1			Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza (–nextStanza–Stanza) + stanzaNumber.Stanza
Nickname of author	1			Opus–hasCreator–Person + altName.Person
Incipit	1		of the poem to whom the stanza belongs	incipit.Redaction
Type of stanza	1			Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza) + typeOfStanza.Stanza
Total number of lines	1		of the stanza	Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + numberOfLines.StanzaPattern
Reference to Tavani’s repertoire	1			Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern–isReferencedIn–Location + identifier.Location
Rhyme scheme	1			Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Metrical scheme	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + syllabicMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern

Table 2.19: Data elements of Window 2.20

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
“VER”	1	1	Opens Window 2.10	<i>Conection with the URI of the Opus instance of the poem</i>
ID poem	1			<i>URI instance Opus</i>
Number of Stanza	1			stanzaNumber.Stanza
Line number	1			lineNumber.Line
Content	1		of the line	content.Line
Number of Syllables	1			Line–isAnalysedThrough–LinePattern + numberOfSyllables.LinePattern
Refrain	1		boolean	isRefrain.Line
Rhyme	1			Line–presents–Rhyme + ending.Rhyme

Table 2.20: Data elements of Window 2.21

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID	1	1	Opens Window 2.11	<i>URI instance Person</i>
Nickname	1			altName.Person
Name	1			name.Person
Origin	1			nationality.Person
Reliability of origin	1			birthPlaceCertainty.Person
Social Status	1			socialStatus.Person
Activity from	1			floruitFrom.Person
Activity until	1			floruitTo.Person
Period	1			literaryPeriod.Person

Chapter 3

Eighteen Century Poetry Archive

URL: <http://www.eighteenthcenturypoetry.org>

3.1 Informational Needs

The entry page of the Eighteen Century Poetry Archive (ECPA) provides two types of searches: by author and by work.

3.1.1 By Author

The window of Figure 3.1 presents the entry page for **Author**. This page lists all authors of the ECPA Database (DB) by alphabetic order, grouped by letter. Each author is presented through their full name (family name, given name, role names and other honorific titles) followed by their birth and death dates. This page also presents the possibility to go directly to a letter, and to list authors by “birth date” (Figure 3.2) and by “gender” (Figure 3.3). When clicking in the name of an author the system opens the window of Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.2 presents the window that results from selecting the link “Birth date” on the window of Figure 3.1. This page groups the authors of the ECPA Database (DB) ordered by dates of birth. Each author is introduced with their full name and birth and death dates. This page also presents the possibility to go directly to a decade, and to list authors by “name” (see Figure 3.1) or by “gender” (see Figure 3.3). When clicking in the name of an author the system opens the window of Figure 3.4.

The window of Figure 3.3 presents the page to which the user is directed after selecting the link “Gender” on the window of Figure 3.1. This page lists the authors of the DB ordered by gender. Each author is presented by their full name followed by their dates of birth and death. This page also presents the possibility to go directly to a specific gender, and to list authors by “name” (Figure 3.1) or by “birth date” (Figure 3.2). When clicking in the name of an author the system opens the window of Figure 3.4.

The window of Figure 3.4 presents information concerning an **Author**:

- Works in the ECPA: a list of the works authored by the current person available in the ECPA. Every work is listed using its title, and a link to the TOC of the source edition used
- Source editions for that author used in the ECPA
- Bibliographical note
- Bibliography
 - References with information on the person (some with URL to other Websites)
 - Manuscripts
 - Bibliography
 - Editions
 - Reference
 - Criticism
 - Studies of individual works

Figure 3.1: Window 3.1: ECPA Front page for “Author” search

Finally, there is a picture of the author with a caption.

3.1.2 By Work

The window of Figure 3.5 presents the entry page for **Works**. This page lists all works of the DB by title in alphabetic order. The titles are grouped by their initial and each work is presented under the format “Title / Author”. This page also presents the possibility to go directly to a letter in order to see all works with a title that starts by the chosen letter, and to go to works with titles in a “Non-Roman” alphabet. When clicking in one of the titles, the system opens the Window of Figure 3.6.

The window of Figure 3.6 presents the default view of an entry page of a specific **Work**. On the left side it shows the whole text of the work. If a user clicks in a word, the window of Figure 3.8 opens. On the right side of window of Figure 3.6, the user sees the default view (“reading” tab on). This page presents “a set of contextual sections in support of a first reading of a text. These include bibliographical information about the text (title, author,” translator (if they exist), “themes, genres, headnote, references) and a choice between a text view that excludes most paratexts and a document view that represents all of the text in the source edition. Depending on the form, structure, and content of the text, other available contextual sections include a table of contents, a summative view of the poetic form (metre, stanza form, syllabic pattern, rhyme type and scheme), bibliographic information about the source of the text, a statement of editorial principles applied, any text-specific secondary literature, an introductory essay, other versions of the text in ECPA, related works, and a list of “Other Works” by the same author.”¹

The right page has several links:

- name of the author: opens the window of Figure 3.4;
- document view: switch to the window of Figure 3.7, which displays the text with different edition criteria from the default view (“Text view”);
- on the “Bibliography” section there are several links to catalogues with information about the references provided;

¹Text from ECPA help page.

The screenshot shows the 'Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive' website. The navigation bar includes 'Home', 'About', 'Authors', 'Works', 'Resources', and 'Help'. The 'Authors' section is active, displaying a filter for 'Birth dates'. A dropdown menu is open, showing options for 'All', '1660s', '1670s', '1680s', '1690s', '1700s', '1710s', '1720s', '1730s', '1740s', '1750s', and 'unknown'. The '1660s' filter is selected, showing 7 authors: Arbuthnot, John (1667-1735); Bentley, Richard (1662-1742); Finch, Anne, countess of Winchilsea (1661-1720); Lansdowne, Baron, George Granville (1667-1735); Pomfret, John (1667-1702); Stennett, Joseph (1663-1713); and Swift, Jonathan (1667-1745). The '1670s' filter shows 13 authors, including Addison, Joseph (1672-1719); Alsop, Anthony (1670-1726); Bolingbroke, 1st Viscount, Henry St. John (1678-1751); Clay, Stephen (1672- ?); Cobb, Samuel (1675-1713); Earle, Jabez (1673-1768); Evans, Abel (1679-1737); Monck, Mary (1677?-1715); Phillips, John (1676-1709); Rowe, Elizabeth (1674-1737); Somerville, William (1675-1742); Taylor, William (1673-1750); and Winstanley, John (1677-1750). The '1680s' filter shows 16 authors, including Barber, Mary (1685?-1755); Berkeley, George (1685-1753); Delany, Patrick (1685-1768); and Diaper, William (1685-1717).

Figure 3.2: Window 3.2: Authors listed by birth date

- on the “Source Edition” section, the page number is a link, but it is not open access (so this link will not be referred in Section 3.2);
- on the “Other Works” section there is a link to the table of contents of the Source Edition of the work at hand (see Figure 3.9).

The window of Figure 3.7 presents the view of the text in the source edition:

- text;
- type of document (e.g. semi-diplomatic, semi-normalised);
- author name: link that opens the window of Figure 3.4;
- line numbers;
- number of page in the source edition;
- link to the facsimile of the witness.

The window of Figure 3.8 presents the description of a Word, that is, the word selected by the user in the window of Figure 3.6. This window presents:

- location of the word (line and number in the line)
- standard form
- lemma
- part of speech
- word class
- pronunciation
- language dictionaries:
 - name
 - URL with a link to the word in the dictionary
- encyclopedias:
 - name
 - URL with a link to word in the encyclopedia

The window of Figure 3.9 presents the table of contents of a source edition. This window opens when the user

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Authors

Names	Birth dates	Gender
All	female	male
		unknown

female

30 authors

- Anonymous
- Anonymous
- Barbauld, Anna Laetitia (1743–1825)
- Barber, Mary (1685?–1755)
- Bennet, Mrs (1719–1792)
- Bindon, Mrs (? – ?)
- Brooke, Frances (1724–1789)
- Carter, Elizabeth (1717–1806)
- Chapone, Hester Mulso (1727–1801)
- Craven, Elizabeth (1750–1828)
- Darwall, Mary (1738–1825)
- Ferrar, Martha (1729–1805)
- Finch, Anne, countess of Winchilsea (1661–1720)
- Greville, Frances (1727?–1789)
- Grierson, Constantia (1704?–1732)
- Hertford, Countess of, Duchess of Somerset, Seymour, Frances Thynne (1699–1754)
- Leapor, Mary (1722–1746)
- Luxborough, Lady, Knight, Henrietta St. John (1699–1756)
- Madan, Judith Cowper (1702–1781)
- Monck, Mary (1677?–1715)
- Montagu, Lady Mary Wortley (1689–1762)
- Pennington, Elizabeth (1732–1759)
- Pilkington, Laetitia (1709?–1750)
- Piozzi, Hester Lynch (1741–1821)
- Pye, Jael Henrietta (1737?–1782)
- Robinson, Mary (1757?–1800)
- Rowe, Elizabeth (1674–1737)
- Soper, Miss (? – ?)
- Thomas, Elizabeth (1714–1779)
- Yearsley, Ann (1753–1806)

male

201 authors

Figure 3.3: Window 3.3: Authors listed by gender

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Oliver Goldsmith
(10 November 1728? - 4 April 1774)

Works in ECPA

- [THE DESERTED VILLAGE](#) (📖)
- [THE DOUBLE TRANSFORMATION: A TALE](#) (📖)
- [EDWIN AND ANGELINA, A BALLAD](#) (📖); [EDWIN AND ANGELINA, A BALLAD](#) (📖)
- [THE GIFT: TO IRIS](#) (📖)
- [THE HERMIT](#) (📖)
- [A NEW SIMILE, IN THE MANNER OF SWIFT](#) (📖)
- [RETALIATION](#) (📖)
- [THE TRAVELLER: OR, A PROSPECT OF SOCIETY](#) (📖)

Source editions

- 📖 *A collection of the most esteemed pieces of poetry: that have appeared for several years. With variety of originals, by the late Moses Mendez, Esq; and other contributors to Dodsley's collection. To which this is intended as a supplement.* London: printed for Richardson and Urquhart, 1767. [8]320p.; 8". (ESTC T124631; DMI 1073; OTA K099398.000;📖)
- 📖 *A collection of poems in four volumes. By several hands. Vol. IV. [The second edition].* London: printed for G. Pearch, 1770. 4v.; 8". (ESTC T116245; DMI 1137; OTA K093079.004;📖)
- 📖 *The Miscellaneous Works of Oliver Goldsmith, M.B. Containing all his Essays and Poems.* London: printed for W. Griffin, Catherine-street, in the Strand, 1775. [8]v.[1],10-200p.; 8". (ESTC T146118; OTA K113624.000;📖)

Biographical note

Oliver Goldsmith was born at Pallas, near Ballymahon, County Longford, Ireland, the fifth child of Charles Goldsmith (c. 1690–1747), curate and later rector at Kilkenny West, and his wife, Ann (d. 1770), the daughter of a clergyman. Goldsmith grew up near the village of Lissoy, where the family moved in 1730. Goldsmith was disfigured by smallpox as a child. He was educated by the village schoolmaster, Thomas Byrne, and then at schools at Elphin, Athlone, and Edgeworthstown. Goldsmith showed early promise as a poet. He entered Trinity College, Dublin, in 1745, but only just graduated BA in 1750. While at university, he supported himself and his gambling habit by selling ballads. He studied medicine at Edinburgh University for two years, and in 1754 went to Leiden for further training. He abandoned the plan, however, and instead travelled on foot through France, Switzerland, Germany, and Italy. On his return to England in 1756, he worked as assistant to an apothecary, doctor (apparently without a medical degree), school-teacher, and writer. Goldsmith became a staff writer first on the *The Monthly Review*, and later on the rival *Critical Review*. He also contributed pieces to other periodicals, wrote biographies, and became a novelist. By 1760, he was established as a professional writer and made new friends, including Smollet, Thomas Percy, Samuel Johnson, Sir Joshua Reynolds, and the bookseller John Newbery. In 1764, he was a founder member of the Club, the literary association formed by Johnson, Burke, Sir Joshua Reynolds, Sir John Hawkins and others. Also in 1764, he completed and published his first major poem, *The Traveller; or, A Prospect of Society*. After his success as a poet, Newbery also published Goldsmith's collected *Essays* in 1765 and his novel, *The Vicar of Wakefield*, in 1766. Goldsmith edited two poetry anthologies in 1766 and 1767 and wrote a play, which was performed at Covent Garden in 1768. In 1769, Goldsmith was appointed Professor of Ancient History at the Royal Academy at the suggestion of Reynolds. In 1770, he published *The Deserted Village*, his most famous poem, contrasting the innocent state of rural life with the evils of commercialism and enclosure. Goldsmith produced several historical and biographical works as well as continuing to write for the stage. Despite his many successes and his fame as a writer, Goldsmith was plagued by his prodigal habits throughout his life. In 1773, he had his greatest success as a playwright with *The Stoops to Conquer*. In 1774, Goldsmith increasingly suffered from bad health and had to seek treatment. His last poem, *Retaliation*, a series of mock epitaphs for his friends, remained unfinished. Goldsmith died on 4 April 1774. The memorial to Goldsmith in Westminster Abbey, erected by Reynolds, carries a Latin epitaph by Johnson.

Oliver Goldsmith (1728?-1774)
© National Portrait Gallery, London

Bibliography

ODNB 10924;📖; DMI 1629;📖; NCBEL 1191-1210

Figure 3.4: Window 3.4: Author view

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Works

Titles First/Last lines Themes Genres Source editions

All A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z non-Roman

A

73 works

ABELARD TO ELOISA / James Cawthorn
 ABSENCE / Philip Parsons
 ABSENT LOVER, The / Stephen Duck
 ABSOLUTION / William Taylor
 ACADEMIC, THE / Sir James Marriott
 ACTOR, THE / Robert Lloyd
 AD D. D. HANNES, INSIGNISSIMUM MEDICUM & POETAM / Joseph Addison; Thomas Newcomb
 Ad Insignissimum Virum D. THO. BURNETTUM, Sacrae Theoriae Telluris Autorem / Joseph Addison; Thomas Newcomb
 AD INSIGNISSIMUM VIRUM, D. THOMAM BURNETTUM, SACRAE THEORIAE-TELLURIS AUTOREM / Joseph Addison; Anonymous
 Ad JOANNEM MILTONUM / Stephen Duck
 ADAM Pos'd / Anne Finch (née Kingsmill), countess of Winchilsea
 Address of the STATUES at STOWE, to Lord COBHAM, on his Return to his Gardens, An / Aaron Hill
 ADDRESS TO FRIENDSHIP / Ann Yearsley (née Cromartie)
 Address to his Elbow-chair, new cloath'd, An / William Somerville
 ADDRESS to the DEITY, An / Anna Laetitia Barbauld (née Aikin)
 ADMIRAL HOSIER's GHOST / Richard Glover
 ADVICE to a Lady in Autumn / Philip Dormer Stanhope, 4th Earl of Chesterfield
 ADVICE to a LADY / George Lyttelton, 1st Baron Lyttelton
 ADVICE TO A SHEPHERD / Joseph Cockfield
 ADVICE to MYRTILLO / Mary Leapor
 Advice to the Ladies at Bath / Anonymous
 ADVICE to the Marquis of ROCKINGHAM, upon a late Occasion / David Garrick
 AFRICAN PRINCE, NOW IN ENGLAND, TO ZARA AT HIS FATHER'S COURT, THE / William Dodd
 Agrippina, a Tragedy / Thomas Gray
 ALBIN and the DAUGHTER of MEY / Jerome Stone
 ALCIDOR / Anne Finch (née Kingsmill), countess of Winchilsea
 ALEXIS / Anonymous
 All is Vanity / Anne Finch (née Kingsmill), countess of Winchilsea
 ALLEN AND ELLA / Andrew Hervey Mills
 Alliance of Education and Government. A Fragment, The / Thomas Gray
 AMABELLA / Edward Jerningham
 AMINTA / John Gerrard
 ANACREON. ODE III / William Hall
 ANACREONTIC / William Shenstone
 Another on the same Subject, written with more Judgment, but fewer good Manners / William Taylor

Figure 3.5: Window 3.5: General Work view - the list of titles

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Text Facsimile (Source Edition) TEI/XML (chunk) Downloads

Reading Analysis

ΤΝΩΘΙ ΣΕΑΥΤΟΝ.
 Know YOUR SELF.

WHAT am I? how produc'd and for what end?
 Whence drew I being? to what period tend:
 Am I th' abandon'd orphan of blind chance,
 Drop'd by wild atoms in disorder'd dance?
 Or from an endless chain of causes wrought,
 And of unthinking substance, born with thought?
 By motion which began without a cause,
 Supremely wise, without design or laws?
 Am I but what I seem, mere flesh and blood;
 A branching channel, with a mazy flood?
 The purple stream that through my vessels glides,
 Dull and unconscious flows, like common tides:
 The pipes through which the circling juices stray,
 Are not that thinking I, no more than they:
 This frame compacted with transcendent skill,
 Of moving joints obedient to my will,
 Nurs'd from the fruitful glebe, like yonder tree,
 Waxes and wastes; I call it mine, not me.
 New matter still the mould'ring mass sustains,
 The mansion chang'd, the tenant still remains;
 And from the fleeting stream, repair'd by flood,
 Distinct, as is the swimmer from the flood.
 What am I then, sure, of a nobler birth,
 By parents right, I own as mother, earth;
 But claim superior lineage by my SIRE,
 Who warm'd th' unthinking clod with heavenly fire:
 Essence divine, with lifeless clay ally'd,
 By double nature, double instinct sway'd;
 With look erect, I dart my longing eye,
 Seem wing'd to part, and gain my native sky;
 I strive to mount, but strive, alas! in vain,
 Ty'd to this massy globe with magick chain.
 Now with swift thought I range from pole to pole,
 View worlds around their flaming centers roll:
 What steady powers their endless motions guide,
 Thro' the same trackless paths of boundless void!
 I trace the blazing comet's fiery trail,

5
10
15
20
25
30
35

About this text

Title (in Source Edition): ΤΝΩΘΙ ΣΕΑΥΤΟΝ. Know YOUR SELF.
 Author: John Arbuthnot
 Themes: hopelessness; vanity of life; God [add]
 Genres: heroic couplet; philosophic poetry [add]
 References: DML 21302#
 Text view / Document view

Poetic form

Metrical notation: -+|-+|-+|-+/-
 Metrical foot type: iambic (+-)
 Metrical foot number: pentameter (5 feet)
 Stanza: couplet (2 lines)
 Syllable pattern: 10
 Rhyme scheme: aa
 Rhyme (stanza position): pair (aabb)

Symbols:
 - metrically non-prominent
 + metrically prominent
 | metrical foot boundary
 / metrical line boundary
 || caesura

Source edition

A Collection of Poems in Six Volumes. By Several Hands. Vol. I. London: printed by J. Hughs, for R. and J. Dodsley, 1763 [1st ed. 1758], pp. 180-185. *6v.*: music; 8^{p.} (ESTC T131163#; OTA K104099.001#) (Page images digitized by the Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive from a copy in the archive's library)

Editorial principles

The text has been typographically modernized, but without any silent modernization of spelling, capitalization, or punctuation. The source of the text is given and all editorial interventions have been recorded in textual notes. Based on the electronic text originally produced by the ECCO-TCP# project, this ECPA text has been edited to conform to the recommendations found in Level 5# of the Best Practices for TEI in Libraries version 3.0.

Figure 3.6: Window 3.6: Work view – Reading tab

selects the TOC link in the “Source Edition” section or “Other Works” section of the window of Figure 3.6. The window of Figure 3.9 presents:

- title of the work with a link to the window of Figure 3.6
- author of the work
- catalogue name and catalogue entry ID with a link to said catalogue

The window of Figure 3.10 presents the view after clicking on the tab “Facsimile (Source Text)” of the window of Figure 3.6. This page shows the facsimile of the complete work.

Figure 3.7: Window 3.7: Document view of a work

Figure 3.8: Window 3.8: Word view

Figure 3.9: Window 3.9: Table of Contents of a Source Edition

Figure 3.10: Window 3.10: Work view – Facsimile

The window of Figure 3.11 presents the view when clicking on the tab “TEI/XML chunk” of the window of Figure 3.6. This page shows the codification in XML (using TEI) of the work at hand. The user can edit the code, and propose a new version to the ECPA team, or even download the XML file.

The window of Figure 3.12 presents the view when clicking on the tab “Downloads” of the window of Figure 3.6. This page shows all the downloadable content in relation to the work at hand:

- TXT, TEI chunk and ECPA schema (RelaxNG format)
- Facsimile (images digitized by the Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive from a copy in the archive’s library):
JPG images and PDF with all images.

The window of Figure 3.13 opens when clicking the “analyses” tab of the window of Figure 3.5. This window presents the “results from a number of computationally-assisted analytical processes on five core linguistic levels.”² This information is generated on the fly and it is very important to analyse it in detail since it is not kept in the database. The information is given by line:

- Number of words of the line
- Phonological Layer:
 - Metre:
 - * metre
 - * metrical foot type
 - * metrical foot number
 - * realisation
 - Rhyme
 - * rhyme label
 - * rhyme pattern (position)
 - * rhyme word
 - * related rhymes:

²Text from ECPA help page.

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Text Facsimile (Source Edition) TEI/XML (chunk) Downloads

```

1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
2 <!DOCTYPE div
3 SYSTEM "about:legacy-compat">
4 <div xmlns:tei="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
5   xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
6   xmlns:ecep="http://www.eighteenthcenturypoetry.org/ns"
7   ana="#iamb #pentameter #couplet #heroiccouplet #philosophic #pair"
8   corresp="#txt_ArbuJo1667_w0001"
9   ecep:syllab="I0"
10  met="-+|-+|-+|-+|-+/"
11  rendition="#lgindent"
12  rhyme="aa"
13  subtype="eceptext"
14  type="poem"
15  xml:id="o5152-w0260"
16  decls="#semi-diplomatic">
17 <link target="authors.xml#aut_ArbuJo1667" type="author"/>
18 <link target="21302" type="DMI"/>
19 <head type="main">
20 <seg rendition="#ls #Large">
21 <w xml:id="o5152-404810"
22   n="182-a-0930"
23   ecep:lem="yvæθl"
24   ecep:pos="np1"
25   ecep:reg="ΓNQ0I"
26   ecep:spe="ΓNQ0I"
27   ecep:syllab="1"
28   ecep:pron="g'æmənj'u: 'æmɪgəθ'i:təi'əʊtə">ΓNQ0I</w>
29 </C> </C>
30 <w xml:id="o5152-404820"
31   n="182-a-0940"
32   ecep:lem="ΣEAYTON"
33   ecep:pos="np1"
34   ecep:reg="ΣEAYTON"
35   ecep:spe="ΣEAYTON"
36   ecep:syllab="1"
37   ecep:pron="s'ɪgmæɪ'alfə'ɒpsɪlənt'əʊ'æmɪkrænjɪ'u:">ΣEAYTON</w>
38 <pc xml:id="o5152-404830"
39   n="182-a-0950"
40   unit="sentence"
41   ecep:lem="."
42   ecep:pos="."
43   ecep:reg="."

```

Submit changes Download XML

Figure 3.11: Window 3.11: Work view – TEI encoding

Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive ^{BETA} Home About Authors Works Resources Help

Text Facsimile (Source Edition) TEI/XML (chunk) Downloads

Text

TEI/XML [chunk] (XML - 321K / ZIP - 31K) / ECPA schema (RNC - 357K / ZIP - 73K)
Plain text [excluding paratexts] (TXT - 6.0K / ZIP - 3.2K)

Facsimile

(Page Images digitized by the Eighteenth-Century Poetry Archive from a copy in the archive's library.)

Images

Image #1 (JPEG - 2.5M) Image #4 (JPEG - 2.6M)
Image #2 (JPEG - 2.7M) Image #5 (JPEG - 2.6M)
Image #3 (JPEG - 2.5M) Image #6 (JPEG - 2.6M)

All Images (ZIP - 15M)

PDF

All Images (PDF - 4.9M)

Figure 3.12: Window 3.12: Work view - Downloads

- line number
 - rhyme word
 - nature of similarity
- Rhetorical Figures
- * Type of rhetorical figure (e.g. Assonance, Consonance, Alliteration) (with link to University of

- Waterloo with the definition of the type of rhetorical figure)
 - * pattern
 - * words
 - * affinity
 - * function
- Morphological Layer (see Figure 3.14):
 - Syllables:
 - * Pattern
 - * Counted
 - Morphology
 - * Token
 - * Syllables
 - * Lemma
 - * Class
 - * Part-of-Speech
 - * UC
 - * Frequency
 - * Context
- Syntactic Layer (see Figure 3.15)
 - stanza form
 - syntactic dependency parse
- Semantic Layer (see Figure 3.16): frame semantic parse
- Pragmatic Layer (see Figure 3.17: named entities (e.g. person, date, location, currency, percentage)

Figure 3.13: Window 3.13: Work view – Analysis tab

3.2 Data needs analysis

3.2.1 Data elements of Window 3.1

Table 3.1 presents the data needs of Window 3.1, the list of authors grouped in alphabetic order by their last name.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.1 is related to the entity “Person” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Person” is: Opus–hasCreator–Person

3.2.2 Data elements of Window 3.2

Table 3.2 presents the data needs of Window 3.2, a window that presents the list of authors grouped by date of birth.

Morphological layer

Syllables
Pattern: 10 / Counted: 10

Morphology

Token	Syll	Lemma	Class	Part-of-speech	UC	Freq	Context
WHAT	1	what	wh-word	Interrogative use, wh-word	Y	12	KWIC on
am	1	be	verb	first person singular, 'be'	N	4	KWIC on
I	1	i	pronoun	first person singular subjective, personal pronoun	Y	24	KWIC on
how	1	how	wh-word	interrogative use, wh-word	N	1	KWIC on
produc'd	2	produce	verb	past tense, verb	N	1	KWIC on
and	1	and	conjunction	coordinating conjunction	N	31	KWIC on
for	1	for	adverb / conjunction / particle / preposition	acp word as preposition	N	5	KWIC on
what	1	what	wh-word	relative use, wh-word	N	12	KWIC on
end	1	end	noun	singular, noun	N	1	KWIC on

Rhetorical figures

Diacope ([scheme](#))
pattern: **WHAT/what**; words: **WHAT/what**; affinity: repetition; function: [\[?\]](#)

Syncope ([scheme](#))
pattern: **produc'd**; words: **produc'd**; affinity: omission, reduction; function: [\[?\]](#)

Figure 3.14: Window 3.14: Work view – Morphological Layer

Syntactic layer

Stanza
Form: couplet (2 lines)

Syntactic dependency parse
Sentence no. 1 (9 words):

[\[nouns / pronouns / verbs / adjectives / adverbs / other\]](#) [edit](#)

This text has 26 sentences. [Sentencing on](#)

Figure 3.15: Window 3.15: Work view – Syntactic Layer

Semantic layer

Frame semantic parse
Sentence no. 1 (9 words):

[\[Tokens // FRAMES // Frame elements \(frame-specific roles\)\]](#) [\[Found an error?\]](#)

Figure 3.16: Window 3.16: Work view – Semantic Layer

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.2 is related to the entity “Person” of the POSTDATA’s

Figure 3.17: Window 3.17: Work view – Pragmatic Layer

Table 3.1: Data elements of Window 3.1

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Author	1	1	Opens Window 3.4	name.Person
Date of birth	1	0		birthDate.Person
Date of death	1	0		deathDate.Person

Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Person” is: Opus–hasCreator–Person

Table 3.2: Data elements of Window 3.2

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Author	1	1	Opens Window 3.4	name.Person
Period	1	0	In decades	<i>not relevant</i>
Date of birth	1	0		birthDate.Person
Date of death	1	0		deathDate.Person

3.2.3 Data elements of Window 3.3

Table 3.3 presents the data needs of Window 3.3, a window that presents the list of authors grouped by gender.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.3 is related to the entity “Person” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Person” is: Opus–hasCreator–Person

Table 3.3: Data elements of Window 3.3

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Author	1	1	Opens Window 3.4	name.Person
Date of birth	1			birthDate.Person
Date of death	1			deathDate.Person
Gender	1	1		gender.Person

3.2.4 Data elements of Window 3.4

Table 3.4 presents the data needs of Window 3.4, a window that presents a detailed view of an author.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.4 is related to the entity “Person” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Opus” is: Opus–hasCreator–Person

Table 3.4: Data elements of Window 3.4

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of the author	1			name.Person
Date of birth	1			birthDate.Person
Date of death	1			deathDate.Person
WORK	M			Person-creates-Opus
Title	1	1	Opens Window 3.5	title.Opus
SOURCE EDITION	M			Person-creates-Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource
TOC	1	1	Opens Window 3.9	toc.PrimarySource
Title	1			title.PrimarySource
Publisher	1			publisher.PrimarySource
Volume	1			volumeNumber.PrimarySource
Place	1			pubPlace.PrimarySource
Person that orders printing	1			PrimarySource-wasOrderedBy-Person + name.Person
Year	1			date.PrimarySource
Year of 1st Edition	1			firstEditionDate.PrimarySource
Total number of volumes	1			numberOfVolumes.PrimarySource
CATALOG ENTRY	M			PrimarySource-isCataloguedIn-Location
Name	1			Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
Biographical note	1			biography.Person
BIBLIOGRAPHY	M			—
BIBLIOGRAPHIC ENTRY	M			Person-isReferencedIn-Location
Index ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
Name of Entry	1			Location-refersThrough-BibliographicSource + title.BibliographicSource
BOOK	M			Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource
Book Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Type of Book	1			typeOfBibliographicItem.BibliographicSource
BOOK AUTHOR	M			BibliographicSource-hasCreator-Person
Author Name	1	0		name.Person
BOOK EDITOR	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person
Editor Name	1			name.Person
Volume	1			volumeNumber.BibliographicSource
Publication Place	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
Date	1			date.BibliographicSource
Pages in the volume	1			BibliographicSource-refersThrough-Location + location.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external link	url.Location
Other information	1			<i>not relevant</i>

3.2.5 Data elements of Window 3.5

Table 3.5 presents the data needs of Window 3.5. This Window is the default entry for work, listing all the works of the ECPA repertoire.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.5 is related to the entity “Opus” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model.

Table 3.5: Data elements of Window 3.5

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1	1	Opens Window 3.6	title.Opus
Author Name	1			Opus–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Type of alphabet of the title	1			<i>not relevant</i>

3.2.6 Data elements of Window 3.6

Table 3.6 presents the data needs of Window 3.6. This Window presents the detailed view of a particular work.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.6 is related to the entity “Redaction”, “StanzaPattern” and “LinePattern” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to these entities is:

- Redaction: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction
- StanzaPattern: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern
- LinePattern: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–LinePattern

Table 3.6: Data elements of Window 3.6

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.Opus
Sub-title	1			subtitle.Opus
Title in Source Edition	1			originalTitle.Opus
Author Name	1			Opus–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Translator Name	1			Opus–hasTranslator–Person + name.Person
Theme	M			theme.Opus
Genre	M	0		genre.Opus
REFERENCE	M			Opus–isCataloguedIn–Location
Name	1			Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource + title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
Type of View	1			<i>Possibility to switch between two instances of the entity Redaction: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction</i>
Metre	1			accentualMetricalScheme.LinePattern
Metrical foot type	1			footType.LinePattern
Metrical foot number	1			numberOfFeet.LinePattern
Stanza	1			metricalType.StanzaPattern
Syllable pattern	1			numberOfSyllables.LinePattern

Continued on next page

Table 3.6 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Rhyme Scheme	1			rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Rhyme (Stanza Position)	1			rhymeDispositionType.StanzaPattern
METRICAL ENCODING	M			StanzaPattern–uses– MetricalEncoding
Symbol used	1			metricalSymbol.MetricalEncoding
Symbol Explanation	1			metricalSymbolExplanation .MetricalEncoding
SOURCE EDITION	M			Redaction–interprets–Witness– isPart–PrimarySource
Book Title	1			title.PrimarySource
TOC of the Book	1	1	Opens Win- dow 3.9	toc.PrimarySource
BOOK AUTHOR	M			PrimarySource–hasCreator–Person
Author Name	1			name.Person
Publisher	1			publisher.PrimarySource
Page Numbers	1	1	Opens external private page	location.Witness
Publication Place	1			pubPlace.PrimarySource
Edition	1			editionNumber.PrimarySource
Year	1			date.PrimarySource
REFERENCE IN CATALOGUE	M			PrimarySource–isCataloguedIn– Location–refersAsPart– BibliographicSource
Name	1			title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
Editorial Principles	1			editionNotes.Redaction
OTHER WORK	M			Person–creates–Opus (<i>same instance of Person of entry “Author Name”</i>)
Work title	1	1	Opens Win- dow 3.6	title.Opus
TOC of the Source Edition	1	1	Opens Win- dow 3.9	Redaction–interprets–Witness– isPart–PrimarySource + toc.PrimarySource

3.2.7 Data elements of Window 3.7

Table 3.7 presents the data needs of Window 3.7 (see Figure 3.7). This Window is the Document View of Window 3.6. This table only presents the elements of the left side of Window 3.7 that are different from Window 3.6.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.7 is related to the entities “Opus/Redaction”.

Table 3.7: Data elements of Window 3.7

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.Opus
Sub-title	1			subtitle.Opus
Author name	1	1	Opens Window 3.4	Opus–hasCreator– Person + name.Person

Continued on next page

Table 3.7 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
PAGE NUMBER	M			Redaction–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine–Line) + nextPageNumber.Line
Page in the Source Edition	1	1	Each time the text changes page, there is a page number reference. The link opens the Facsimile of the page.	—

3.2.8 Data elements of Window 3.8

Table 3.8 presents the data needs of Window 3.8 (see Figure 3.8). This Window gives the information about a Word.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.8 is related to the entity “Word” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Word” is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine–Line)–hasFirstToken–Word/Punctuation (nextToken)–Word/Punctuation.

Table 3.8: Data elements of Window 3.8

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
WORD PROPERTY	M			Word
Standard Form	1			content.Word
Lemma	1			lemma.Word
Part of Speech	1			morphologicalAnnotation.Word
Pronunciation (IPA)	1			phoneticTranscription.Word
EXTERNAL TOOL	M			—
DICTIONARY	M			Word–isReferencedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource + typeOfBibliographicItem.BibliographicSource (=dictionary)
Name	1			title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
ENCYCLOPEDIA	M			Word–isReferencedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource + typeOfBibliographicItem.BibliographicSource (=encyclopedia)
Name	1			title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location

3.2.9 Data elements of Window 3.9

Table 3.9 presents the data needs of Window 3.9 (see Figure 3.9). This Window gives the table of contents of a book that is a Source Edition of a work.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.8 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of the POST-DATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “PrimarySource” is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–interprets–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 3.9: Data elements of Window 3.9

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.PrimarySource
Author Name	M			PrimarySource–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Publisher	1			publisher.PrimarySource
Number of Pages	1	1	Opens external page	numberOfPages.PrimarySource
Publication Place	1			pubPlace.PrimarySource
Edition	1			editionNumber.PrimarySource
Publication Year	1			date.PrimarySource
CATALOGUE	1			PrimarySource–isCataloguedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
Name	1			title.BibliographicSource
ID	1			identifier.Location
URL	1	1	Opens external page	url.Location
WORK ENTRY	M			PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness–isInterpretedBy–Redaction
Title	1	1	Opens Window 3.6	title.Redaction
Author Name	1			Redaction–hasCreator–Person + name.Person

3.2.10 Data elements of Window 3.10

Table 3.10 presents the data needs of Window 3.10 (see Figure 3.10). This Window gives the Facsimile images, ordered, of the work in the Source Edition.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.10 is related to the entity “Facsimile” of the POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Facsimile” is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–interprets–Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile

Table 3.10: Data elements of Window 3.10

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Facsimile Image	1			url.Facsimile
Order Number	1	1	Opens Facsimile image number	Facsimile–nextPage–Facsimile

3.2.11 Data elements of Window 3.12

Table 3.11 presents the data needs of Window 3.12 (see Figure 3.12). This Window allows users to download the XML files (XML or ZIP, and ECPA schema RNC), plain text, and the images of the Facsimile of the text of the Source Edition (individual images in jpg, a zip file with all the images JPG and a PDF file).

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.11 is related to the entity “Redaction” of the POSTDATA’s

Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “Redaction” is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 3.11: Data elements of Window 3.12

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
TEXT FILE	M			—
TEI/XML [chunk] - XML	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
TEI/XML [chunk] - ZIP	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
ECPA schema - RelaxNG	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
ECPA schema - ZIP	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
FACSIMILE	M			—
Image jpg	M	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
Image zip	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction
Image pdf	1	1	Downloads file	additionalFile.Redaction

3.2.12 Data elements of Window 3.13

Table 3.12 presents the data needs of Window 3.13. This Window presents the details of a work – Analysis tab.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 3.11 is related to the entity “LinePattern” of the POST-DATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to “LinePattern” is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-FirstLine-Line(nextLine-Line)-isAnalysedThrough-LinePattern

Table 3.12: Data elements of Window 3.13

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Line Number	1			lineNumber.Line
Number or Words of the line	1			<i>not relevant</i>
Metre	1			accentualMetricalScheme.LinePattern
Metre: Metrical foot type	1			footTtype.LinePattern
Metre: Metrical foot number	1			numberOfFeet.LinePattern feetType.LinePattern
Metre: Realisation	1			altAccentualMetricalScheme .LinePattern
Rhyme: Rhyme Label	1			Line-presents-Rhyme + label.Rhyme
Rhyme: pattern (position)	1			redundant
Rhyme: Rhyme Word	1			Line-presents-Rhyme + rhymeWord.Rhyme
RHYME: RELATED RHYME	M			Line-presents-Rhyme-matches- RhymeMatch
Line Number	1			RhymeMatch- lineOfEcho lineofCall-Line + lineNumber.Line
Rhyme Word	1			rhymeWordMatch.RhymeMatch
nature of similarity	1			typeOfRhymeMatching.RhymeMatch
RHETORICAL FIGURES	M			Line-presents-FigureOfSpeech
Type of rhetorical figure	1	1	URL to external page	device.FigureOfSpeech

Continued on next page

Table 3.12 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
pattern	1	1	Highlights the words in the whole text that have the same pattern	FigureOfSpeech-hasRelationsWith-Word
Repetition	M			commentary.FigureOfSpeech + FigureOfSpeech-hasRelationsWith-Word
Text total number of tokens	1			<i>not relevant</i>
Syllables: Pattern	1			syllabicMetricalScheme.LinePattern
Syllables: Counted	1			numberOfSyllables-LinePattern
Stanza Form	1			metricalType.StanzaPattern
Named Entities	M			Line-mentions-Place + name.Place
				Line-mentions-Person + name.Place
Total number of Named Entities	1			<i>not relevant</i>

Chapter 4

Estonian Runic Songs

URL: <http://www.folklore.ee/regilaul/andmebaas/>

4.1 Informational Needs

Figure 4.1 presents the entry page of the Estonian Runic Songs Database.

The screenshot shows the search interface of the Estonian Runic Songs Database. The title is "EESTI REGILAULUDE ANDMEBAAS" (ESTONIAN RUNIC SONGS' DATABASE). The interface includes several search filters:

- County:** abroad, Harjumaa, Järvamaa, Läänemaa, Pärnumaa
- Place:** Ambla, Anna, Anseküla, Audru, Emmaste
- The collector:** is (dropdown), First letter of surname (dropdown), All collectors (dropdown)
- Time of collecting:** min (dropdown) - max (dropdown)
- Words included:** in verses (dropdown) or (text input), choose (dropdown)
- Class:** Upper class (all classes dropdown), Subclass (all subclasses dropdown), Tüüp (koik tüübid dropdown)
- Function:** all functions (dropdown), Genre: jutt (dropdown)
- Results:** Show 20 (dropdown) results, Show the original (dropdown) version

On the right side, there are links to related resources: The Runic Song Site, Estonian Folklore Archives, Estonian Literary Museum, Estonian Folklorists' Server, Finnish Runic Songs' Database, introduction, and supporters. Logos for ERA and EESTI KIRJANDUSMUSEUM are also visible.

Figure 4.1: Window 4.1: Estonian Runic Songs Database FrontPage

This Window allows the user to search by:

- Place (county and parish)
- The collector (is; is another than): the search is done by surname
- Time of collection: between two year dates. It allows the definition of “unkown” as either of the values of the range
- Words contained in:
 - verses
 - data
 - comments
- Classes and sub-classes of songs (e.g. wedding songs, songs of marriage, mourning songs)
- Types of songs (e.g. some kurds, breakfast halls, Mother on the grave)
- Genres of songs (e.g. facts, story, history)
- Functions of songs (e.g. spell, sad home)

During the definition of the search the user can also choose between obtaining the **edited version** or **original version** of the song. In the edited version there was a regularisation accommodating the text to the modern orthography rules that enable a more efficient search. The dialectical features, however, have been preserved. In the original version the style of the collector is maintained.

Figure 2 presents the result of a search conducted on the window of Figure 4.1, selecting the type of song “Arbijalaul”.

EESTI REGILAULUDE ANDMEBAAS
ESTONIAN RUNIC SONGS' DATABASE

Maksimaalne eksporditav laulude arv on 1000

[New search](#)
[Show search](#)
[Näita kaardil](#)
[TXT Export of chosen files](#)
[XML Export of chosen files](#)
[TXT Ekspordi kõik](#)
[XML Ekspordi kõik](#)

In all 2 Show 1-2 » Go to page /1

<input type="checkbox"/>	Number	Place	The collector	Time
<input type="checkbox"/>	E, StK 33, 76/85 (21)	Setu, Napi k.	V. Kalle	1926
<input type="checkbox"/>	E, StK 22, 126/8 (4)	Setu, Kerbä k.	Harald Jänes	1924

[» The Runic Song Site](#)
[» Estonian Folklore Archives](#)
[» Estonian Literary Museum](#)
[» Estonian Folklorists' Server](#)
[» Finnish Runic Songs' Database](#)
[» introduction](#)
[» supporters](#)

ERA EESH KIRJANDUSMUSEUM ESTONIAN LITERARY MUSEUM

Contact Piksel

Figure 4.2: Window 4.2: Result of a search (type of Song “Arbijalaul”)

The result presents the information in a table concerning:

- The number of the song. As far as we understand this number is unique and taken from a catalogue
- The name of the collector
- The place of collection
- The year of collection

The window of Figure 4.2 also allows the user 1) to go to a map of the place where the song was collected; and 2) export the selected results in a TXT or XML file (local encoding).

When clicking on the number of the song, the system opens the window of Figure 4.3 presenting details of the selected song. This Window presents the number of the song, the name of the collector, the place where the song was collected and the date of the collecting, and, finally, the content of the song organised in pages as it is in the original version. On this window the user can switch between the original version and the edited version. The data needs of both versions are the same so we only present one of them.

E, StK 33, 76/85 (21)

» Show the edited version

E, StK 33, 76/85 (21) < Setu, Napi k. - V. Kalle < Nasta Kuuste (Höödori Nasta) (1926)
tüübinimed kontrollimata
Au-, sõja- ja kooluhein + Arbijalaul
Lüroepilised laulud

Mõtsa minek.
Tulli üles hummogulla
Astõ üles aigsahe
Mia oll tüü edimäne
Kua huuli hummogunõ
Käppe ol' l jala kangiminõ
Sorrõ suu mõskõminõ
Känge jala' käügi pääle
Heidi sõlmõ' sõidu poolõ
lätsi näio minemähe
Kabukõnõ kallumahe
Arä lätsi tükkü teedä
Kulla käve pala maad
Arä mul kaksi tsuvva kabla'
Perrä vinnü viisu kabla'
Lei käe kätt vasta
Tõista vasta tõrahudi

pag. 77
Mia õks tettä kohe minnä
Kohe minnä kullakõsõl.
Istõ ma maalõ jakkumahe
Kivi pääle kinnitämä
Näio sis lätsi jal minemä
Kabukõnõ kallumahe
Kia mul vasta puttusigi
Puttusigi johtusigi
Johtu säääl vasta vanameesi
Puttu vasta puhas meesi
Küsütelli nõvvatõli
Kohe sa läät näiokõnõ
Kohe kallut kabokõnõ
Toolõ ma lausi meelestäni
Poolõ meele poolõstani

pag. 78
Lää ma mõtsa minemähe
Varikohe valamahe
Vanameesi vasta lausi
lausi tä umast meelestäni
Naiokõnõ noorõkõnõ
Mino meeli maräkõnõ

Figure 4.3: Window 4.3: A song

4.2 Data needs analysis

4.2.1 Data elements of Window 1

Table 4.1 presents the data needs of Window 4.1. This Window is the entry page of the Website, where the user can search for a song or group of songs.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 4.1 is related to the entities “Opus” and “Redaction”. The core of the POSTDATA model is the entity Opus, which represents an abstract piece of Work (e.g. a poem). An “Opus” relates to a “Redaction” (which is the work materialised in, for example, a text) as follows: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction.

4.2.2 Data elements of Window 4.2

Table 4.2 presents the data needs of Window 4.2; this page is the result of a search done on Window 4.1.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 4.2 is related to the entities “Opus” and “Redaction”.

Table 4.1: Data elements of Window 4.1

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Place	1			Opus-comesFrom-Place + name.Place
Parish	1			Opus-comesFrom-Place + settlement.Place
Collector name	1		The search is done using the surname of the collector. Dropdown list with all possibilities of the database	Redaction-interprets-Witness-hasCollector-Person + name.Person
Date of collection min	1			Redaction-interprets-Witness + dateOfCollection.Witness
Date of collection max	1			Redaction-interprets-Witness + dateOfCollection.Witness
String match	1			text.Redaction
Class of song	1		Dropdown list with all possibilities of the database	genre.Redaction
Type of song	1		Dropdown list with all possibilities of the database	genre.Redaction
Function of song	1		Dropdown list with all possibilities of the database	function.Opus function.Redaction

The core of the POSTDATA model is the entity Opus, which represents an abstract piece of Work (e.g. a poem). An “Opus” relates to a “Redaction” (which is the work materialised in, for example, a text) as follows: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction.

Table 4.2: Data elements of Window 4.2

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Number of Song	1	1	Opens Window 4.3	Redaction-interprets-Witness + workNumber.Witness
Place	1			Opus-comesFromPlace + name.Place
Collector name	1			Redaction-interprets-Witness-hasCollector-Person + name.Person
Date of collecting	1			Redaction-interprets-Witness + dateOfCollection.Witness
TXT content	1	1	downloads content in TXT	additionalFile.Redaction
XML content	1	1	downloads content in XML	additionalFile.Redaction
Localisation in a map	1	1	Opens map. Its contents have not been analysed by the authors due to their lack of knowledge about the Estonian language	Opus-comesFrom-Place + latitude.Place + longitude.Place

4.2.3 Data elements of Window 4.3

Table 4.3 presents the data needs of Window 4.3, this page is the result of a search done on Window 4.2.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 4.3 is related to the entities “Opus” and “Redaction”. The core of the POSTDATA model is the entity Opus, which represents an abstract piece of Work (e.g. a poem). An “Opus” relates to a “Redaction” (which is the work materialised in, for example, a text) as follows: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction.

Table 4.3: Data elements of Window 4.3

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Type of edition			Possibility to switch between both editions (original or edited)	typeOfRedaction.Redaction
Number of Song	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness + workNumber.Witness
Place	1			Opus–comesFromPlace + name.Place
Collector name	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness–collectsMaterials–Person + name.Person
Date of collecting	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness + dateOfCollection.Witness
Type of Song	M			genre.Redaction
Class of Song	M			genre.Redaction
Content of the song	1			Redaction–hasFirstLine–Line(nextLine–Line) + content.Line
Page number	M		The content is organised by page.	Redaction–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine–Line) + nextPageNumber.Line

Chapter 5

Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages

URL: <http://skaldic.abdn.ac.uk/m.php?p=skaldic>

5.1 Informational Needs

The Skaldic entry page provides various entries. We will limit our analysis to the entries: Manuscripts, Works, Runic poetry, Skalds (authors) and Kennings since the remaining topics are not relevant to our project. The window of Figure 5.1 presents the default entry page.

Figure 5.1: Window 5.1: Skaldic project frontpage

If the user clicks on “Manuscripts,” the system opens the window of Figure 5.2. As described in the own contents of the website, this window presents a list that “contains manuscripts relevant to the *skaldic* database, plus some printed works and other objects that have independent textual evidence for the corpus.” Each entry presents the siglum of the manuscript and a number whose meaning we were unable to infer.

If the user clicks on “Poems,” the system opens the window of Figure 5.3. The window presents a list of the works (that is, “Lausavísur, fragments and other groupings will appear with information for individual skalds”) on the database. Each entry displays the title of the work and the number of stanzas it contains.

If the user clicks on “Runic Poetry,” the system opens the window of Figure 5.4. This window presents a list of the runic poetry available in the Skaldic database organised by period: Older *Futharc*, Viking age and Middle ages. Each entry presents the name of the period and the total number of works of the period at hand.

If the user clicks on “Skalds” (authors), the system opens the window of Figure 5.5. This window displays a

Manuscripts

This list contains manuscripts relevant to the skaldic database, plus some printed works and other objects that have independent textual evidence for the corpus.

Q Filter items...

UppsUB R 693	29	>
Adv 21 4 7	1	>
Adv 21 5 2	5	>
Adv 21 6 7 II	1	>
AM 6 fol	29	>
AM 9 fol	11	>
AM 10 fol	10	>
AM 11 fol	11	>
AM 18 fol	1	>
AM 19 fol	2	>
AM 20 b I fol	19	>
AM 20 b II fol	7	>
AM 20 d fol	32	>
AM 20 i 23 fol	5	>
AM 35 fol (Kringla)	197	>
AM 36 fol (Kringla)	177	>
AM 37 fol (Kringla)	55	>

Figure 5.2: Window 5.2: Skaldic project – Manuscripts

Poems

Note that only named poems are listed here. *Lausavísur*, fragments and other groupings will appear with information for individual skalds.

Q Filter items...

Aðalsteinsdrápa (Egill Skallagrímsson)	2	>
Aðalsteinsdrápa (Gunnlaugr ormstunga Illugason)	1	>
Allra postula minnisvísur (Anonymous Poems)	13	>
An exchange of verses between Bragi and a troll-woman (Bragi inn gamli Boddason)	1	>
Andréasdrápa (Anonymous Poems)	4	>
Ara heiti (Anonymous Pulur)	1	>
Arinbjarnarkviða (Egill Skallagrímsson)	25	>
Atlöguflokkur (Ingjaldr Geirmundarson)	6	>
Austrfararvísur (Sigvatr Þórðarson)	21	>
Á heiti (Anonymous Pulur)	6	>
Árónsdrápa (Óláfr hvítaskáld Þórðarson)	2	>
Ása heiti I (Anonymous Pulur)	1	>
Ása heiti II (Anonymous Pulur)	1	>
Ásynja heiti (Anonymous Pulur)	5	>
Bandadrápa (Eyjólfur dáðaskáld)	9	>
Bárðardrápa (Anonymous Poems)	1	>
Bersögglisvísur (Sigvatr Þórðarson)	18	>
Berudrápa (Egill Skallagrímsson)	1	>

Figure 5.3: Window 5.3: Skaldic project – Works

list with “all named persons to whom poetry in the corpus is attributed.” Each entry contains the name of the *skald* and the total number of their works in the database.

If the user clicks on “Kennings,” the system opens the window of Figure 5.6. This window presents a list of all classified *kennings*.

Figure 5.4: Window 5.4: Skaldic project – Runic Poetry

Figure 5.5: Window 5.5: Skaldic project – Skalds (authors)

5.1.1 Manuscripts

When the user clicks in one entry of the window of Figure 5.2, the system opens the Window of Figure 5.7. This Window presents:

- the siglum of the manuscript
- the type of material of the manuscript (the support)
- the approximate dates of the manuscript (e.g. 1755-1758)
- the location of the manuscript (e.g. *National Library of Scotland*)
- a list of the contents (works). Each entry has:
 - the name of the work
 - folios (locus, the beginning and ending of the work)
 - a link to the original text and sources (see Window of Figure 8)
 - if the work is in prose, the link opens a list of stanzas that belong to the same work (see the window of Figure 5.9)
 - “Text and Images”. Each entry has the following information per folio:
 - * the number of the folio
 - * the image definition of the facsimile of the folio at hand
 - * a link to the facsimile of the current folio that opens the window of Figure 5.10
 - * Each entry of the facsimile has from one to several entries. Each entry has:
 - the line numbers of the folio where a work is located
 - the nickname of the author

Kennings

Kennings are circumlocutions where two nouns (as a compound or genitive(s)) refer to a third, unspoken noun. Elements can be substituted with further kennings. There are around 10,000 kennings in the corpus, most of which are unique. This is a list of the kennings in the published volumes, grouped according to Meissner's categories where applicable.

E.g. (random): *hjaldrmós* — 'of the battle-gull' = RAVEN/EAGLE — in *RvHbreiðm HI 50*^{III}

classified	unclassified	ungrouped	named referents	big kennings
------------	--------------	-----------	-----------------	--------------

(Referents classified according to Meissner's categories, where relevant. This list is [in progress](#) and should not be cited.)

air	1	▶
arm, hand	71	▶
armour	13	▶
arrow, spear	59	▶
axe	19	▶
battle	600	▶
beard	1	▶
bed	1	▶
bird of prey	102	▶
blood	81	▶
bow	1	▶
cat, mouse	2	▶
cave	6	▶
chest	42	▶

Figure 5.6: Window 5.6: Skaldic project – Kennings

- the number of the work
- the name of the work
- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.11 with details about the work at hand

On its default view (“Contents” tab), the window of Figure 5.8 displays the following details about one work:

- the title of the work
- the nickname of the author of the work
- edition of the work: a chapter in a book with all the details of the bibliographic reference
- the paleographic transcription of the work and its translation, organised by stanzas; each stanza has a stanza number with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.11
- a “Sources” tab that opens the window of Figure 5.12
- an “Introduction” tab that opens the window of Figure 5.13.
- buttons that allow the user to navigate between stanzas of the work at hand
- a button to go back to the whole text divided by stanzas (see the window of Figure 5.8)
- a button to go to all texts/works written by the same author (see the window of Figure 5.34 on Section 5.1.4)

The window of Figure 5.9 presents an ordered list of stanzas of the same work in prose, with the title of the stanza, the abbreviated name of the author and the title of the edition. Each entry has a link that opens the window of Figure 5.11.

The window of Figure 5.10 presents the following information:

- the image of the facsimile selected on the window of Figure 5.7
- two buttons to go to the next and previous pages of the facsimile at hand
- a button to go back to the manuscript, the window of Figure 5.7, of the facsimile at hand
- other facsimiles available of the same work
- the option “On this page”: lists the works present in the same facsimile: each entry has the siglum of the manuscript where the work is, the *incipit* of the work, and a link that opens the window of Figure 5.11
- the folios of the Witness

The window of Figure 5.11 presents information about a specific stanza on a work:

- the name of the author
- a critical edition of the stanza: the complete bibliographic reference to a book chapter
- text and translation section: the contents of the critical edition of the stanza and a translation in English
- notes and context section: notes about the stanza
- readings (apparatus) section: each entry on “readings” includes the location (line and word), the variant

AM 173 fol^X (173^X)

paper; in Reykjavík; c1700; The Arnarnagnæan Collection, Den arnamagnæanske samling, Nordisk forskningsinstitut, University of Copenhagen and Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum, Reykjavík

contents

Sturlaugs saga starfsama	1r-18v
Gríms saga loðinkinna	11v-16r
Orvar-Odds saga	17r-65v
Ans saga bogsvægis	66r-79v
Fríðþjófs saga ins frækna	80r-95r

text and images

page images sts/text

7 | 150dpi
8 | 150dpi
9 | 150dpi
10 | 150dpi
11 | 150dpi
13 | 150dpi
14 | 150dpi
15 | 150dpi
16 | 150dpi
17 | 150dpi
19 | 150dpi
20 | 150dpi
21 | 150dpi
22 | 150dpi
12r | 150dpi 30-07: Gríml Lv 1^{VIII} (GrL 1)
12v | 150dpi 09-16: Feima Lv 1^{VIII} (GrL 2)
18-25: Gríml Lv 2^{VIII} (GrL 3)
27-03: Kleima Lv 1^{VIII} (GrL 4)
30-07: Gríml Lv 1^{VIII} (GrL 1)
13r | 150dpi 27-03: Kleima Lv 1^{VIII} (GrL 4)
15v | 150dpi 17-24: Gríml Lv 4^{VIII} (GrL 6)
25-27: Gríml Lv 5^{VIII} (GrL 7)
19r | 150dpi 08-15: Heiðr Lv 1^{VIII} (Orv 1)
16-23: Heiðr Lv 2^{VIII} (Orv 2)
24-31: Heiðr Lv 3^{VIII} (Orv 3)
24v | 150dpi 16-23: OrvOdd Ævdr 21^{VIII} (Orv 91)
26v | 150dpi 29-03: OrvOdd Lv 5^{VIII} (Orv 13)
30r | 150dpi 24-31: OrvOdd Ævdr 38^{VIII} (Orv 108)
31r | 150dpi 24-29: Orv Lv 1^{VIII} (Orv 4)
31v | 150dpi 01-08: OrvOdd Ævdr 41^{VIII} (Orv 111)
35r | 150dpi 19-28: Hjálml Lv 1^{VIII} (Orv 5)
30-04: Hjálml Lv 2^{VIII} (Orv 6)
35v | 150dpi 07-14: OrvOdd Lv 1^{VIII} (Orv 7)
18-27: OrvOdd Lv 2^{VIII} (Orv 8)
30-04: Hjálml Lv 2^{VIII} (Orv 6)
36r | 150dpi 29-03: OrvOdd Lv 5^{VIII} (Orv 13)

Figure 5.7: Window 5.7: After clicking on an entry of Window 5.2

Hugsvinnsmál — Anon ^{VII}Hsv

← Anonymous Poems

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper 2007, '(Introduction to) Anonymous, *Hugsvinnsmál*' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 358-449.

contents	sources	introduction
1.	Heyri seggir, þeir er vilja at sið lifa ok góð verk gera, horsklígr ráð, þau er heiðinn maðr kendi sínum syni.	'Men who want to live with good conduct and do good works should listen to the wise advice that a heathen man taught his son.'
2.	Ástsamlígr ráð kenni ek þér, minn einkason; mun þú þau eptir öll; gálaus þú verðr, ef þú gleyma vilt, því er þarf horskr at hafa.	'I will teach you, my only son, loving advice; remember all of it; you will be careless if you forget what a wise [man] needs to have.'
3.	Þarflátr ok þakklátr skaltu fyrir þínum guði ok vammalauss vera; föður ok móður unn þú fróðhugaðr; ræktu þína alla ætt.	'You must be humble and thankful and unblemished before your God; love your father and mother as a man with intelligence; take care of all your family.'
4.	Ef þér góðan grip gefa hollir vinir, eiga þú skalt ok unna allvel; góðu þú fylg, en gakk illu frá; hvergi þú fyrir ráð rasir.	'If loyal friends give you a precious thing, you must own it and enjoy it well; follow good and keep away from evil; by no means rush in headlong.'
5.	Hreinlífr þú vert, ok hræztu þinn læriföður; halt þú heiðsæi.	'Be pure of life and fear your teacher; preserve your reverence.'
6.	Bragna hvern, er þú á brautu finnr, kveð þú hann kunnliga; ófróðr er sá, er einskis spyr, ef finnr at máli mann.	'Each man whom you meet on the road, greet him intimately; he who does not ask is unwise, if he finds a man to talk to.'
7.	Afli deila þú skalt aldri þér við máttugra mann; athuga öflugann skaltu við alt hafa, ok ræk þín hús ok hjú.	'You must never test your strength with a mightier man; you must have strengthened attention for everything, and take care of your house and household.'

Figure 5.8: Window 5.8: After clicking on an entry of the manuscript (Window 5.7–Figure 5.7)

and its location in the Witness. Each entry contains a link to more details about the apparatus (opens the window of Figure 5.14)

- sources section: a list of other witnesses of the same work in other manuscripts. Every entry declares:

contents	sources
Stanzas in prose work	
1. Hallm Hallkv 1 ^V (Bergb 1)	>
2. Hallm Hallkv 2 ^V (Bergb 2)	>
3. Hallm Hallkv 3 ^V (Bergb 3)	>
4. Hallm Hallkv 4 ^V (Bergb 4)	>
5. Hallm Hallkv 5 ^V (Bergb 5)	>
6. Hallm Hallkv 6 ^V (Bergb 6)	>
7. Hallm Hallkv 7 ^V (Bergb 7)	>
8. Hallm Hallkv 8 ^V (Bergb 8)	>
9. Hallm Hallkv 9 ^V (Bergb 9)	>
10. Hallm Hallkv 10 ^V (Bergb 10)	>
11. Hallm Hallkv 11 ^V (Bergb 11)	>
12. Hallm Hallkv 12 ^V (Bergb 12)	>

Figure 5.9: Window 5.9: A list of stanzas that belong to the same work in prose

Figure 5.10: Window 5.10: After clicking in a link of a folio on a entry of the manuscript (Window 5.7–Figure 5.7)

- the siglum of the manuscript
- the folios where the stanza is located
- the paleographic edition
- the interpretative edition
- the abbreviated name of the editor of the paleographic edition
- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.15, with the possibility to see the facsimile of the witness in another page
- a link that opens a thumbnail of the facsimile of the page of the witness (see the window of Figure 5.16)
- editions and texts section: bibliographic references that contains information about the stanza at hand
- if the stanza is also part of other works, the system presents a menu at the bottom of the page that allows the user to go to any of those works (see detail on Figure 5.17):
 - each entry of the menu (the works that also contain the current stanza) has a link that opens the window of Figure 5.9 that presents the complete work
- an “interactive” tab, that opens the window of Figure 5.18
- a “full text” tab, that opens the window of Figure 5.19

The window of Figure 5.12 presents the sources (manuscripts) that are related to the complete work or to parts of it (separated). Each entry has:

- the siglum of the manuscript
- the folios where said work is located

Anon *Hsv* 1^{VII}

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper (eds) 2007, 'Anonymous Poems, *Hugsvinnsmál* 1' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 361-2.

Anonymous Poems > Hugsvinnsmál >

1 ▾ 2 ⇄

information

interactive

full text

Page structure <

text and translation

Heyri seggir, þeir er vilja at sið lifa
ok góð verk gera,
horsklig ráð, þau er heiðinn maðr
kendi sínum syni.

(Men who want to live with good conduct and do good works should listen to the wise advice that a heathen man taught his son.)

Top ^

notes and context

Lat. parallel: (*Epistula*) *Cum animadverterem quam plurimos graviter in via morum errare, succurrendum opinioni eorum et consulendum famae existimavi, maxime ut gloriose viverent et honorem contingerent* "Since I am aware of how very many people go seriously astray in the path of morals, I thought I should come to the aid of their understanding and take their reputations into account, so that they might live with greatest glory and obtain honour". The st. translates the first part of the introductory letter (*Epistula*) preceding the Lat. poem.

Top ^

readings

[1] Heyri: Hlýði 624

>

[2] er: so 624, eð 1199*

>

[2] sið: lið 624

>

[2] lifa: lifi 624

>

[3] gera: geri 624

>

[6] sínum syni: so 624, syni sínum 1199*

>

Top ^

SOURCES

Text is based on reconstruction from the base text and variant apparatus and may contain alternative spellings and other normalisations not visible in the manuscript text. Transcriptions may not have been checked and should not be cited.

Lbs 1199 4°x (1199x) — 72r/3 - 72r/4

(VEP)

Heyri seggir,
þeir eð vilja at sið lifa
ok góð verk gera,
horsklig ráð,
þau er heiðinn maðr
kendi **syni sínum syni sínum**.

Heire Segger þeir ed Vilja ad Sid Lifa og God | verk giöra hoskleg Räd þau er heidinn maður kende Sýne synum. |

o

AM 249 q V fol (249q) — 2v/1 - 2v/2

(TW)

Heyri seggir þeir er vilja sid nema ok goð verk gi | ora · hoslig rad er heidinn maðr kiende sinum syni

o

AM 624 4° (624) — 140/5 - 140/6

(VEP)

Hlýði seggir,
þeir er vilja at **lið lifi**
ok góð verk **geri**,
horsklig ráð,
þau er heiðinn maðr
kendi sínum syni.

Hlydi segger þeir er uilia at lid lifi ok god verk giori · hosk | lig rad þav er heidin maður kendi sinvm synne ·

o

AM 148 8vox (148x) — 69r/2 - 69r/4

(VEP)

Hlijde segger þeir er vilia, ad lid life, og göð verk | giore, hoskleg räd þau, er heidinn maður, kende fordum | syne sijnum.

>

Top ^

editions and texts

Skj: Anonyme digte og vers [XIII], [C. E/5]. *Hugsvinnsmál* 1: **AlI, 167-8, BII, 185, Skald II, 96; Hallgrímur Scheving 1831**, 7, Konráð Gíslason 1860, 549, **Gering 1907**, 1, **Tuvestrand 1977**, 71, **Hermann Pálsson 1985**, 24.

Figure 5.11: Window 5.11: After clicking on a link of a stanza of Window 5.8 (Figure 5.8)

Hugsvinnsmál — Anon *Hsv*^{VII}

← Anonymous Poems

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper 2007, '(Introduction to) Anonymous, *Hugsvinnsmál*' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 358-449.

contents	sources	introduction
mss linked to whole text		
Adv 21 5 2* (21 5 2*)		334v-338v >
Adv 21 5 2* (21 5 2*)		668-676 >
AM 243 f fol (243f)		- >
AM 243 f fol (243f)		3-9 >
AM 249 q V fol (249q)		2v-2v >
AM 624 4° (624)		140-148 >
AM 696 XV 4° (696XV)		1r-1v >
AM 720 a IV 4° (720a IV)		1r-2v >
AM 720 a VIII 4° (720a VIII)		1r-2v >
AM 723 a 4°* (723a*)		39r-42v >
AM 723 a 4°* (723a*)		77-84 >
AM 37 a 8° (37a)		53v-54r >
AM 65 a 8°*		- >
AM 148 8vo* (148*)		244v-245v >

Figure 5.12: Window 5.12: After clicking on the button “Sources” of Window 5.8 (Figure 5.8)

- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.8 with information about the manuscript at hand

The window of Figure 5.13 presents:

- commentary about the work at hand
- references to the bibliography employed

The window of Figure 5.14 presents the following information:

- the content of the stanza with the variant
- the English translation of the stanza
- the English translation of the word
- the lemma
- the morphological analysis
- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.20 which presents a list of citations of references to other witnesses that contain the same variant
- references to the other witnesses where the variant is present: each entry opens the window of Figure 5.7
- notes
- grammar section

The window of Figure 5.15 presents the following information:

- the paleographic transcription
- the thumbnail of the facsimile of the stanza
- a link that opens the facsimile in a new window where the image is bigger and with a good definition. It is possible to enlarge the image with a magnifying glass
- a button to go back to the stanza at hand (go back to the window of Figure 5.11)
- a button to go back to the window of Figure 5.7, the manuscript (of the witness represented by the facsimile)
- the nickname of the editor of the paleographic text
- a link to the editor of the paleographic text that opens the window of Figure 5.21

The window of Figure 5.18 presents:

- the stanza, where the user has the possibility to select a word to know its lemma and other information shown on the window of Figure 5.22
- the stanza in prose shown on the window of Figure 5.23. The window has the same functionality as the window of Figure 5.22 regarding the possibility of selecting a word and see its lemma and other linguistic characterisation

The window of Figure 5.19 presents a text with the stanza and all the information of the tab “Information” of the window of Figure 5.11. It also provides a list with the complete bibliography related to the work at hand.

The window of Figure 5.20 presents the following information:

- the lemma
- a link to an entry in a dictionary (external link)
- a list of mentions of words with the same lemma. Each entry presents:
 - the inflected form
 - the siglum of the manuscript
 - notes
 - a link that opens the window of Figure 5.14, the reading (apparatus) present in the citation at hand

The window of Figure 5.21 presents the following information:

- the name of the editor
- the nickname of the editor
- biography of the editor
- list of the edited items. Each entry presents:
 - a list of allocated stanzas by volume: opens the volume by section, the user can read the contents of each section. The entries that concern the stanzas open the window of Figure 5.11
 - a list of works and stanza groups: each entry has a link that opens the window of Figure 5.8
 - a list of other individual stanzas: each entry has a link that opens the window of Figure 5.9
 - a list of prose works

The window of Figure 5.22 presents the following information:

- the word
- the literal meaning in English
- the lemma
- a link to the entry of the lemma in the dictionary of the Old Norse *skaldic* poetry (the *Lexicon Poeticum*)
- the siglum of the work that presents said word

The window of Figure 5.23 presents the text of the work in prose.

5.1.2 Works

When the user selects an entry of the window of Figure 5.3 the system opens the window of Figure 5.8.

5.1.3 Runic Poetry

When the user clicks on one entry of the default view of the window of Figure 5.4 the systems opens the window of Figure 5.24. This window presents a list of works organised by region.

The window of Figure 5.4 has three more buttons besides the default button:

- region: with the list of runes organised by the region where they are located (opens the window of Figure 5.25)
- siglum: with a list of all the rune editions organised by siglum (opens the window of Figure 5.26)
- place: with a list of all runes organised by the place where they are located (opens the window of Figure 5.27)

The window of Figure 5.24) presents:

- the name of the period
- a button that allows the user to go back to the window of Figure 5.4
- the name of the editor of the works of the period at hand
- each region has the following information:
 - “information about text” that opens Window 5.27 (Figure 5.28) with the collection of works of that region
 - the total number of works of the region
 - a list of the existent works. Each entry has
 - * an ID
 - * the incipit of the critical edition of the text
 - * a link that opens the window of Figure 5.29. This window is similar to the window of Figure 5.8 but there are specificities to the runes that demand another analysis of the same window

Each entry of the window of Figure 5.25 presents the following information:

- name of the region
- name of the period
- total number of runes in that region
- link that opens the window of Figure 5.28

Each entry of the window of Figure 5.26 presents the following information:

- siglum of the rune
- name of the place where the rune is located
- incipit
- link that opens the window of Figure 5.29.

Each entry of the window of Figure 5.27 presents the following information:

- name of the place where the rune is located
- siglum of the rune
- incipit
- link that opens the window of Figure 5.29.

The window of Figure 5.28 presents a list with of the complete set of works of the region at hand. The window presents the following information:

- name of the region
- a button with the name of the period at hand that allows the user to go back to the window of Figure 5.24
- information about the edition of the collection of the works
- each entry has:
 - the ID of the work and a link that opens the window of Figure 5.29
 - the critical edition of the text
 - the translation of the critical edition
 - a button “sources” that opens the window of Figure 5.30 with a list of the runes

The window of Figure 5.29 presents the information about the critical edition of a text. The information this window provides is:

- the name of the region
- the ID of the work
- information about the critical edition
- button to go back to the period (name of the period) – Window of Figure 5.24
- button to go back to the region (name of the region) – Window of Figure 5.28
- the critical edition
- a link to go to the next work in the collection
- a link to go to the previous work in the collection
- the sources of the critical edition. Each entry of the sources section has:
 - the ID of the rune
 - a sequential number that identifies the specific source in the set of sources
 - a link that opens a thumbnail of the facsimile of the rune at hand
 - a link that opens the window of Figure 5.31
- editions or texts of the same work

Window 5.29 (Figure 5.30) presents a collection of runes on a certain region. The listing provides the following information:

- the name of the region
- the nickname of the region
- the period name (with a link that returns to Window 5.23)
- information about editions of the collection
- each entry of the listing has the following information:
 - the ID of the rune
 - a link that opens the window of Figure 5.32
- a button “sources” that opens the window of Figure 5.30

The window of Figure 5.31 presents the miniatures of the facsimiles of a specific rune. This window provides:

- the ID of the critical edition of the rune (with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.29)
- a link to the page with information about the source (opens the window of Figure 5.32)
- thumbnails of the facsimiles of the rune (each thumbnail provides a link that opens the window of Figure 5.33)

The window of Figure 5.32 presents the paleographic edition/transcription of a specific rune and its location in a map. The information that this window provides is:

- ID of the rune
- technique on the support (e.g. inscription)
- date of the rune
- country and region of the location
- the name of the local where the rune is located (e.g. path)
- paleographic edition or transcription of the text
- English translation of the paleographic edition (or translation)
- a map with the location of the rune
- the ID of the critical edition of the text with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.29

The window of Figure 5.33) presents the facsimiles of a specific rune. This window provides:

- the facsimile of the rune
- alternative facsimile: miniatures of other facsimiles of the same rune. If the user clicks on the miniature the page loads the new facsimile of the image selected and updates the miniatures
- information about the critical edition of the rune (link that opens the window of Figure 5.29)
- the ID of the source (rune) with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.32

5.1.4 *Skalds* (authors)

The Window of Figure 5.34 opens when the user selects a *skald* from the window of Figure 5.5.

This window presents information concerning one author (*skald*):

- the complete name of the author
- the nickname
- the name of the editor with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.21
- a biography of the author
- bibliography about the author (both external and internal references)
- a list of all works in the database by this author. This list contains (see Figure 5.35):
 - name of the work
 - total number of stanzas of the work
 - introduction and information about the work with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.7
 - name of the stanza with a link that opens the window of Figure 5.8

5.1.5 *Kennings*

On its “default view” the window of Figure 6 presents a list of all *kennings* classified according to Meissner’s categories. Each entry of the list has the following information:

- the classification name
- the number of *kennings* under the classification
- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.36

The window of Figure 5.6 also presents other buttons:

- unclassified
- ungrouped
- named referents
- big *kennings*

All these buttons open the window of Figure 5.36.

The window of Figure 35) presents the following information:

- the classification in which all the *kennings* are grouped
- a button that returns back to the window of Figure 5.6
- the paleographic edition of the *kenning*
- the translation of the *kenning*
- the meaning of the *kenning*
- the ID of the work where the specific *kenning* is used
- a link that opens the window of Figure 5.37 (which is the same as the window of Figure 5.18 but here the explanation of the *kenning* is done in the translation)

The *kenning* is divided as many times as needed to explain its final meaning. It is possible to have *kennings* inside *kennings* so the information “translation” and “meaning” may appear multiple times.

The window of Figure 36 presents the same information as the window of Figure 5.18. This window presents clearly the explanation of the *kennings* inside the translation of the critical edition.

Figure 5.14: Window 5.14: After clicking on a entry of a “reading” of Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11)

Figure 5.15: Window 5.15: After clicking on a source entry of Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11)

Figure 5.16: Window 5.16: A thumbnail of the facsimile of a source on Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11)

Figure 5.17: A detail on a menu of Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11). Functionality that allows the user to browse works of the same collection

Anon *Hsv* 1^{VII}

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper (eds) 2007, 'Anonymous Poems, *Hugsvinnsmál* 1' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*: Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 361-2.

Anonymous Poems | Hugsvinnsmál

1 | 2

information | **interactive** | full text

Interactive view: tap on words in the text for notes and glosses

verse | prose

Heyri seggir,
þeir er vilja at sið lifa
ok góð verk gera,
horsklig ráð,
þau er heiðinn maðr
kendi sínum syni.

Men who want to live with good conduct and do good works should listen to the wise advice that a heathen man taught his son.

Lat. parallel: (*Epistula*) *Cum animadverterem quam plurimos graviter in via morum errare, succurrendum opinioni eorum et consulendum famae existimavi, maxime ut gloriose viverent et honorem contingerent*: 'Since I am aware of how very many people go seriously astray in the path of morals, I thought I should come to the aid of their understanding and take their reputations into account, so that they might live with greatest glory and obtain honour'. The st. translates the first part of the introductory letter (*Epistula*) preceding the Lat. poem.

Figure 5.18: Window 5.17: The “interactive” tab of Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11)

Anon *Hsv* 1^{VII}

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper (eds) 2007, 'Anonymous Poems, *Hugsvinnsmál* 1' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*: Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 361-2.

Anonymous Poems | Hugsvinnsmál

1 | 2

information | interactive | **full text**

Heyri seggir, þeir er vilja at sið lifa
ok góð verk gera,
horsklig ráð, þau er heiðinn maðr
kendi sínum syni.

Seggir, þeir er vilja lifa at sið ok gera góð verk, heyri horsklig ráð, þau er heiðinn maðr kendi sínum synum.

Men who want to live with good conduct and do good works should listen to the wise advice that a heathen man taught his son.

Mss: 1199*(72r), 624(140)

Readings: [1] Heyri: Hljóði 624 [2] er: so 624, eð 1199*, sið. líð 624; lifa: lífi 624 [3] gera: geri 624 [6] sínum syni: so 624, syni sínum 1199*

Editions: *Skj* All, 167-8, *Skj* Bll, 185, *Skald II*, 96, *Hallgrímur Scheving 1831*, 7, *Konráð Gíslason 1860*, 549, *Gering 1907*, 1, *Tuvestrand 1977*, 71, *Hermann Pálsson 1985*, 24.

Notes: [All]. Lat. parallel: (*Epistula*) *Cum animadverterem quam plurimos graviter in via morum errare, succurrendum opinioni eorum et consulendum famae existimavi, maxime ut gloriose viverent et honorem contingerent*: 'Since I am aware of how very many people go seriously astray in the path of morals, I thought I should come to the aid of their understanding and take their reputations into account, so that they might live with greatest glory and obtain honour'. The st. translates the first part of the introductory letter (*Epistula*) preceding the Lat. poem. — [4] *ráð* 'advice'. Lit. pl.: 'pieces of advice'. *Ráð* is usually used in the pl. but translated here and elsewhere in the sg. — [6] *syni sínum* 'his son': The 624 reading of l. 6 is more correct in *ljóðahátt*, since long-stemmed disyllabic words are generally avoided in the final two positions.

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5. Hallgrímur Scheving, ed. 1831. *Hugsvinnsmál, ásamt þeirra látinska frumriti*. Skóla hátíð. Viðeyrar Klaustr: prentuð af Helga Helgasyni, á kostnað Bessastaða Skóla.

Figure 5.19: Window 5.18: The “Full text” tab of Window 5.11 (Figure 5.11)

Search headwords...

2^heyra (verb) 'hear'

Words: h

Please note that the lexical concordance has not been reviewed and should not be referenced. Dates in particular may be taken from earlier editions and should be checked.

ONP article

Page structure <

citations (undefined)

Filter items...

Vilð, Hrafnketill, heyra, — Bragi Rdr 1¹⁰1	825
Vilð, Hrafnketill, <i>heyra</i> , hvé skalik ... 'Do you wish, Hrafnketill, <u>to hear</u> how I shall ...'	
Heyrðak svá, þat síðan — Þjóð Haustí 12¹⁰1	850
Heyrðak svá, þat ... 'I <u>have heard</u> thus, that ...'	
þeim es ek mey heyra — Þhom Harkv 1¹⁶6	900
...es ek <i>heyra</i> hvíta, haddbjarta ... '...I <u>heard</u> a white, bright-haired ...'	
Heyrði [var.] 'Heyrðir þú, í Hafsríði — Þhom Harkv 7¹1	900
[1] Heyrðir þú: Heyrði Flat Flat Heyrde hafri lírde hve hr austliga bardizst konungr hinn kynstora víð kiotua hinn audlagða knerrir kuomu austan kaps vm lystir með ginandum hoðum ok grofanum tinglum	
Heyrðu [var.] 'Heyrðir þú, í Hafsríði — Þhom Harkv 7¹1	900
[1] Heyrðir þú: Heyrðu 51 ^x , FskB ^x , 302 ^x , FskA ^x , 52 ^x , 301 ^x FskA Hoyr þu í Hafsríðe hve hizi barðez konongrenn kynstora við kiotvan auðlagða knerrir komo austan kaps vm lystir með ginandum hoðum oc grofnom tinglum 51 Hóyrðu í hafis ríði hve hizug barðez konungr konungr kynstor við kiotvan auðlagða knerrir komo austan kaps vm lystir með ginandum hoðum oc grofnum tinglum FskB Hóyrðu hafis ríði hve hizug barðez konungr konungr kynstor við kiotvan auðlagða knerrir komo austan kaps vm lystir með ginandum hoðum oc grofnum tinglum	

Figure 5.20: Window 5.19: An entry of the dictionary of the Old Norse *skaldic* poetry (the *Lexicon Poeticum*) after clicking in the lemma of Window 5.14 (Figure 5.14)

Valgerður Erna Þorvaldsdóttir (VEP)

all editors

Valgerður Erna Þorvaldsdóttir was a Research Associate (from June 2002 to April 2008) to the project *Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages*. Her main area of interest within Old Norse-Icelandic Studies is skaldic poetry, especially that of the thirteenth century.

allocated stanzas by volume	
Vol. II	21
Vol. III	1
Vol. IV	23
Vol. VII	33
poems and stanza groups	
Anonymous Poems, <i>Brúðkaupsvisur</i>	33
Eilífr Snorrason, <i>Lausavísur</i>	3
Guðbrandr í Svþlum, <i>Fragment</i>	1
Guðmundr Svertingsson, <i>Hrafnadrápa</i>	11
Magnús Þórðarson, <i>Lausavísur</i>	2
Sturla Þórðarson, <i>Lausavísur</i>	3
Sturla Þórðarson, <i>Fragments</i>	2
Sturla Þórðarson, <i>Hrynhenda</i>	21
other individual stanzas	
prose works	
<i>Hrafn saga Sveinbjarnarsonar in sérstaka</i>	

Figure 5.21: Window 5.20: The editions of a specific *Skaldic* editor – (after clicking in his/her nickname on Window 5.15 (Figure 5.15))

— Heyri 'should listen'

2. heyra (verb): hear

[1] Heyri: Hlýði 624

Figure 5.22: Window 5.21: The lemma of the word selected in Window 5.17 (Figure 5.18)

Anon *Hsv* 1^{VII}

Tarrin Wills and Stefanie Gropper (eds) 2007, 'Anonymous Poems, *Hugsvinnsmál* 1' in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*: Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 361-2.

Anonymous Poems | Hugsvinnsmál

1 | 2

information | **interactive** | full text

Interactive view: tap on words in the text for notes and glosses

verse | **prose**

Seggir, þeir er vilja
lifa at sið ok gera
góð verk, heyr!
horsklig ráð, þau er
heiðinn maðr kendi
syni sínum.

Men who want to live with good conduct and do good works should listen to the wise advice that a heathen man taught his son.

Lat. parallel: (*Epistula*) *Cum animadverterem quam plurimos graviter in via morum errare, succurrendum opinioni eorum et consulendum famae existimavi, maxime ut gloriose viverent et honorem contingerent* 'Since I am aware of how very many people go seriously astray in the path of morals, I thought I should come to the aid of their understanding and take their reputations into account, so that they might live with greatest glory and obtain honour'. The st. translates the first part of the introductory letter (*Epistula*) preceding the Lat. poem.

Figure 5.23: Window 5.22: The stanza in prose of Window 5.17 (Figure 5.18)

Viking Age

+ skalds

— ed Edith Marold

Page structure <

Poetry

+ Bornholm	3
+ Jylland (Jutland)	6
+ Lolland	1
+ Sjælland (Zealand)	1
+ Schleswig-Holstein	1
+ Troms fylke	1
+ Gotland	5
+ Närke	1
+ Skåne (Scania)	5
+ Småland	10
— Södermanland	41
information about text	>
Sö 9. 'hann ændaðis með Ingvari ...'	>
Sö 14. 'Vet iak þæt var Sven ...'	>
Sö 33. 'Hann ændaðis austr at þingum. ...'	>
Sö 34-5. 'Styrlegr ok Holmbr ...'	>
Sö 41. 'mærkit mikla ...'	>
Sö 47. 'Hann er grafinn a Gotlandi ...'	>
Sö 54. 'Váru allir ...'	>

Figure 5.24: Window 5.23: List of works of a certain period (after selecting a period on Window 5.4) (Figure 5.4)

Runic Poetry			
period	region	siglum	place
Q filter items...			
Blekinge (Older Futhark)			2 >
Bornholm (Viking Age)			3 >
Buskerud (Older Futhark)			1 >
Buskerud (Middle Ages)			1 >
Fyn (Older Futhark)			1 >
Fyn (Funen) (Middle Ages)			1 >
Gotland (Viking Age)			5 >
Hordaland (Older Futhark)			1 >
Hordaland (Middle Ages)			28 >
Jylland (Older Futhark)			1 >
Jylland (Jutland) (Viking Age)			6 >
Jylland (Jutland) (Middle Ages)			2 >
Lolland (Viking Age)			1 >
Närke (Viking Age)			1 >
Orkney (Middle Ages)			1 >
Rogaland (Older Futhark)			1 >
Schleswig-Holstein (Older Futhark)			1 >

Figure 5.25: Window 5.24: List of works of a certain region (after selecting a region on Window 5.4) (Figure 5.4)

Runic Poetry			
period	region	siglum	place
Q filter items...			
Br Barnes20 (Maeshowe 20)		Pessar rúnar reist sá maör	>
Colton Caligula A XV 4 ^o		Far þu nu fundin æstu. þur uigi þik, (þ)orsa trutin.	>
DR 7 (KJ20 Torsbjerg-dúpsko)		WulþuþewaR ni wajemariR	>
DR 12 (Gallehus horn 2)		Ek HlewagastiR HoltijaR horna tawido	>
DR 37 (Egtved)		rest [runaR], broþiR æft broþur, sten sasi ?skarni	>
DR 40 (Randbøl)		Þer stafar munu Þorgunni, miok længi lifa.	>
DR 68 (Árhus 6)		SaR do manna mæst unipingR	>
DR 94 (Álum 1)		þau munu minni mærkt æ of birta	>
DR 131 (Árs)		sten kwæzk hersi standa længi saR Waltoka warþa næfni.	>
DR 149 (Tjydbý)			>
DR 163 (Ø. Brønderslev)		Kirkja er Kristi kend mönnum til miskundar.	>
DR 186 (Svendborg knife)		Karl ærke skar á hæftæ Aræ læmæþe skæftæ.	>
DR 208 (KJ24 - Vimose buckle)		A Andag Ansula ansau wija	>
DR 212 (Tillitse)		E mun standa mæþ sten lifiR witrind su æR wan Æskil.	>
DR 222 (Allerslev 1)		Iordan risti runur, raþi þæn ær kan.	>
DR 229 (Sandby 3)		E mun sannas lif-witring susi æR wan Solfæ!	>
DR 263 (Skabersjö)		Raþi tók fauka féar sins,	>
DR 279 (Sjörup stone)		saR flo egi at Upsalum æn wa, mæþ (h)an wapn (h)afþi.	>

Figure 5.26: Window 5.25: List of works of a certain siglum (after selecting a siglum on Window 5.4) (Figure 5.4)

period	region	siglum	place
Q filter items...			
Ydby (DR 149)			
Allerslev 1 (DR 222)			
Ardre kyrka 3 (G 113)			
Arlanda (U Fv1992:157)			
Aspa (Sö 136)			
Aspa (Sö 137)			
Aspa (Sö Fv1948:289)			
Aspö (Sö 174)			
Berga (Vs 19)			
Bjudby I (Sö 54)			
Bjudby II (Sö 55)			
Björke (Sö 41)			
Björketorp stone (DR 360)			
Broby (U 136)			
Broby (U 437)			
Bryggen, Bergen (N B11)			

Figure 5.27: Window 5.26: List of works of a certain place (after selecting a place on Window 5.4) (Figure 5.4)

Södermanland — Run Sö ^{VI}		
contents	sources	
Sö 9	hann ændaðis með Ingvari	<i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>
Sö 14	Vet iak þæt var Sven væstr með gati	<i>This text is from an old edition.</i> <i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>
Sö 33	Hann ændaðis austr at þingum.	<i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>
Sö 34-5	Styrlagr ok Holmbr steina réstu at bræðr sína brættu næsta þær ændaðrus í Östrvæghl þorkæl ok Styrbærn þiæghnar göðr. Let IngæiRR annan ræisa stæin at syni sína syna gærði	<i>This text is from an old edition.</i> <i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>
Sö 41	mærkit mikla man é á (h)æRn	<i>The new edition is unavailable.</i> <i>This text is from an old edition.</i>
Sö 47	Hann er grafinn a Gotlandi	<i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>
Sö 54	Váru allir Vikings syniR lændborniR mæn, lætu rættu stein.	<i>The new edition is unavailable.</i> <i>The new edition is unavailable.</i>

Figure 5.28: Window 5.27: Collection of runes of a region

Run Sö 34-5^{VI}

Södermanland 4 — ed. Jana Krüger

Not published: do not cite (Run Sö 34-5^{VI})

Viking Age Södermanland

3 Sö 34-5 5

Page structure

text and translation

The new edition is either unpublished or unavailable. The following is taken from an old edition (Skj where relevant):

Styrlæg ok HolmBR
 steina réstu
 at bræðr sína
 brættu næsta
 þÉR ændaðhus
 í Østrvæghi
 Þorkæl ok Styrbiærn
 ÞlægnaR góðIR.
 Let InigæIRR
 annan ræisa stæin
 at syni sína
 syna gærði

Top

SOURCES

Text is based on reconstruction from the base text and variant apparatus and may contain alternative spellings and other normalisations not visible in the manuscript text. Transcriptions may not have been checked and should not be cited.

Sö 34 (Sö34) — 1 - 2	↻
Sö 35 (Sö35) — 1 - 1	↻

Top

editions and texts

Runverser, 155; SRI III, 26-8, 368-9, Pl. 10: B. 780, 24. — Rask 1990, 53-8;1995, 30-5; Larsson 2002, 56-7; Jesch 2011, 41-4.

Figure 5.29: Window 5.28: The information about the edition of a text on a specific rune

Södermanland — Run Sö^{VI}

Viking Age

Södermanland —

Not published: do not cite (Run Sö^{VI})

contents sources

mss linked to stanzas/sections

Sö 9 (Sö9)	➤
Sö 14 (Sö14)	➤
Sö 33 (Sö33)	➤
Sö 34 (Sö34)	➤
Sö 35 (Sö35)	➤
Sö 41 (Sö41)	➤
Sö 47 (Sö47)	➤
Sö 54 (Sö54)	➤
Sö 55 (Sö55)	➤
Sö 56 (Sö56)	➤
Sö 61 (Sö61)	➤
Sö 65 (Sö65)	➤
Sö 85 (Sö85)	➤

Figure 5.30: Window 5.29: Collection of runes in a region

Stanza/text on inscription

Run Sö 34-5^{VI} in: Sö 34 1 - 2

Figure 5.31: Window 5.30: Thumbnails of the facsimiles of a rune

Sö 34 (Sö34) - Tjuvstigen I

inscription; date not specified; Sweden: Sodermanland

stýrilaugr * auk * hulmbr * staina * raistu * at * brypr * sina * braut(tu * nesta * þair * entaþus * i * austruiki * þurkil * auk sturbiarn þiaknar * kupir

Stýrilaugr and Holmr raised the stones next to the path in memory of their brothers. They met their end on the eastern route, Þorkell and Styrþjörn, good Thegns.

map

Edited as Run Sö 34-5^{VI}

Figure 5.32: Window 5.31: Paleographic edition/transcription and the location of a rune

Sö 34 (Sö34) - 1

On this page...

Run Sö 34-5^{VI} 'Stýrilaugr ok Holmbr ...'

Alternative images

Figure 5.33: Window 5.32: Facsimile of a rune

Bjarni byskup Kolbeinsson — Bjbp¹

skalds

Vol. 1, 953 — — ed. Jonna Louis-Jensen

Poetry

Jómsvíkingadrápa 45

Biography

Jonna Louis-Jensen 2012. '(Biography of) Bjarni byskup Kolbeinsson' in Diana Whaley (ed.), *Poetry from the Kings' Sagas 1: From Mythical Times to c. 1035*. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 1. Brepols, Turnhout, p. 953.

Bjarni Kolbeinsson (Bjbp) was born into a powerful family in the Orkney Islands, possibly c. 1150-60 (af Petersens, *Jvs 1879*, 122). His father was the Norwegian-Orkadian chieftain Kolbeinn hrúga 'Heap' and his mother was Herborg, a great-granddaughter of Páll jarl Þorfinnsson on the maternal side (see *Ættaskrár* [Genealogies] II in *ÍF 35*). Bjarni was also very well connected: he was a close friend of Haraldr jarl Maddaðarson (*ÍF 35*, 289), sent precious gifts to Hrafn Sveinbjarnarson in Iceland on three occasions (*Guðrún P. Helgadóttir 1987*, 2-3), and had connections with the Oddaverjar (see further *Einar Ól. Sveinsson 1937*, 17-18, 34-9).

Bjarni was Bishop of Orkney from 1188 (*ÍF 35*, 289) until his death on 15 September 1223. Among his achievements as bishop were the exhumation and canonisation of *Rognvaldr jarl Kali Kolsson* (*ÍF 35*, 282, *SKP II*, 575) and the extension of St Magnús's Cathedral in Kirkwall. Bjarni was also a diplomat and is known to have travelled to Norway for political reasons in 1194-5, 1208-9, 1210, 1218 and 1223 (see *Bugge 1875*, 244, *Holtmark 1937a*, 2-3); he probably died in Norway (*Jón Stefánsson 1907-8*, 46).

Bjarni is introduced as *Bjarni skáld* 'Poet' in *Orkn* (*ÍF 35*, 193), but *Jómsvíkingadrápa* (*Jóms*) is the only literary work attributed to him in medieval sources. Suggestions that he compiled *Orkn* (*Jón Stefánsson 1907-8*) and the *pulur* in *SnE* (*Bugge 1875*) have not been generally accepted; see Introduction to *Jóms* below on the attribution of *Anon Mhkv* to Bjarni.

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4. *SKP II = Poetry from the Kings' Sagas 2: From c. 1035 to c. 1300*. Ed. Kari Ellen Gade. 2009.
5. *Jvs 1879 = Petersens, Carl af, ed. 1879. Jómsvíkinga saga (efter Cod. AM. 510, 4:to) samt Jómsvíkinga drápa*. Lund: Gleerup.
6. Einar Ólafur Sveinsson. 1937. *Sagnaritun Oddaverja: Nokkrar athuganir*. Studia Islandica 1. Reykjavík: Ísafold.
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8. Jón Stefánsson. 1907-8. 'Bjarme Kolbeinsson, the Skald, Bishop of Orkney, 1188-1223'. *Orkney and Shetland Miscellany* 1, 43-7.

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2. Kari Ellen Gade 2009. 'Orkneyinga saga (Orkn)' in Kari Ellen Gade (ed.), *Poetry from the Kings' Sagas 2: From c. 1035 to c. 1300. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 2. Brep...*
3. Judith Jesch 2017. '(Biography of) Rognvaldr jarl Kali Kolsson' in Kari Ellen Gade and Edith Marold (eds), *Poetry from Treatises on Poetics. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 3. Brep...*
4. Roberta Frank 2017. '(Introduction to) Anonymous, Málisháttakvæði' in Kari Ellen Gade and Edith Marold (eds), *Poetry from Treatises on Poetics. Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 3...*
5. Emily Lethbridge 2012. '(Introduction to) Bjarni byskup Kolbeinsson. Jómsvíkingadrápa' in Diana Whaley (ed.), *Poetry from the Kings' Sagas 1: From Mythical Times to c. 1035. Skaldic Poetry of ...*

other information

Bjarni byskup Kolbeinsson (Bjbp)

13th century

Skj All, 1-10; BII, 1-10

volume 1

main editor: Jonna Louis-Jensen

Figure 5.34: Window 5.33: works of a specific *skald* selected on Window 5.5 (Figure 5.5)

Poetry

Jómsvíkingadrápa 45

Introduction and information about text

1. 'Engan kveðk at óði ...'
2. 'Hendir enn sem aðra ...'
3. 'Dreng var dátt of svarra ...'
4. 'Varkak fróðr und forsum ...'
5. '-----'
6. 'Suðr frógum vér sitja ...'
7. 'Hvervetna frá heryja ...'
8. 'Geta skal hins hverr hvatra ...'
9. 'Sigvaldi hét seggja ...'
10. 'Heldu dreyrgra darra ...'
11. 'Enn vildu þá (einkum) ...'
12. 'Heitstrenging frá heryja ...'
13. 'Búi lézk barr at fylgja ...'
14. 'Vagn kvað hitt enn hrausti, ...'
15. 'Ein drepr fyr mér allri, ...'

Figure 5.35: Window 5.34: The list of works of a *skald* (author), a detail of Window 5.33 (Figure 5.34)

Kennings for battle

← kennings (classified)

<p>Anon Gyð 3^{VII} þeim brynflagð^a þing 'for those of the assembly of the trolls of the mailcoat' = BATTLE for those of the trolls of the mailcoat → AXES of AXES of the assembly → BATTLE</p>	▶
<p>Anon Gyð 5^{VII} fetilþielar iel 'of the storm of the strap-file' = BATTLE the strap-file → SWORD the storm of the SWORD → BATTLE</p>	▶
<p>Anon Gyð 5^{VII} óðs regns odda 'of the furious rain of sword-points' = BATTLE the furious rain of sword-points → BATTLE</p>	▶
<p>Anon Gyð 6^{VII} Ullar iel 'of the storm of Ullr' = BATTLE the storm of Ullr → BATTLE</p>	▶
<p>Anon Gyð 7^{VII} blára odda brak- 'of the crash of dark spear-points' = BATTLE the crash of dark spear-points → BATTLE</p>	▶

Figure 5.36: Window 5.35: The list of classification of the *kennings*

Anon Gyð 3^{VII}

Katríná Attwood (ed.) 2007, Anonymous Poems, *Gyðingsvísur* 3^r in Margaret Clunies Ross (ed.), *Poetry on Christian Subjects*: Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages 7. Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 519-20.

Anonymous Poems ▶ Gyðingsvísur ▶

◀ 2 3 ▼ 4 ▶

information	interactive	full text
-------------	-------------	-----------

Interactive view: tap on words in the text for notes and glosses

verse	prose
-------	-------

**Hvarf er þeim, er þurfa,
þingnárungum, váru,
branda rjóðr i bráðar
brynflagð^a nauðsynjar.
Fekkk strandlöga stökkvir
stígerjanda hverjum
fráns af fjárlut sínum
fullar hendr, meðan endiz.**

The reddener of swords [WARRIOR] is a support for those beings of the assembly of the trolls of the mailcoat [(lit. 'assembly-beings of the mailcoat-trolls')] AXES > BATTLE > WARRIORS] who were poor, in cases of sudden need. The flinger of shore-flame [GOLD > GENEROUS MAN] gave every defender of the path of the snake [(lit. 'snake's path-defender')] GOLD > MAN] hands full of his wealth, while it lasted.

[1-4] In l. 1 the second word is difficult to read in B, but Finnur Jónsson's 'er' (SKJ A) is almost certainly right; he noted there that 399a-b's suggested *firi* must be incorrect, and similarly Rydberg's *við*. Attwood 1996a: 116 has *öf*. Rydberg (1907: 59) reads the word as *vöð* and takes *hvarf* to be 3rd pers. sg. pret. of *hverfa* 'to turn'. He arranges: *rjóðr branda hvarf við þeim þingnárungum brynflagðara i bráðar nauðsynjar* 'the reddener of swords turned to the assembly-beings of mailcoat-trolls in cases of sudden need'. Although this interpretation is grammatically possible, it is rather unlikely in context. Assuming the *rjóðr branda* of l. 3 to be identified with *sá er kunnir veita firum unneyg* in 2/1-2 and with the person whose generosity is eulogised in 3/5-8 and st. 4, it is difficult to understand why he should approach other men for financial help in 3/1-4. This edn follows SKJ B in taking *hvarf* as the nom. sg. of n. *hvarf* 'shelter, refuge, support, help' (cf. Fritzer: *hvarf* 2), which fits rather better with the second *helmingr* and with the situation of other people's dependency on the rich man established in st. 2 and confirmed in st. 4. There appear to be two possible interpretations of the remaining phrase *er váru þurfa* (ll. 1-2). This edn follows Finnur Jónsson in taking *váru* as 3rd pers. pl. pret. of *vera* 'to be', construed with *brynflagða þingnárungar* (see Note below). *Þurfa* (l. 1) is taken to be the corresponding form of the adj. *þurfi* meaning 'needy'. This interpretation is corroborated by a parallel use of the adj. in the ONorw. *Bjarkö-ret. Fylkisprestur eðr annarr i stað hans skal heima vera ok gera mönnum reidub er þurfa eru* 'The district priest or another in his stead must remain at home and provide assistance for people if they are needy' (NGL I, 315; CVC; Fritzer: *þurfi*).

Figure 5.37: Window 5.36: The explanation of a *kenning* in the context

5.2 Data needs analysis

Table 5.1 presents the data needs of Window 5.2 (Figure 5.2). This window presents a list that “contains manuscripts relevant to the *skaldic* database, plus some printed works and other objects that have independent textual evidence for the corpus.”

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.1 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource

Table 5.1: Data elements of Window 5.2

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
siglum	1	1	Opens Window 5.7	siglum.PrimarySource
total number of works in the manuscript	1	1	Opens Window 5.7	numberOfWorks.PrimarySource

Table 5.2 presents the data needs of Window 5.3 (Figure 5.3). This window presents a list of all works in the corpus.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.2 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 5.2: Data elements of Window 5.3

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title of work	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	title.Redaction
Name of author	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	Redaction-hasCreatorPerson-Person + name.Person
Total number of stanzas in the work	1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern

Table 5.3 presents the data needs of Window 5.4 (Figure 5.4). This window presents the periods of all runes in the corpus.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.3 is related to the entity “Opus” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model.

Table 5.3: Data elements of Window 5.4

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Period	1	1	Opens Window 5.23	literaryPeriod.Opus
Total number of runes in the period	1			<i>Redundant</i>
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.24	Opus-comesFrom-Place

Table 5.4 presents the data needs of Window 5.5 (Figure 5.5). This window presents a list with the authors represented in the database.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.4 is related to the entity “Person” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 5.5 presents the data needs of Window 5.6 (Figure 5.6). This window presents a list of categories of *kennings*, alphabetically order.

Table 5.4: Data elements of Window 5.5

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of author	1	1	Opens Window 5.33	name.Person
Short name of author	1			altName.Person
Total number of works of the author	1			<i>Redundant</i>

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.5 is related to the entity “FigureOfSpeech” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–hasCreator–Redaction–presents–FigureOfSpeech (device.FigureOfSpeech = kenning)

Table 5.5: Data elements of Window 5.6

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Category name	1	1	Opens Window 5.35	category.FigureOfSpeech
Total number of <i>kennings</i> of that classification	1			<i>Redundant</i>

5.2.1 Manuscripts

Table 5.6 presents the data needs of Window 5.7 (Figure 5.7). This window presents information about the contents of one specific manuscript.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.6 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 5.6: Data elements of Window 5.7

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1			siglum.PrimarySource
Material	1			support.PrimarySource
Date from	1			from.PrimarySource
Date to	1			to.PrimarySource
Library name	1		Where the manuscript is kept	PrimarySource–belongsTo–Repository + name.Repository
TABLE OF CONTENTS	M			PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness
Name of work	1	1	Opens Window 5.8 or Window 5.9	title.Witness
Folios	1		Location of the work in the manuscript	location.Witness
TEXT and IMAGES	M			PrimarySource–isReproducedIn–Facsimile
Folio number	1		Location of the work in the manuscript	location.Facsimile
Facsimile image definition	1	1	Opens Window 5.10	<i>Not relevant</i>

Continued on next page

Table 5.6 – continued from previous page

Label		Card.	Link	Comments	DM
	STANZA	M			Facsimile-reproduces-Witness-isConsideredBy-Stanza
	Line numbers of the witness	1			location.Witness
	Short name of the author of the stanza	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-Stanza-hasCreator-Person + name.Person
	Short name of the work	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-Stanza-previousStanza-Stanza-isFirstStanzaOf-Redaction + altTitle.Redaction
	Number of stanza in the work	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-stanzaNumber.Stanza
	Short Title of the Edition of the stanza	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-Stanza-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + altTitle.BibliographicSource
	Number of the stanza in the Edition	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-Stanza-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + workNumber.Location

Table 5.7 presents the data needs of Window 5.8 (Figure 5.8). This Window presents details about a work.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.7 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 5.7: Data elements of Window 5.8

Label		Card.	Link	Comments	DM
	Work title	1			title.Redaction
	Short name of author	1			Redaction-hasCreator-Person+ altName.Person
	CRITICAL EDITION	1			Redaction-retrievesText-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource
	Editor Name	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person+ name.Person
	Year of Edition	1			date.BibliographicSource
	Edition Name (Title)	1			title.BibliographicSource
	Chapter Name	1			BibliographicSource-hasPart-BibliographicSource + typeOfBibliographicItem. BibliographicSource (=chapter)
	Author Name	M			BibliographicSource-hasCreator-Person+ name.Person
	Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
	Place of Publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
	Pages of chapter	1			scope.BibliographicSource
	CONTENTS	1			Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)
	Stanza number	1	1	Opens window 5.11	Win-stanzaNumber.Stanza
	Critical edition	1			Stanza-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)+ content.Line

Continued on next page

Table 5.7 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
English translation of the critical edition	1			Stanza-isTranslated-Stanza- hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)+content.Line
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.12	Win-Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.13	Win-Redaction-isReferencedIn-BibliographicSource

Table 5.8 presents the data needs of Window 5.9 (Figure 5.9). This Window presents details about a collection of works.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.8 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 5.8: Data elements of Window 5.9

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Work title	1			title.Redaction
Short name of author	1			Redaction-hasCreator-Person+altName.Person
STANZA	M			Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)
Short name of the work	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	Win-Stanza-previousStanza-Stanza-isFirstStanzaOf-Redaction + altTitle.Redaction
Number of stanza in the work	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	Win-stanzaNumber.Stanza
Short Title of the Edition of the stanza	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	Win-Stanza-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource+altTitle.BibliographicSource
Number of the stanza in the Edition	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	Win-Stanza-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource+workNumber.Location

Table 5.9 presents the data needs of Window 5.10 (Figure 10). This Window presents a Facsimile.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.9 is related to the entity “Facsimile” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness-isReproducedIn-Facsimile

Table 5.9: Data elements of Window 5.10

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Image file	1			url.Facsimile
Folio	1			location.Facsimile
Siglum	1		This information is not clearly stated, it is present by the button that returns to the manuscript at hand	siglum.Facsimile

Continued on next page

Table 5.9 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Next Page	1	1	Opens Window 5.10	Facsimile–nextPage–Facsimile
Previous Page	1	1	Opens Window 5.10	Facsimile–previousPage–Facsimile
WORK	M			Facsimile–reproduces–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Incipit	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	incipit.Witness
Folios	1			location.Witness

Table 5.10 presents the data needs of Window 5.11 (Figure 11). This Window presents information about a specific stanza on a work.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.10 is related to the entity “Stanza” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction—hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)

Table 5.10: Data elements of Window 5.11

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Author name	1	1	Opens Window 5.33	Stanza–hasCreator–Person+ name.Person
Author nickname	1			Stanza–hasCreator–Person+ altName.Person
Work title	1	1	Opens Window 5.7	title.Stanza
Work short title	1			altTitle.Stanza
Next stanza	1	1	Opens Window 5.12	Stanza–nextStanza–Stanza
Previous stanza	1	1	Opens Window 5.12	Stanza–previousStanza–Stanza
CRITICAL EDITION	1			Redaction–retrievesText–Location– refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
Editor name	M			BibliographicSource–hasEditor– Person+ name.Person
Year of edition	1			date.BibliographicSource
Edition name (title)	1			title.BibliographicSource
Chapter name	1			BibliographicSource–hasPart– BibliographicSource + typeOfBib- liographicItem. BibliographicSource (=chapter)
Author name	M			BibliographicSource–hasCreator– Person+ name.Person
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Pages of chapter	1			scope.BibliographicSource
CONTENT AND CONTEXT	1			Stanza–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine– Line)
Critical edition	1			content.Line
Translation	1			Stanza–isTranslated–Stanza+ content.Line
Notes	1			editionsNotes.Stanza
APPARATUS	M			Stanza–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine– Line)–isAnalysedThrough–Apparatus

Continued on next page

Table 5.10 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Location	1	1	Line and Word. Opens Window 5.14	location.Apparatus
Variant	1	1	Opens Window 5.14	Apparatus-hasReading-Reading + variant.Reading
Localisation of variant in Witness	1	1	Opens Window 5.14	Reading-isReadingOf-Witness + siglum.Witness
SOURCE	M			Stanza-considers-Witness
Siglum	1	1	Opens Window 5.15	siglum.Witness
Folios	1	1	Opens Window 5.15	location.Witness
Paleographic edition	1	1	Opens Window 5.15	Witness-isInterpretedBy-Stanza-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)+ content.line
Interpretative edition	1	1	Opens Window 5.15	Witness-isConsideredBy-Stanza-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)+ content.line
Short name editor of paleographic edition	1	1	Opens Window 5.15	Stanza-hasEditor-Person + name.Person
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.16	Stanza-isPart-Redaction-considers-Witness-isRepresentedIn-Facsimile
EDITION	M			Stanza-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person+ name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.17	Stanza-isEditedIn-Location
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.18	<i>Stays in the same Entity</i>
WORK	M			Stanza-isPart-Redaction
short-title of work	1	1	Opens Window 5.9	altTitle.Redaction
Internal Num of stanza	1	1	Opens Window 5.9	<i>Not relevant</i>
Number of stanza in work	1	1	Opens Window 5.9	stanzaNumber.Stanza
Next stanza in work	1	1	Not the work at hand but the work of the menu. Opens Window 5.11	Stanza-nextStanza-Stanza
Previous Stanza in work	1	1	Not the work at hand but the work of the menu. Opens Window 5.11	Stanza-previousStanza-Stanza

Table 5.11 presents the data needs of Window 5.12. This window presents all the sources (Manuscripts) that are related to the whole work or parts of the work (separated).

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.11 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 5.11: Data elements of Window 5.12

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
EDITION	M			Redaction-retrievesText-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person+ name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
SOURCE	M			Redaction-considers-Witness
Siglum of the manuscript	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	siglum.Witness
Folios	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	location.Witness

Table 5.12 presents the data needs of Window 5.13. This Window presents the introduction of the edition of a work and references.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.12 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction

Table 5.12: Data elements of Window 5.13

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Introduction	1			commentary.Redaction
REFERENCE	M			Redaction-isReferencedIn-BibliographicSource
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person + name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			scope.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource

Table 5.13 presents the data needs of Window 5.14. This window presents the apparatus.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.13 is related to the entity “Word” and “Apparatus” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to these entities is:

- Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)-hasFirstToken-Word(-nextToken-Word)-isMentionedIn-Apparatus
- Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)-isAnalysedThrough-Apparatus

Table 5.13: Data elements of Window 5.14

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Contents of the stanza that contains the variant	1			content.Line

Continued on next page

Table 5.13 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Translation EN of the stanza that contains the variant	1			paraphrasis@en.Stanza
Lemma (apparatus)	1			lemma.Apparatus
<i>Locus</i> (apparatus)	1			location.Apparatus
Variant (apparatus)	1			Apparatus–hasReading–Reading + variant.Reading
Location of the variant	1	1		Apparatus–hasReading–Reading– isReadingOf–Witness + siglum.Witness
Notes	1			criticalNotes.Apparatus
Word-Translation EN	1			translation@en.Word
Lemma of the lexeme	1	1	Opens Window 5.19	lemma.Word
Short Name of author	1			Stanza–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Short title of work	1			Stanza–isFirstStanzaOf–Redaction + altTitle.Redaction
Morphological classification	1			morphologicalAnnotation.Word
Notes on grammar	1			<i>Not relevant</i>

Table 5.14 presents the data needs of Window 5.15. This window presents the text in the manuscript.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.14 is related to the entities “Stanza”, “Witness” and “Facsimile” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to these entities is:

- Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)
- Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–considers–Witness
- Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–considers–Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile

Table 5.14: Data elements of Window 5.15

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Paleographic edition	1			Witness–isInterpretedBy– Stanza
				Stanza–hasFirstLine– Line(–nextLine–Line) + content.Line
Facsimile of stanza	M		An image has a link that opens the facsimile in a higher definition	Witness–isReproducedIn– Facsimile
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Folio	1			location.Witness
Author Name	1			Stanza–hasCreator– Person + altName.Person
—	1	1	A link that opens Window 5.11	Stanza–interprets– Witness–isReproducedIn– Facsimile
Continued on next page				

Table 5.14 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
—	1	1	A link that opens Window 5.7 – goes back to the manuscript (to which the witness belongs)	Witness-isPart-PrimarySource
Short name of editor of paleographic edition	1	1	Opens Window 5.20	Stanza-hasEditor-Person

Table 5.15 presents the data needs of Window 5.17. This window presents the iterative screen of the stanza.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.15 is related to the entity “Stanza” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)

Table 5.15: Data elements of Window 5.17

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Content	M	1	Content of the stanza (paleographic edition). Opens Window 5.21	Stanza-hasFirstLine-Line(-nextLine-Line)+content.Line
Translation in English	M	1	Contains <i>kennings</i> – see Window 5.36	paraphrasis@en.Stanza

Table 5.16 presents the data needs of Window 5.18. This window presents the content of the “full text” tab of Window 5.11.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.16 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-hasFirstStanza-Stanza(-nextStanza-Stanza)-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource

Table 5.16: Data elements of Window 5.18

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person + name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			scope.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource

Table 5.17 presents the data needs of Window 5.19. This window presents an entry of the dictionary of the Old Norse Skaldic Poetry.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.17 is related to the entity “Word” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine–Line)–hasFirstToken–Word(–nextToken–Word)

Table 5.17: Data elements of Window 5.19

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Lemma	1			lemma.Word
URL	M	1	External link for an entry in a dictionary	Word–isReferencedIn–Location+url.Location
LINE	M			Word–isMentionedIn–Line
Content of the citation	1		Opens Window 5.14, with the apparatus.	content.Line
Siglum	M		Of the manuscript where the citation is	Redaction–interprets–Witness + siglum.Witness
Number of Line	1			lineNumber.Line
Number of Stanza	1			stanzaNumber.Stanza
Short name of author	1			Stanza–hasCreator–Person + altName.Person
Short title of work	1			altTitle.Redaction
Translation of excerpt	1			+ paraphrasis@en.Stanza

Table 5.18 presents the data needs of Window 5.20. This window presents all the editions of a specific author (Skald).

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.18 is related to the entity “Person” (as editor) of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasEditor–Person

Table 5.18: Data elements of Window 5.20

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Name of editor	1	1		name.Person
Short name of editor	1	1		altName.Person
Biography of editor	1	1		biography.Person
EDITED ITEM	M			—
EDITED STANZA	M			Person–isEditor–BibliographicSource
Volume Number	1	1	Opens Window 5.11	volumeNumber.BibliographicSource
POEM/STANZA GROUP	M			BibliographicSource–refersThrough–Location–edits–Stanza
Author name	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	Stanza–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Work title	1	1	Opens Window 5.8	Stanza–isPart–Redaction + title.Redaction
Individual Stanza	M	1	Opens Window 5.9	BibliographicSource–refersThrough–Location–edits–Stanza + <i>URI instance Stanza</i>

Table 5.19 presents the data needs of Window 5.21. This window presents the lemma of a word.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.19 is related to the entity “Word” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(–nextStanza–Stanza)–hasFirstLine–Line(–nextLine–Line)–hasFirstToken–Word(–nextToken–Word)

Table 5.19: Data elements of Window 5.21

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Word	1			content.Word
Meaning in English	1			translation.Word
Siglum	1		Of the manuscript where the work (where the word appears) is located	Word–isMentionedIn–Line–isPart–Redaction–interprets–Witness + siglum.Witness
WORD	1			Word–isInflectedForm–Word
Lemma	1	1	Opens Window 5.19	content.Word
Lemma in English	1			translation.Word

Window 5.22 presents the “prose” tab of Window 5.17. This analysis is out of context of the project POSTDATA.

5.2.2 Runic Poetry

Table 5.20 presents the data needs of Window 5.23. This window presents a list of works organised by region.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.19 is related to the entity “Opus” of the POSTDATA Domain Model.

Table 5.20: Data elements of Window 5.23

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Word	M	1	Content in prose of the stanza (paelographic edition). Opens Window 5.21	
Period name	1			literaryPeriod.Opus
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.4	<i>(filter per literaryPeriod.Opus)</i>
REGION	M			Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource
Information about the text	1		Opens Window 5.27	<i>no information available</i>
Total number of works	1		Of the region.	<i>Redundant</i>
Name of the region	M			PrimarySource–comesFrom–Place + region.Place
WORK	M			PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness–isConsideredBy–Redaction
ID work	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	<i>URI instance Redaction</i>

Continued on next page

Table 5.20 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Incipit	1	0	Of the critical edition of the text	incipit.Redaction

Table 5.21 presents the data needs of Window 5.24. This window presents the Regions with Works.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.21 is related to the entity “Place” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource–comesFrom–Place

Table 5.21: Data elements of Window 5.24

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
REGION	M			—
Name of the region	1		Opens Window 5.28	region.Place
Name of the period	1		Opens Window 5.28	literaryPeriod.Opus
Total number of works	1		On that region. Opens Window 5.28	<i>Redundant. Connection to works:</i> Place–isTheOrigin–PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness–isConsideredBy–Redaction

Table 5.22 presents the data needs of Window 5.25. This window presents a complete list of the editions of runes ordered by siglum.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.22 is related to the entity “Witness” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness

Table 5.22: Data elements of Window 5.25

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	siglum.Witness
Place name	1	1	Where the rune is. Opens Window 5.28	Witness–isPart–PrimarySource–comesFrom–Place + settlement.Place
Incipit	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	incipit.Witness

Table 5.23 presents the data needs of Window 5.26. This window presents a complete list of the editions of Runa Works ordered by siglum.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.23 is related to the entity “Place” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource–comesFrom–Place

Table 5.23: Data elements of Window 5.26

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Place name	1	1	Where the rune is. Opens Window 5.28	settlement.Place
Siglum	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness + siglum.Witness
Incipit	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness + incipit.Witness

Table 5.24 presents the data needs of Window 5.27. This window presents a list of the works that are in Runas located in a certain Region.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.24 is related to the entity “Place” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place

Table 5.24: Data elements of Window 5.27

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
region name	1			region.Place
Siglum	1			Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness + siglum.Witness
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.4	Works from the same region organised by: Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isConsideredBy-Redaction + literaryPeriod.Redaction
Title	1			Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isConsideredBy-Redaction-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + title.BibliographicSource
Notes	1			Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isConsideredBy-Redaction-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + notes.BibliographicSource
WORK	M			Place-isTheOrigin-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isConsideredBy-Redaction
Work ID	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	<i>URI instance Redaction</i>
Critical edition	1			text.Redaction
Critical edition in English	1			paraphrasis.Redaction
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.29	<i>Connects to the PrimarySource of the work: Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource</i>

Table 5.25 presents the data needs of Window 5.28. This window presents the information about the critical

edition.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.25 is related to the entity “Ensemble” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isPart–Ensemble

Table 5.25: Data elements of Window 5.28

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Region name	1			Ensemble–comesFrom–Place + region.Place
Information of critical edition	1			notes.Ensemble
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.23	Connection with Region: Ensemble–comesFrom–Place + region.Place
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.27	Connection with the Ensemble: Ensemble–hasPart–Redaction
Content (critical edition)	1			Ensemble–hasFirstOpus–Opus(–nextOpus–Opus)–isRealisedThrough–Redaction + text.Redaction
SOURCE	M			Ensemble–hasFirstOpus–Opus(–nextOpus–Opus)–isRealisedThrough–Redaction –considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource
Rune ID	1	1	Opens Window 5.30	URI instance PrimarySource
Source ID	1			siglum.PrimarySource
Facsimile thumbnail	1			Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile + url.Facsimile
EDITION or TEXT	M			Redaction–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource–hasEditor–Person + name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			scope.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource

Table 5.26 presents the data needs of Window 5.29. This window presents the information about the critical edition.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.26 is related to the entity “Ensemble” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isPart–Ensemble

Table 5.26: Data elements of Window 5.29

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Region name	1			Ensemble–comesFrom–Place + region.Place
Short name of the region	1			<i>Not relevant</i>
Period name	1	1	Opens Window 5.23	Ensemble–hasPart–Redaction–realises–Opus + literaryPeriod.Opus

Continued on next page

Table 5.26 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
—	1	1	Opens Window 5.27	Ensemble–hasPart–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource
EDITION or TEXT	M			Ensemble–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Editor	M			BibliographicSource–hasEditor–Person + name.Person
Year	1			date.BibliographicSource
Place of publication	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			scope.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
RUNA	M			Ensemble–hasPart–Redaction–considers–Witness
Runa ID	1	1	Opens Window 5.31	siglum.Witness

Table 5.27 presents the data needs of Window 5.30. This window presents the thumbnails of the facsimiles of a specific rune.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.27 is related to the entity “Witness” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness

Table 5.27: Data elements of Window 5.30

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Runa ID	1	1	Opens Window 5.28	<i>URI instance Witness</i>
Source ID	1	1	Opens Window 5.31	siglum.Witness
Facsimile miniature	M	1	Opens Window 5.32	Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile + url.Facsimile

Table 5.28 presents the data needs of Window 5.31. This window presents the information on the paleographic edition.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.27 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–considers–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 5.28: Data elements of Window 5.31

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Rune ID	1			PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness <i>URI instance Witness</i>
Technique	1		Of the support.	writingTechnique.PrimarySource
Date	1			date.PrimarySource

Continued on next page

Table 5.28 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Region	1			PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place + region.Place
Country	1			PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place + country.Place
Place	1			PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place + settlement.Place
Paleographic edition	1			PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isInterpretedBy-Redaction + text.Redaction
Paleographic edition Translation EN	1			paraphrasis@en.Redaction
Localisation	1			PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place + longitude.Place & latitude.Place
ID Critical edition	1	1	Opens window 5.28	Win-PrimarySource-hasPart-Witness-isInterpretedBy-Redaction-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource <i>URI instance BibliographicSource</i>

Table 5.29 presents the data needs of Window 5.32. This window presents the facsimiles of a rune.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.27 is related to the entity “Witness” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness

Table 5.29: Data elements of Window 5.32

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Facsimile	M			Witness-isReproducedIn-Facsimile
CRITICAL EDITION	M			Witness-isConsideredIn-Redaction
Alternative Title	1	1	Opens window 5.28	Win-Redaction-isEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + altTitle.BibliographicSource
Incipit	1	1	Opens window 5.28	Win-incipit.Redaction

5.2.3 Authors

Table 5.30 presents the data needs of Window 5.33. This window presents the works by a specific author.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.30 is related to the entity “Person” (as an author) of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-hasCreator-Person

Table 5.30: Data elements of Window 5.33

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Author name	1			name.Person
Author shortname	1			altName.Person
WORK	M			Opus

Continued on next page

Table 5.30 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Total number of stanzas	1			<i>Redundant</i>
Information and Texts	1	1	Opens Window 5.7	Connects with PrimarySource of the work: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-considers-Witness-isPart-PrimarySource
STANZA	M			Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction
Stanza number	M	1	Order of Stanza in work. Opens Window 5.8	stanzaNumber.Stanza
Stanza Incipit	M	1	Opens Window 5.8	incipit.Redaction
EDITION	1			Person-authorIsEditedIn-Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource
Editor name	1	1	Opens Window 5.20	BibliographicSource-hasEditor-Person + name.Person
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Publisher	1			publisher.BibliographicSource
Volume	1			volumeNumber.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			scope.BibliographicSource
Place of Edition	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Biography	1			biography.Person

5.2.4 Kennings

Table 5.31 presents the data needs of Window 5.35. This window presents information about the *kennings*.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 5.31 is related to the entity “FigureOfSpeech” of the POSTDATA Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-presents-FigureOfSpeech (device.FigureOfSpeech =kenning)

Table 5.31: Data elements of Window 5.35

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Category name	1			category.FigureOfSpeech
KENNING	1			FigureOfSpeech-isPresentIn-Redaction
ID of the work	1		Where the <i>kenning</i> appears.	<i>URI instance Redaction</i>
Paleographic edition	1		Opens Window 5.35	text.Redaction & typeOfRedaction.Redaction =paleographic
Kenning	1			periphrasis.FigureOfSpeech
Translation	1			periphrasisReferent.FigureOfSpeech
Meaning	1			periphrasisTranslation.FigureOfSpeech
—	1			FigureOfSpeech-hasPart-FigureOfSpeech

Chapter 6

Nederlandse liederenbank

URL: <http://www.liederenbank.nl>

6.1 Informational Needs

Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2 present the entry page of the Dutch Song Database.

Figure 6.1: Window 6.1: Dutch Song Database FrontPage – with the drop down box for search expanded

Figure 6.2: Dutch Song Database FrontPage – with the drop down box “sort by” expanded

Figure 6.1 shows that Window 6.1 allows the user to perform searches in Songs or Sources (i.e. songbooks, manuscripts, broadsides, field recordings). Regarding the searches in Songs, the user can search by:

- Word(s)
- Title: is the designation of the genre of the song, or its contents as written above the proper text. E.g. “Een oudt liedeken” (*An Old Song*), “Herders-klacht van Philander en zijne liefste Dorinde” (*Shepherd’s Complaint Of Philander And His Beloved Dorinde*), “De Zilvervloot” (*The Silver Fleet*), “Mamma’s ziekbed” (*Mother’s Sickbed*), or “Goal! die zit” (*Goal! The Ball Is In*).
- First Line (incipit): is the first verse of the first stanza of the song text
- Tune indication: tonality of the song

- Author: this field may contain the writer of the lyrics, but also the composer of the melody, the arranger or translator. In the case of 16th and 17th century songs, it could refer the motto of the author or of its Chamber of Rhetoric. In the case of contemporary popular music, you may also find the name of the singer.
- Keyword: most of the songs have at least one keyword associated to them: the genre or type of song.
- Stanza form: the number of accents per line, the rhyme scheme and the gender of the rhymes, whether masculine (upper case) or feminine (lower case).
- Recording place

Regarding searches in Sources, the user may search by:

- Words
- Title

Figure 6.2 shows that Window 6.1 also allows to sort the result of the search by:

- First line
- Year
- Siglum

The first page has two links to advanced searches:

- Stanzas (see Figure 6.3)
- Melody (see Figure 6.4)

Searching for stanza forms enter 3 characters or more in at least 1 field: [examples](#)

search field	example	explanation
rhyme scheme	ababcbcd	equal rhyme sounds get the same letter
accents	34343434	the number of accents per verse line
rhyme gender	vmvmvmvm	m=masculine rhyme (last syllable of the line stressed) v=feminine (last syllable unstressed)
key words		words from the title, first line, the author, etc.

search method

exact match if wanted, use an asterisk (*) to truncate individual fields

starts with all fields are truncated

sort by

stanza form = rhyme scheme + accents + rhyme gender

stanza form without rhyme gender

rhyme scheme

rhyme scheme without rhyme gender

accents

year

standard name melody

tune indication

Figure 6.3: Window 6.2: Search Stanza

Figure 6.3 shows that on Window 6.2 it is possible to look for:

- Rhyme scheme
- Accents
- Rhyme gender
- Keywords

It is also possible to sort by:

- Stanza form
- Stanza form without rhyme gender
- Rhyme scheme
- Rhyme scheme without rhyme gender
- Accents
- Year
- Standard name melody
- Tune indication

Search Melody

JavaScript keyboard used with permission from *Musipedia*

Figure 6.4: Window 6.3: Search Melody

Figure 6.4 shows that on Window 6.3 it is possible to look for a song based on a melody (or partial melody). This melody is created by the user using the JavaScript keyboard of the MusiPedia¹. The search function will search a similar melody among the songs available on the database.

6.1.1 Search Source

Figure 6.5 presents the sources that match the criteria of search performed on the window of Figure 6.1, using [“meisje” AND “title (sources)” sort by “year“] as criteria of search.

For each source the result of the search presents the following information:

- Siglum – link to the window of Figure 6.6
- Title
- Name of author
- Place
- Publisher
- Year: the year can be represented in three different ways: XXXX, XXXX-XXXX or ca.XXXX, where “XXXX” represents a year.
- Mus.: boolean that informs if the source has musical notation
- Song: the total number of songs of the source available in the DB² – link to the Window of Fig 6.7 which is the same as the window of Figure 6.9. This Window will be analysed later (see Section 6.1.2).
- Scan: the facsimile of the source – link to an external database (website).

Figure 6.6 presents Window 6.5 which has detailed information about a source. This window has the following informational needs:

- the siglum of the source

¹See http://www.musipedia.org/js_piano.html

²The total number of songs of the source is presented in another screen (see Fig 6.6).

siglum title author	place printer year	mus. song* scan
NeeitjeJaspers1610 Aen Neeiken Jaspers, een Meysjen van 17. [...]	[1610]	6
Melkmeisje1771 HET NIEUW Klugtig en zeer Aangenaam Zingende [...]	Amsterdam Putte, Erve H. van der 1771	42
Melkmeisje1779 HET NIEUW Klugtig en zeer Aangenaam zingende [...]	Amsterdam Putte, Erve H. van der 1779	
Melkmeisje1780 Het Nieuw, Klugtig en zeer Aangenaam [...]	Amsterdam Koene, S. en W. [1780 ca.]	
Lbi KB Wouters 08175 Het Matrozen Meisje	[18e eeuw]	1 scan
Lbi KB Wouters 10156 KLAGT-LIED Of troost aan een MEISJE	Amsterdam (Anjellersgracht) Wendel, J. 1795-1819	2 scan
VnNederlander1799 De vrolyke Nederlander, Zingende met zyn [...]	Amsterdam Koene 1799	
VnNederlander1800 DE VROLYKE NEDERLANDER, ZINGENDE MET ZYN [...]	Amsterdam Koene, S en W. 1800	25

Figure 6.5: Window 6.4: Dutch Song Database FrontPage – Result after search in Sources

source:	VnNederlander1800										
title:	DE VROLYKE NEDERLANDER, ZINGENDE MET ZYN INCÉABLE MEISJE DE HEDENDAAGSCHE LIEDEREN. Nooit te voeren gedrukt										
address:	TE AMSTELDAM, By S. en W. KOENE, Boekdruckers, En Papierverkoopers, op de Linde-gragt. 1800										
year:	1800										
druk/uitgave:	Amsterdam: Koene, S en W. (uitgave)										
music:	without musical notation										
number of songs:	25 25 entered in the Dutch Song Database										
type:	print. liedboek.										
literature:	Schl., p. 221										
Scheurleer:	3445 (p. 222-1)										
copy used:	Gent UB: BL 8401										
available:	scan (books.google.nl) scan (books.google.nl)										
available:	full text (DBNL.org) download pdf (DBNL.org)										
copies (2):	Gent UB: BL 8401 Leiden UB: 1197 G 63										
comment:	Dit is een ander liedboek dan 'De vrolijke Nederlander, Zingende en Speelende de Aangenaamste Liederen, die hedendaags Gezongen worden' (Amsterdam, B. Koene, c. 1814).										
	songs in this source (25)										
2 drukken:	<table> <tr> <td>VnNederlander1799</td> <td>De vrolyke Nederlander, [...]</td> <td>Amsterdam / Koene / 1799</td> <td>25</td> <td>www.earlydutchbooksonline.nl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>VnNederlander1800</td> <td>DE VROLYKE NEDERLANDER, [...]</td> <td>Amsterdam / Koene, S en W. / 1800</td> <td>25</td> <td>DBNL.org books.google.nl</td> </tr> </table>	VnNederlander1799	De vrolyke Nederlander, [...]	Amsterdam / Koene / 1799	25	www.earlydutchbooksonline.nl	VnNederlander1800	DE VROLYKE NEDERLANDER, [...]	Amsterdam / Koene, S en W. / 1800	25	DBNL.org books.google.nl
VnNederlander1799	De vrolyke Nederlander, [...]	Amsterdam / Koene / 1799	25	www.earlydutchbooksonline.nl							
VnNederlander1800	DE VROLYKE NEDERLANDER, [...]	Amsterdam / Koene, S en W. / 1800	25	DBNL.org books.google.nl							
	<small>NB bij de inventarisatie van bronnen tot 1600 is volledigheid nagestreefd, bij jongere bronnen niet.</small>										

Figure 6.6: Window 6.5: Detailed information about a source

- the title of the source
- the year of the source: The year can be represented in for different ways: XXXX, XXXX-XXXX or ca.XXXX, where “XXXX” represents a year, or free text (e.g. “middle XV century”).
- music: boolean informing whether the musical notation is available
- publisher
- place
- print
- number of songs
- number of songs in the DB – a link that opens the window of Figure 6.9
- notes on the number of songs in the DB
- collation
- type
- editions – each edition has a link that opens the window of Figure 6.8
- copy used
- copy/repro. Meertens
- available
- copies
- reference of Scheurleer

first line author title source	tune indication standard name of this melody stanza form	mus. mp3 scan
<p>Ick wensche u veel genaed' en vree', / So Paulus, [...]</p> <p>NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A1r [nr. 1]</p>	<p>Het waren 3. Gespeekens goet <i>Het waren twee gespelen goed</i></p>	
<p>Sterckt my o Godt mijn Heer / Want ick ben swack [...]</p> <p>Een Schriftuurlijck Liet NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A2r [nr. 2]</p>	<p>Van den 3. Psalm. Hoe veel is des volcks Heere <i>Psalm 003 Datheen</i></p>	
<p>Ick roepe tot u o schepper mijn / Waer sal ick sijn</p> <p>NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A4v [nr. 3]</p>	<p>een Meysken op een revierken sat <i>Een meisje op een riviertje zat</i></p>	
<p>Dit Liedeken van my uyt liefde jent / Is aen u [...]</p> <p>Een nieu Liedeken NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A5v [nr. 4]</p>	<p>Ai is het vleys gelijk een gras, die Heer [...]</p>	
<p>O Heer wilt my hooren / En neycht daer toe u Ooren</p> <p>Een nieu Liedeken NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A7r [nr. 5]</p>	<p>En straft my niet O Heere <i>Psalm 006 Datheen</i></p>	
<p>Siet hoe fijn, en hoe liefelijck mede / End' hoe [...]</p> <p>Mander, Karel van] Den 133. Psalm NeeltjeJaspers1610 ([1610]), A8r [nr. 6]</p>	<p>Hy mach wel vrolijck weesen etc. <i>Hij mag wel vrolijk wezen</i></p>	

Figure 6.7: List of songs in a source

- notes
- other sources of the same collection. Each source is identified with:
 - siglum
 - title
 - name of authors
 - year
 - external link to facsimile. It provides the URL of the link.

Figure 6.8 presents Window 6.6 with the edition of a book. This Window has the following informational needs:

- ID of the book
- authors of the book
- title of the book
- year of edition (and of re-editions)
- place of publication
- number of songs in the DB
- type of book
- copy used
- copy/repro. Meertens
- notes/comments

source:	Schl
authors:	D.F. Scheurleer (samensteller) R. Rasch (co-auteur)
title:	Nederlandsche Liedboeken: lijst der in Nederland tot het jaar 1800 uitgegeven liedboeken. Ongewijzigde herdruk met een voorwoord van R. Rasch. Utrechtse herdrukken 15.
year:	1912 (1977)
druk/uitgave:	Utrecht
print:	1
number of songs:	0 entered in the Dutch Song Database
type:	print. editie/secundaire literatuur. Bibliografie (meestal 1 vindplaats per druk). Liedboeken gedrukt in Nederland.
copy used:	3978 1 c A Alg/Bibl.
copy/repro. Meertens:	3978 1 c A Alg/Bibl.
comment:	In 1977 verscheen een ongewijzigde herdruk, met een voorwoord van Rudi Rasch, bij HES publishers, Utrecht.

Figure 6.8: Window 6.6: A bibliographic entry

6.1.2 Search Song

Figure 6.9 presents the songs that match the criteria of search conducted on Window 6.1 – Figure 6.1, using [“jongen” AND “first line (songs)” sort by “year”] as criteria of search.

first line author title source	tune indication standard name of this melody stanza form	mus. mp3 scan
Wat is de werelt met al haer rijckdom, / Eere [...] Twisck KLB1633 (1633), p343 [nr. 131]	Van den 104 Psalm Psalm 104 Datheen	dbnl
Laet ons dat kindeken wiegen, / Dat herts tom [...] GHarmonie1637 (1637), p34 [nr. 28]	[geen wijsaanduiding] .3a.3b.3c.3b.2c.2c	dbnl
Tom Tinker [inst.] Playford EDM1651 (1651), p88 [nr. 88]	Tom Tinker Tom Tinker	♩
Verblij u ghy Batavieren, / Maeckt vreughden om en tom Vreugde Lied. op het Edel Houwelijck van sijn [...] NiAmMinnebeekje1680 ([1679+]), p70 [nr. 27]	Als 't Begint Verblij u gij Batavieren .3a.3b.3a.3b.2c.2c.3d.3e.3e.3f.3f	dbnl
Verheugt u Batavieren, / Maeckt blijdschap om en tom ECHT-GROET, Aen Willem Henrick Prince d'Orange. [...] CMaagdenkruid1685 (1685), p9 [nr. 4]	[geen wijsaanduiding] Verblij u gij Batavieren .3a.3b.3a.3b.2c.2c.3d.2e.2e.3f.3f	dbnl
Sa, sa Neerlande, / Maeckt vreugde om en tom Een Nieuw Lied van de Batalje die is [...] Beginhof1710 (1710), p71 [nr. 38]	Van de Kwezel Hoor Kees mijn vierjer	
Hoe minn' ik u, ó nutte en fraale Boeken! / Wat [...] Riemsnyder, H. AAN DE BOEKEN Riemsnyder Liedjeskinderen1781 (1781), p78 [nr. 61]	Amour, Amour, qu'elle est donc ta puissance Amour, amour, quelle est donc ta puissance .5a.4b.4a.4b.4c.4d.4c.4d	dbnl
Wat doet de gaaf my smaaken / Aan dien armen [...] Riemsnyder, H. HET VERMAAK VAN WELDOEN Riemsnyder Liedjeskinderen1781 (1781), p80 [nr. 62]	Ami, qu'en mes bras je presse .3a.4b.3a.4b.3c.4d.4d.4e.2e.4f.4e.4f.4g	dbnl
Luister Vrienden allemaal, / Wat ik u zal verhaalen Een Nieuw Lied DrieKemp1784 (1784), p35 [nr. 15]	Op een Aardige Wys 4a.3b.4a.3b.2c.2d.1d.2c.2d.1e.1e	dbnl
Men weet dat de zonde erfelijk is / Al van de [...] Long Tom Nieuwe voordracht [...] LBI KB Wouters 04190 ([19e eeuw]), f21 [nr. 1]	[geen wijsaanduiding]	scan

Figure 6.9: Window 6.7: Dutch Song Database FrontPage – Result after search in Songs

For each song the result of the search presents the following information:

- first line (incipit) – a link that opens the window of Figure 6.10
- name of author
- title
- source: siglum of the source (e.g. manuscript) where the song is located
- tune indication
- standard name of the melody
- incipit of the transcription
- stanza form
- incipit of the musical notation
- mus.: informs if the song has musical notation
- mp3: audio file of the song in mp3 format – link that opens window of Figure 6.14
- scan: link to the facsimile of the transcription (external or internal)
- edition: name of the database that has the edition of the song (with link)
- transcription – a link to the window of Figure 6.11

Figure 6.10 presents Window 6.8 that shows the details of a song. The Window has the following informational needs:

- About the song:
 - incipit
 - incipit normalised
 - refrain
 - number of stanzas
 - all songs with the same lyrics:
 - * total number of texts
 - * warning that informs that the Window to be opened has additional information
 - * link to the window of Figure 6.12. This Window is similar to the window of Figure 6.9 but with additional information:
 - text that explains the context/contents of the source for the lyrics of the listed songs.
 - title of the text in common
 - music: boolean that indicates whether the song has musical notation
 - link to the full text. It is possible to have both of the following options, or one of them:
 - * information about the source of the full text referred (e.g. “dbnl” and a link to open the external link)

song:			
<i>first line:</i>	Ik hoorde claghen enen jonghen / Tote sijre liefster vrouwen reine		<i>all songs with this text</i>
<i>text norm:</i>	Ik hoorde klagen een jongen Tot zijn liefste vrouwe rein		(1 song)
<i>refrain:</i>	[var] ghenen raet [v8]; [var] een gheminnen can [v8]		
<i>no. of stanzas:</i>	5		
<i>music:</i>	with musical notation		
<i>link (full text):</i>	text dbrnl after the edition Heeroma 1966		
<i>genre:</i>	liefdesklacht / dialooglied (wereldlijk)		
<i>keyword:</i>	jongen <-> vrouwe		
<i>melody name:</i>	<i>tune indication:</i> [geen wijsaanduiding]	<i>standard name of this melody:</i> Ik hoorde klagen een jongen ↕	<i>all songs sung to this melody</i> (1 song)
<i>stanza form:</i> 4a 4b 4a 3b 4b 4b 4C 4C		<i>all songs with this stanza form</i> (all songs)
<i>no. of verses:</i>	8		
<i>comment:</i>	Alternerend refrein.		
<i>record ID:</i>	24845		
source:			
<i>siglum:</i>	HsGruuthuse (1390 - 1400)		
<i>title:</i>	Gruuthuse-handschrift		
<i>page:</i>	f22v (song number 68)		
<i>copy used:</i>	Koolkerke (thans Den Haag)		
<i>edition:</i>	Heeroma 1966, 374		
<i>available:</i>	scan of the full source (www.kb.nl)		

Figure 6.10: Window 6.8: Detail of a song

- * link to local window – see Figure 6.13
- notes about the full text
- genre
- keyword
- melody name
- tune indication
- standard name of the melody
- total number of songs with the same melody – link to window of Figure 6.9 with the list of the songs
- stanza form
- number of verses
- notes
- record ID (A number)
- total number of songs with the same stanza form – link to window of Figure 6.9 with the list of songs
- About the source:
 - siglum – a link that opens window of Figure 6.6
 - date (the same possibilities as already referred before)
 - title
 - folio
 - number of song in source
 - copy used
 - editions – opens window of Figure 6.8
 - scan of the full source (external link; information about the repository)

Figure 6.11 presents Window 6.9. This window gives the musical transcription of a song and has the following informational needs:

- siglum (source)
- name of author
- incipit
- second line
- musical notation (image)

Figure 6.12 presents Window 6.10 with a list of songs that have as source the same text/narrative. This Window has the same information needs as the Window of Figure 6.9 and still:

- title of the text that is common
- notes on the text
- full text, of the text that is common.

LV. VAN TWEE KONINGS KINDEREN
 Het waren twee koningskinderen / Zij hadden malkander zo lief

Het waren twee conincskinderen, / Sy hadden malcan [...]

Figure 6.11: Window 6.9: The transcription of a song

Het waren twee koningskinderen Zij hadden malkander zo lief

Verhalend lied. Twee koningskinderen hebben elkaar lief. Zij kunnen elkaar niet krijgen, want het water dat hen scheidt is te diep. De jongen verdrinkt in zee. Het meisje laat hem opduiken en verdrinkt zich vervolgens ook.

De oudst opgetekende variant in de Nederlanden dateert van ca. 1525, in het handschrift Meerman. Ook in Het oudt Haerlemsch Liedboek van 1640 vinden we een schriftelijke weerslag van dit lied.

Het lied over de twee koningskinderen kent een brede verspreiding in Duitstalige gebieden (deel uitmakend van de "Schwimmersage") en Scandinavië en was in deze streken, evenals in Nederland, zeer geliefd. Ook uit Frankrijk zijn liederen bekend met dezelfde onderwerpsstof. Vanaf de veertiende eeuw deden in Europa talrijke verhalen met dit thema de ronde, maar de Griekse mythologie kent al de geschiedenis van de ongelukkige liefde tussen Hero en Leander, die aan beide zijden van de Hellespont woonden.

De 17e eeuwse tekst is via volksliedbundels in de twintigste eeuw onder de middenklasse bekend geraakt. Als Doornbos heeft in het hele land vele opnames uit de mondelinge overlevering gemaakt, waarbij de diversiteit aan melodielijnen opvalt.

Ook is het lied in Nederland via 19e eeuwse liedbladen verspreid geraakt.

tekst

first line author title source	tune indication standard name of this melody stanza form	mus. mp3 scan
Tusschen se berch hoghe / Daer leit een water vijt [!] Dit lydekijn gaet op die wijse [...] Ende is van [...] HsBskB II2631-B ([1525 ca.]), f99v [nr. 33]	Ic sie die morghe sterre <i>Ik zie de morgenster</i> .3a.3b.3c.3b.3c.3b	txt
Het waeren twee Konings kinderen / Zy hadden [...] Van twee Konings Kinderen HOLb1640 ([1640 ca. / 1630-1640]), p45 [nr. 29]	Wilt tsamen nu, &c. .3a.3b.3c.3b	dbnl
Wie wil hooren Zingen, / Van vreugde een nieu [...] Een nieuw Liedeken Coll Nijhoff ([1700 ca.]), p629 [nr. 275]	als 't begint .3a.3b.3c.3b	dbnl
Het waren twe conincskinderen, / sy hadden [...] VI. Van twe conincskinderen HoraeBelgicae HVI1833 (1833), p112 [nr. 34]	[geen wijsaanduiding]	
Et wassen twe künigeskinner, / de hadden enanner so lief 91 Uhland Volkslieder(1) (z.), p134 [nr. 10]	[geen wijsaanduiding]	
Het waren twee conincskinderen, / Sy hadden [...] LV. VAN TWEE KONINGS KINDEREN Willems OVLd1848 (1848), p142 [nr. 49]	[geen wijsaanduiding] Daar waren twee koningskinderen (2) 	dbnl transcr.

Figure 6.12: Window 6.10: List of songs based on the same text/narrative

Figure 6.13 presents Window 6.11 with the complete text of the song and some other information:

- complete text
- notes
- date of the source
- siglum of the source
- place (library where the source is preserved)
- other places where the source was preserved in the past

Figure 6.14 is out of scope of the project.

Maria coninginne
 mijn troest mijn to verlaet
 vercrigt u kindes mynne
 berou van mijn misdaet

des wordic wel geware
 dat u kint myn is goet
 want si kan wel hart verclaren
 ende gheven goeden raet

[handschrift zonder titel]
 midden 15e eeuw
 Reykjavik, National Museum of Iceland (voorheen: árbAEjarsafn Museum?)

Figure 6.13: Window 6.11: full text of a song and notes

CD: Dowland in Holland, 1: 24
Klagte van Jan Jansz. Starter
 C. van Langerack (tekst)
 Camerata Trajectina: Nico van der Meel (tenor); Louis Peter Grijp (luit)

Tekst uit uit D.R. Camphuysens Stichtelycke Rymen (Amsterdam: Jacob Colom 1647);
 melodie uit J.B. Stalpart van der Wiele, Gulde Jaers Feestdagen (Antwerpen 1635)
 tekst

Figure 6.14: Details of a performance of a song (audio)

6.2 Data needs analysis

Window 6.1 is the entry page of the Website, where the user can search for songs or sources of songs. Table 6.1 presents the data needs related to the queries concerning songs.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.1 is related to the entity “Opus” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model.

Table 6.1: Data elements of Window 6.1

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.Opus
Incipit	1			Opus-isRealised-Redaction + incipit.Redaction
Tune indication	1			Redaction-isUsedIn-Performance-hasMelody-Melody + tonality.Melody
Writer	M		Of the lyrics of the song	Opus-hasCreator-Person + name.Person

Continued on next page

Table 6.1 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Translator	M			Opus–hasTranslator–Person + name.Person
Composer	M		Of the melody	Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Arranger	M		Of the melody	Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody–hasArranger–Person + name.Person
Recording Place	1			Performance–isRecordedIn–Place + name.Place
Chamber of Rhetoric	1			<i>Unable to understand</i>
Singer	M			Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasPerformer–Person
Naamspreuk	M			<i>Unable to understand</i>
Word	M			Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction + text.Redaction
Keyword	1		It can have gender or type of song as content	Not relevant
Stanza	1			Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza(nextStanza–Stanza)
Accents per line	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + accentualMetricalScheme .StanzaPattern
Rhyme Scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Gender of rhymes	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + clausulaScheme.StanzaPattern
Year	1			date.Opus
Siglum	1		Of the Witness	Redaction–interprets–Witness + siglum.Witness

Table 6.2 presents the data needs related to the queries concerning sources.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.2 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–interprets–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 6.2: Data elements of Window 6.1

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1			title.Opus
Word	M			Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction + text.Redaction
Year	1			date.PrimarySource
Siglum	1			siglum.PrimarySource

Table 6.3 presents the data needs of Window 6.2.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.2 is related to the entity “Stanza” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasFirstStanza–Stanza–(–nextStanza–Stanza)

Table 6.3: Data elements of Window 6.2

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Accents per line	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + accentualMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern
Rhyme Scheme	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Gender of rhymes	1			Stanza–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern + clausulaScheme.StanzaPattern
Keywords	1			Not relevant
Year	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody + date.Melody
Standard name of the melody	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody + title.Melody
Tune indication	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody + tonality.Melody

Window 6.3 is outside the scope of the POSTDATA project so its contents will not be analysed.

6.2.1 Search Source

Table 6.4 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.4. This Window presents the sources that match the criteria of the search conducted on Window 6.1.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.4 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–interprets–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 6.4: Data elements of Window 6.4

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1	1	Opens Window 6.6.6	siglum.PrimarySource
Title	1			title.PrimarySource
Name of author	M			PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness–isInterpretedBy–Redaction–hasCreator–Person + name.Person

Continued on next page

Table 6.4 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Place	M		It refers both to the current location and previous ones	PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place + name.Place
Publisher	1			publisher.PrimarySource
Year	1		XXXX, XXXX-XXXX, ca.XXXX, free text.	date.PrimarySource
Musical Notation	1		Boolean	hasMusic.PrimarySource
Total number of songs	1		On the DB. Not on the Source.	<i>Not relevant</i>
SCAN	M			PrimarySource-isReproducedIn-Facsimile
URL	1		external or internal to a image	url.Facsimile
Name of the database	1		DB that provides the facsimile (e.g. “dbnl”)	PrimarySource-isReproducedIn-Facsimile-isProvidedBy-Repository+ name.Repository

Table 6.5 presents the informational needs of Window 6.5. This Window provides information with detailed information of a source.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.5 is related to the entity “PrimarySource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus-isRealisedThrough-Redaction-interprets-Witness-isPartOf-PrimarySource

Table 6.5: Data elements of Window 6.5

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1	1		siglum.PrimarySource
Title	1			title.PrimarySource
Place	M		Can keep the information of the different locations in the past until present.	PrimarySource-comesFrom-Place+ name.Place
Publisher	1			publisher.PrimarySource
Year	1		XXXX, XXXX-XXXX, ca.XXXX, free text.	date.PrimarySource
Musical Notation	1		Boolean	hasMusic.PrimarySource
Total number of songs	1	1	On the DB. Opens Window 6.7	<i>Not relevant</i>
Total number of songs in source	1			numberOfWorks.PrimarySource
Notes	1			notes.PrimarySource
Colophon	1			PrimarySource-hasItem-Paratext + typeOfParatext.Paratext (=colophon)
Colophon	1		Contents of the Colophon	content.Paratext

Continued on next page

Table 6.5 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Colophon Location	1		Folio in the PrimarySource	location.Paratext
Collation	1			<i>Unable to understand</i>
Type	1			isPrint.PrimarySource category.PrimarySource
Copy used	1			catalogueNumber.PrimarySource
Copy/repro. Meertens	1			PrimarySource–hasTheSameContent–BibliographicSource + catalogueNumber.BibliographicSource BibliographicSource–belongsTo–Repository + name.Repository(= Meertens)
EDITION	M			PrimarySource–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
URL	1		external or internal to edition	url.BibliographicSource
name of database	1			BibliographicSource–belongsTo–Repository + name.Repository
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Pages	1			numberOfPages.BibliographicSource
FACSIMILE	M			PrimarySource–isReproducedIn–Facsimile
URL	1		external or internal to edition	url.Facsimile
name of database	1			Facsimile–isProvidedBy–Repository + name.Repository
Copies	1			PrimarySource–hasTheSameContent–BibliographicSource + catalogueNumber.BibliographicSource
SCHEURLEER REFERENCE	1			PrimarySource–isCataloguedIn–Location
Reference ID	1			identifier.Location
Page	1			location.Location
Notes	1			notes.PrimarySource
COLLECTION	1			PrimarySource–isPart–Ensemble–hasPart–PrimarySource
Siglum	1			siglum.PrimarySource
Title	1			title.PrimarySource
Year	1			date.PrimarySource
FACSIMILE	M			PrimarySource–isReproducedIn–Facsimile
URL	1		external or internal to edition	url.Facsimile
name of database	1			Facsimile–isProvidedBy–Repository + name.Repository
Songs in Source	1	1	Opens Window 6.7	PrimarySource–hasPart–Witness–isInterpretedBy–Redaction

Table 6.6 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.6. This Window presents details about an edition.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.5 is related to the entity “BibliographicSource” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–interprets–Witness–isPart–PrimarySource

Table 6.6: Data elements of Window 6.6

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
ID	1			<i>URI instance BibliographicSource</i>
Name of author	M			BibliographicSource–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Title	1			title.BibliographicSource
Year	M			firstEditionDate.BibliographicSource date.BibliographicSource
Place	1			pubPlace.BibliographicSource
Number of Songs in the database	1			<i>Not relevant</i>
Type of Book	1			typeOfEdition.BibliographicSource
Copy used	1			<i>In this context, unable to understand this information.</i>
Copy repro. Meertens	1			<i>In this context, unable to understand this information.</i>
notes	1			notes.BibliographicSource

6.2.2 Search Song

Table 6.7 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.7. This Window presents the result after the user searches for a song on the entry page.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.7 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction

Table 6.7: Data elements of Window 6.7

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Incipit	1	1	Opens Window 6.8	incipit.Redaction
Name of author	M			Redaction–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Title	1			title.Redaction
WITNESS	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Page/folio	1			location.Witness
Number of Song in Witness	1			workNumber.Witness
Musical notation	1		Boolean	hasMusicalNotation.Witness
Tune Indication	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody + tonality.Melody
Standard name of the melody	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody + title.Melody
Stanza form	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern

Continued on next page

Table 6.7 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Rhyme Scheme	1			rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Accent	1			accentualMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern
Rhyme Gender	1			StanzaPattern–presents–Rhyme + rhymeType.Rhyme
Incipit of musical notation	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation + firstStaves.MusicalNotation
Audio File	1			Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance + audio.Performance
Facsimile	1		Opens image file (internal or external)	Redaction–interprets–Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile + url.Facsimile
Edition of Song	1		Opens external page	<i>Not relevant.</i>
Transcription	1	1	Opens Window 6.9	Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance–hasMelody–Melody–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation + imageOfTranscription.MusicalNotation

Table 6.8 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.8. This Window presents the detail of a song.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.8 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction

Table 6.8: Data elements of Window 6.8

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Incipit	1			incipit.Redaction
Incipit normalised	1			altTitle.Redaction
Refrain	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + refrain.WorkPattern
Number of Stanzas	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–WorkPattern + numberOfStanzas.WorkPattern
Total number of songs – text	1	1	All songs with the same text. Opens Window 6.10	<i>All instances of “Performance” that point to the same instance of “Redaction” with the property “hasLyrics”</i>
Musical Notation	1		Boolean	Redaction–hasMusic–MusicalNotation + imageOfTranscription.MusicalNotation
Notes	1			notes.Redaction
CONTENT	M			Redaction–isEditedIn–Location–refersAsPart–BibliographicSource
Name of database	1			BibliographicSource–belongsTo–Repository + name.Repository

Continued on next page

Table 6.8 – continued from previous page

Label		Card.	Link	Comments	DM
	URL	1		Opens Window 6.11 or external Window	url.BibliographicSource
Genre		1			genre.Redaction
Melody name		1			Redaction-isUsedIn-Perfomance-hasMusic-Melody + title.Melody
Keyword		1			Not relevant
Tune indication		1			Redaction-isUsedIn-Perfomance-hasMusic-Melody + tonality.Melody
Standard name of the melody		1			Redaction-isUsedIn-Perfomance-hasMusic-Melody + title.Melody
Total number of songs – melody		1		All songs sung with the same melody. Opens Window 6.7	Redaction-isUsedIn-Perfomance-hasMusic-Melody
Stanza form		1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-StanzaPattern
	Rhyme Scheme	1			rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
	Accent	1			accentualMetricalScheme.StanzaPattern
	Rhyme Gender	1			StanzaPattern-presents-Rhyme + rhymeType.Rhyme
Number of verses		1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + numberOfLines.WorkPattern
Notes		1			Redaction-isAnalysedThrough-WorkPattern + metricalNotes.WorkPattern
Record ID		1			<i>URI instance Performance</i>
Total number of songs – stanza form		1		All songs with the same stanza form. Opens Window 6.7	Redaction-isUsedIn-Perfomance-hasMusic-Melody
MANUSCRIPT		1			Redaction-interprets-Witness
	Siglum	1		Opens Window 6.5	siglum.Witness
	Date	1			Witness-isPart-PrimarySource + date.PrimarySource
	Title	1			Witness-isPart-PrimarySource + title.PrimarySource
	Folio	1		Location of the Witness.	location.Witness
	Number of song in source	1			numberOfWork.Witness
	Copy used	1			<i>Not relevant</i>
EDITION		M			Redaction-interprets-Witness-isEditedIn-Location
	Title	1		Opens Window 6.5	Location-refersAsPart-BibliographicSource + title.BibliographicSource
	Location	1			location.Location

Continued on next page

Table 6.8 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
FACSIMILE	M			Redaction–interprets–Witness– isReproducedIn–Facsimile
URL	1		external or internal to edition	url.Facsimile
name of database	1			Facsimile–isProvidedBy–Repository + name.Repository

Table 6.9 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.9. This Window provides the musical notation of a song.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.9 is related to the entity “MusicalNotation” of POST-DATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation

Table 6.9: Data elements of Window 6.9

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1		Source	MusicalNotation–interprets–Witness + siglum.Witness
Name of author	M			MusicalNotation–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Incipit	1			MusicalNotation–represents– Redaction + incipit.Redaction
Second line	1			MusicalNotation–represents– Redaction + firstsLines.Redaction
Page/folio	1			MusicalNotation–interprets–Witness + location.Witness
Number of Song in Witness	1			MusicalNotation–interprets–Witness + workNumber.Witness
Musical Notation	1		Image file	imageOfTranscription.MusicalNotation

Table 6.10 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.10. This Window provides a list with all songs that are based on the same text.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.10 is related to the entity “Performance” of POST-DATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction–isUsedIn–Performance

Table 6.10: Data elements of Window 6.10

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Title	1		Of the base text	Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction + title.Redaction
Notes	1			Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction + notes.Redaction

Continued on next page

Table 6.10 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Full text	1			Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction + text.Redaction
SONG	1			Performance
Incipit	1	1	Opens Window 6.8	Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction + incipit.Redaction
Name of author	M			Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction–hasCreator–Person + name.Person
Title	1			Performance–hasLyrics–Redaction + title.Redaction
WITNESS	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness
Page/folio	1			location.Witness
Number of Song in Witness	1			workNumber.Witness
Tune Indication	1			tonality.Melody
Standard name of the melody	1			Performance–hasMusic–Melody + title.Melody
Stanza form	1			Redaction–isAnalysedThrough–StanzaPattern
Rhyme Scheme	1			rhymeScheme.StanzaPattern
Accent	1			accentualMetricalScheme .StanzaPattern
Rhyme Gender	1			StanzaPattern–presents–Rhyme + rhymeType.Rhyme
Musical notation	1		Boolean	Performance–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation
Incipit of musical notation	1		Image file	Performance–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation + firstStaves.MusicalNotation
Audio File	1			audio.Performance
Facsimile	1		Opens image file (internal or external)	Witness–isReproducedIn–Facsimile + url.Facsimile
Edition of Song	1		Opens external page	<i>Not relevant</i>
Transcription	1	1	Opens Window 6.9	Performance–hasMusicalNotation–MusicalNotation

Table 6.11 presents the informational needs of Windows 6.11. This Window provides the musical notation of a song.

Remark concerning the Domain Model: Table 6.11 is related to the entity “Redaction” of POSTDATA’s Domain Model. The process to “arrive” to this entity is: Opus–isRealisedThrough–Redaction

Table 6.11: Data elements of Window 6.11

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Full text	1			text.Redaction
Notes	1			notes.Redaction
SOURCE	1			Redaction–interprets–Witness
Date	1			Witness–isPart–PrimarySource + date.PrimarySource
Continued on next page				

Table 6.11 – continued from previous page

Label	Card.	Link	Comments	DM
Siglum	1			siglum.Witness (or Witness- isPart-PrimarySource + siglum.PrimarySource)
Place	M		Ordered.	Witness-isPart-PrimarySource- belongsTo-Repository + name.Repository

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